

Euscorpius

Occasional Publications in Scorpiology

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morphological reassessment of the genus
Chaerilus Simon, 1877 in China
(Scorpiones: Chaerilidae)**

Victoria Tang

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Current challenges and preliminary morphological reassessment of the genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 in China (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae)

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Summary

The genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 in China is preliminarily revised on a morphological basis, derived from the available literature and newly examined specimens. The robustness of several commonly applied species-level diagnostic criteria are evaluated. Ten species are provisionally recognized for China, including one new morphospecies, *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., described from 9 females, 40 males, and 2 juvenile females collected in Mèdog County. The current study only reveals and resolves several most elementary issues in the taxonomy of Chinese *Chaerilus*. Further molecular investigations are warranted until topotypes of certain species become available.

Introduction

The genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 belongs to the family Chaerilidae, being the only extant genus of this family (if one were to ignore the dubious genus *Chaerilourencous* Rossi, 2018 that accommodates two anophthalmous *Chaerilus* species; Prendini et al., 2021: 124) representing one of the most ancient scorpion lineages, alongside several fossil records from Burmese amber (e.g., Santiago-Blay et al., 2004; Xuan et al., 2022). This family, together with Buthidae C. L. Koch, 1837, is sister to Pseudochactidae Gromov, 1998 (phylogenetic relationship: [Pseudochactidae + [Buthidae + Chaerilidae]]; Sharma et al., 2015, 2018; Du et al., 2024), collectively forming the parvorder Buthida exhibiting the “primitive” Type 1 sternum, where the posterior depression does not bisect the posterior edge (Soleglad & Fet, 2003a: 8–9, 12). Chaerilids distinguish themselves from all other extant scorpions by their unique Type B orthobothriotaxic trichobothrial pattern (vs. Type A in buthids, Type D in pseudochactids, and Type C in others; Soleglad & Fet, 2003b: 4, 34). Another distinctive character is the distally expanded, spatulate coxapophyses I (= maxillary lobes I), considered an autapomorphy of this lineage (Soleglad & Fet, 2003a: 7). In addition, the non-conjoined median and basal denticles on the dorsal edge of cheliceral fixed finger is also a diagnostic feature, although similar conditions have as well been observed in some Iurida taxa, such as family Troglotayosicidae Lourenço, 1998 (monotypic), subfamily Typhlochactinae Vignoli & Prendini, 2009, and genus *Troglocormus* Francke, 1981 (Soleglad & Fet, 2003b: 32). Intriguingly, these lineages are either endogean or hypogean (troglobites) (Prendini et al., 2021: 129–133). However, the monotypic genus *Somalicharmus* Kovařík, 1998 also has a

non-bicuspid basal denticle (Kovařík et al., 2016: fig. 127), but it is neither endogean nor hypogean (rather, epigean). More recently, Loria & Prendini (2014) also discovered the universal presence of a yellow, elliptical eyespot, situated posteroventral or ventral to the lateral ocelli, in all *Chaerilus* they investigated. Nevertheless, this structure is not unique to this genus.

The genus *Chaerilus* currently comprises 57 species (including 2 *nomina dubia*: *C. lehtrearensis* Khatoon, 1999 and *C. vietnamicus* Lourenço & Zhu, 2008) distributed in the south and southeast Asia (Tang, 2022a; Lourenço & Ythier, 2024). Nine species have been recorded from China, six of which being endemic (Tang, 2025). All Chinese species occur in the forested southeast region of the Tibet Autonomous Region (Xizang), restricted to the Nyingchi and Shannan prefecture-level cities. Notably, the two cities also extend to a politically disputed territory known as “Arunachal Pradesh” (c.f., Wikipedia), where several species were recorded near the southern border with India. Among the countries bordering China to the southwest, only five species have been recorded in proximity (e. g., Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013): *C. assamensis* Kraepelin, 1913 (India), *C. insignis* Pocock, 1894 (India), *C. pictus* (Pocock, 1890) (Bangladesh and India), *C. tricostatus* Pocock, 1899 (India), and *C. truncatus* Karsch, 1879 (India and Nepal). Among these, *C. pictus* and *C. tricostatus* have also been recorded from China (Tang, 2025), while *C. insignis* and *C. truncatus* are distributed in the northwestern India (Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 136, 142; Fet, 2000: 326). Other congeners in nearby countries were recorded even further: *C. andamanensis* Lourenço, Duhem & Leguin, 2011 from the Andaman Islands (India); *C. adrianoi* Lourenço & Ythier, 2024 (Kayin State) and *C. birmanicus* (Thorell, 1899) (Yangon City) from Myanmar.

Figure 1. Map showing the known distribution of Chinese *Chaerilus* species. Black lines represent China national border, downloaded from GitCode. Yellow lines represent county-level division in Nyingchi and Shannan cities, downloaded from Tianditu. Red dash lines represent disputed area (Arunachal Pradesh), downloaded from Natural Earth. The locality of *C. pseudoconchiformis* is represented by the examined adult pair. Localities of *C. conchiformis* include those of an examined specimen, iNaturalist observations, and published records (see text). Localities of other species include those of iNaturalist observations and published records only (see text). Insets: left above corner, closeup of type locality of *C. herta* sp. n.; right bottom corner, localities of the studied *C. cf. tryznai* (white cross) and *C. cf. wrzecionkoi* (white triangle).

Within China, *Chaerilus* is the second diverse scorpion genus trailing behind *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 (Scorpiopidae). The two genera, overlapping in distribution, are also similar in general morphology: relatively small size, typically robust pedipalps, and proportionally short metasoma. However, aside from the aforementioned higher-level characters of *Chaerilus*, it can also be distinguished from *Scorpiops* by several readily perceptible features: (1) the carapace anterior margin is generally straight in *Chaerilus* (can be slightly convex or concave in certain species), while an abrupt anteromedian notch is present in all *Scorpiops* species (e. g., Tang et al., 2024b: figs. 140–147); (2) the carapace is somewhat more elevated and conspicuously widens posteriorly in *Chaerilus*, often with two pairs of strong, continuous carinae (centromedian carina connected with posteromedian carina—henceforth referred to as “centro-posteromedian carina”—anteriorly situated external to the anterolateral carina), while it is more flattened and quadrate with obsolete carinae in *Scorpiops*; (3) the pedipalp chela appears more stereoscopic (either rotund or cuboid) in most *Chaerilus* due to the development of dorsal secondary carina (obsolete in certain species), while this carina is always obsolete in *Scorpiops*. Moreover, Tang (2024b) recently discovered a difference in the configuration of basitarsal compound slit sensilla between the two genera (probably also between their own families), with an additional long “sensillum” present external to the main sensillar area in *Chaerilus*.

A revision of the genus is imperative before advancing further studies or justifying the recognition of new species. The diagnostic characters used to discriminate species, along with the taxonomic status of currently accepted species, require critical reassessment and clarification. This study revises all nine *Chaerilus* species recorded or described from China to date. However, partially due to political tensions in disputed regions, specimens of several species remain unavailable for examination. Finally, a new morphospecies is described from Médog County.

Methods, Material & Abbreviations

Methods. Nomenclature and measurements generally follow Tang (2023, 2024a); pedipalp chela carinae follow Soleglad & Sissom (2001: figs. 43, 46): *E*, external secondary; *D*₁, digital; *D*₃, dorsal secondary carina; *D*₄, dorsal marginal; *D*₅, dorsal internal; *I*, interomedian; *V*₁, ventroexternal; *V*₃, ventrointernal. All comparisons were based on adult specimens. Meristics were expressed with “/” separating left and right counts intrinsic of the animal. Annotations were given in figures to prevent confusions. Diagnoses for previous Chinese *Chaerilus* species were all based on earlier papers. Previous authors’ statements were occasionally cited *verbatim* to minimize information distortion. Corrections to or explanations for the cited paragraphs were given in brackets and not italicized. Maps were generated in QGIS (ver. 3.32.3), using ‘Bing Maps

Satellite Imagery' as the base layer. Vector layers of China national border and administrative divisions employed in QGIS were downloaded respectively from GitCode ([gitcode.com/open-source-toolkit/3a3f0/overview](https://github.com/open-source-toolkit/3a3f0/overview)) and Tianditu (www.tianditu.gov.cn). To facilitate future research, it is essential to incorporate "Arunachal Pradesh" as a separate layer into the map (downloaded from Natural Earth: www.naturalearthdata.com), thereby identifying the species that may potentially lie beyond domestic scholars' reach. Coordinates, aside from those of the examined materials, were cited or approximated from iNaturalist and past literatures (e. g. Bastawade, 2006; Di, 2009; Di et al., 2013); all localities marked in the map were explicitly explained in the text and figure captions. Additional material and distribution notes listed under each species are confined to those **within Xizang**, China. Coordinate distance between two given localities was calculated online (gps-coordinates.org/distance-between-coordinates.php). Elementary statistical tests were performed online with default settings or otherwise noted (www.statskingdom.com). Further multivariate analyses were conducted in IBM SPSS Statistics (ver. 27.0), OriginPro 2024b (ver. 10.1.5.132), RStudio (R ver. 4.4.2), and MATLAB R2024b (ver. 24.2.0.2806996). Statistical values were rounded to three decimal places when applicable.

Toponyms. 巴宜: Bayi = Chagyib; 波密: Bomê = Pome = Bomi; 背崩: Drepung = Beibeng = Baibung; 隆子: Lhünzê = Lhöntse = Longzi; 米林: Mainling = Milin; 墨脱: Mêdog = Pemako = Motuo; 林芝: Nyingchi = Nyingtri = Linzhi; 山南: Shannan = Lhoka; 通麦: Tongmai = Tangmai; 扎木: Tramog = Tramo = Zhamu = Zhamog = Zhamo; 错那: Tsona = Cuona; 察隅: Zayü = Zayul = Chayu. Nyingchi and Shannan cities are prefecture-level; Mainling and Tsona cities are county-level. To avoid confusions with Pinyin used in the previous literatures, the administrative division levels are explained as follows: "村 (cūn)" = village; "镇 (zhèn)" = town; "乡 (xiāng)" = township; "区 (qū)" = district; "市 (shì)" = city; "县 (xiàn)" = county; "辖区 (xiá qū)" or "州 (zhōu)" = prefecture (province-level). Bayi (Chagyib) District (巴宜区) should not be confused with Bayi Town (八一镇).

Materials. All specimens were collected by the friends of the current author or purchased online. Scorpions were either collected manually or by pitfall traps. Part of the specimens were alive upon reception. All specimens are now preserved in 75% ethanol, except for the holotype female, allotypic paratype male, and an additional pair of paratypes of *C. herta* sp. n. (in 99% ethanol). Part of the specimens were rigidified thus certain structures cannot be examined (e. g., cheliceral and chelal fingers). Additional specimens examined (VT) are listed as follows:

Chaerilus hofereki Kovařík, Král, Kořínková & Lerma, 2014, **Vietnam**, 2♂, purchased live specimens (now preserved in 75% ethanol) from a local friend; not examined in detail.

Chaerilus stockmannorum Kovařík, Lowe & Štáhlavský, 2018, **Thailand**, 1♀ (Fig. 11), purchased live specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol) from UK pet trade, captive bred and born, likely originated from Mr. Mark Stockmann; not examined in detail.

Chaerilus variegatus Simon, 1877, **Indonesia**, 1♂1♀ (Figs. 76–91), purchased live specimens (now preserved in 75% ethanol) from a local friend (Mr. Ang Wei Ayang in Tang & Liu, 2024). The Chinese species, *Scorpiops jendeki* Kovařík, 1994, has been informally misidentified as this species (Tang, 2022c: 14).

Chaerilus sp. (cf. *herta* sp. n.), **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, June 2024, 2♀ (Figs. 52–67), purchased dried specimens from goofish.com, allegedly from a recent expedition to this county, collector unknown.

Chaerilus sp. (aff. *chubluk*), **Vietnam, Đắk Lắk Province**, Buôn Ma Thuột City, Hòa Khánh Commune, December 2023, 2♀1♂ (alive), 2 juv. ♂ (now preserved in 75% ethanol), purchased specimens from a local friend; not examined in detail.

Abbreviations. Morphology: CAM, carapace anterior margin; CG, carapacial granulation; ChL/W, pedipalp chela length (ChL) to width (ChW) ratio; CPM, centro-posteromedian carina(e); DSC, pedipalp movable finger denticle subrow count(s); EDD, enlarged distal denticle; EPD, enlarged proximal denticle; FL/CaL, pedipalp femur length (FL) to carapace length (CaL) ratio; MIIC, number of carinae on metasoma II; MLMa, mediolateral major ocellus(i); PLMa, posterolateral major ocellus(i); PTC, pectinal tooth count(s); SVII, ventral surface of sternite VII; TL, total length (in mm); VADC, ventral accessory denticle (VAD) count(s) of cheliceral finger (movable/fixed). **Others:** AC, anonymous collector; ANOVA, analysis of variance; CC, canonical correlation; CDA, canonical discriminant analysis; CV, canonical variables; FAMD, factorial analysis of mixed data; HCA, hierarchical cluster analysis; ISS, incorrect subsequent spelling; KMCA, k-means cluster analysis; KMO, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure; MAE, mean absolute error; MANOVA, multivariate ANOVA; MCA, multiple correspondence analysis; MCS, Monte Carlo simulation; MWU, Mann-Whitney U test; PCA, principal component analysis; PD, principal dimension; PERMANOVA, permutational MANOVA; RMSE, root-mean-square error; SD, standard deviation; SW, Shapiro-Wilk test; UPGMA, unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean; UV, ultraviolet; WSR, Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Specimen Depositories. FKCP, personal collection of František Kovařík, Prague, Czech Republic (will in future be merged with the collections of the National Museum of Natural History, Prague, Czech Republic); MHBU, Museum of Hebei University, Baoding, China; MNHN, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; MWHU, Museum of Wuhan University, Wuhan, China; NHMUK, Natural History Museum, London, UK; NZSI, National Collection, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata, India; USTC, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China; VT, personal collection of Victoria Tang, Shanghai, China (will in future be donated to NHMUK); ZMNH, Zoologie des Museums der Natur Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany (formerly known as "Zoologisches Institut und Zoologisches Museum, Universität Hamburg, Germany").

Figures 2–6: **Figures 2–4.** *Chaerilus cf. dibangvalleycus* Bastawade, 2006, adult male *in vivo* habitus (photo courtesy of Ashwin Viswanathan); record not included in the map. **Figures 5–6.** Adult female *Chaerilus cf. wrzecionkoi* (same as in iNaturalist obs. ID = 108856746) preserved in 75 % ethanol for about 5 years, photographs taken under 365 nm UV light on A4 paper (5) and black cloth (6) in a dark room at night, on 5th November 2024 (the current author had already investigated problems associated with UV fluorescence using this specimen in 2023 deriving the same contrasting results, but no formal photos were taken). Setup and settings: Canon 5DsR paired with Kenko extension tubes (12 + 20 mm) and Sigma 70mm f2.8 macro lens; M mode, ISO 100, F 9.0, shutter speed 1/6 for Fig. 5 and 0.6 for Fig. 6, single shot (not edited).

Etymology of genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877

As clarified in Tang (2022a: 9), this genus has been historically referred to as “豚蝎” or “豕蝎” (both denoting “pig scorpion”) in Chinese papers (mainly dissertations) as its “formal Chinese names”, most likely based on the Ancient Greek χοῖρος (choiros, khoiros), meaning “pig”. As such, the two “formal Chinese names” are inherently translated names, albeit erroneous. This situation echoes a similar case with another scorpion taxon, *Lychas scutillus* C. L. Koch, 1845, whose specific epithet was interpreted as Latin *scutum* (shield) and was assigned the appellation “盾狼蝎” (“shielded wolf scorpion”) as its “formal Chinese name” (again, the generic epithet was wrongly interpreted as λύκος (lúkos), “wolf”; *op. cit.*: 10–11). Both “formal Chinese names” overlooked the term *-ilus* present in both epithets, leading to their misinterpretation. The specific epithet of the second taxon in fact corresponds to the very same Latin word, *scutillus*, meaning “slender”, portraying the habitus of this species (C. L. Koch, 1845: 3, “...Schwanz und Taster scharfkielig, beide sehr dünn...”; *op. cit.*: 4, “...Der Schwanz dünn, im Durchschnitt ziemlich walzenförmig...”, “...Die Taster dünn und lang...”). On the other hand, while it is likely for the name *Chaerilus* itself to be originated from χοῖρος (“pig”), this simultaneously renders “-ιλος (-ilos)” as an uninterpretable suffix. It could be a diminutive suffix analogous with the Latin suffix *-illus*, or simply one that conveys the meaning of “having the nature of”.

The etymology of genus *Chaerilus* has been suggested by Dupré (2016: 15) as an eponym of a Greek epic poet or playwright, Χοιρίλος (Choirilos, Choerilus). In fact, Simon (1877: 238) did not provide an explanation for his choice of this name (originally spelled as “CHÆRILUS”, latinized name of “Choirilos”). As discussed in Tang (2022a: 14), Simon was fond of proposing new taxonomic names after historical and literary figures, and thus the presumed etymology is most plausible. Similarly, the genus *Timogenes* Simon, 1880 was named after Timagène (Τιμαγένης), a Greek historian from 1st century B.C. Since the identity of Χοιρίλος complicates an appropriate translation in Chinese, the genus *Chaerilus* was transliterated based on the first two syllables of “**CHOERILUS**”, as “寇里蝎” in Tang (2022). This approach aims to differentiate modern names from ancient or fictional ones, where the translation of modern characters is accompanied by the term “氏” (equivalent to the possessive case, ’s), indicating the eponymous nature of the name. On the contrary, the other types of names are used as nouns in apposition within their respective eponyms, as there is no Latin suffix (e. g., *-i*, *-ae*, *-orum*) attached to them. Nonetheless, names of modern characters have also been occasionally used directly as specific epithets without adding suffixes. Similarly, for those unfamiliar with the principles of coining Latin names, such suffixes may be mistakenly added to non-human names (e. g., *Ramisyllis kingghidorahi* Aguado, et al. 2022).

While the names of ancient Greek or Roman characters are often deconstructable, translation of scientific names derived from these characters should avoid undue deconstruction, preferring transliterations or translations based on their

identities unless the name serves as a pun. However, although the etymology of the genus *Grosphus* Simon, 1880 was suggested as a wealthy Sicilian landlord in Horace’s *Odes* (Dupré, 2016: 27; Tang, 2022a: 23), this name has a direct Greek origin, γρόσφος (grósfhos), meaning “the point of a javelin”. Thus, it was translated as “矛蝎” (“spear scorpion”) in Chinese, considering the character’s identity hinders a suitable translation, and that transliteration of eponyms without “氏” is less preferable and rarely employed due to ambiguity for those unfamiliar with the etymology. On the other hand, the etymology of the genus *Buthus* Leach, 1815 was deduced to be a Greek athlete, βούθος, who devoured an ox within a day (Sousa et al., 2017: 32–33). This name can be further deconstructed into βούς (boús, “ox”) and θυσία (thysia, “sacrifice”), an etymology formally adopted in the naming of another scorpion genus, *Trypanothacus* (Lowe et al., 2019: 3). Consequently, a translation based on the deconstructed etymology was employed, leading to the equivalent Chinese name “杀牛蝎” for genus *Buthus* (Tang, 2022a). The translated name of genus *Buthus* can be equally justified if one advocates for the name “豚蝎” for genus *Chaerilus*, should it be rooted in χοῖρος (“pig”) and intended as a pun for its type species, *C. variegatus* Simon, 1877. However, there was no trace of such indications in Simon’s morphological characterization.

Fluorescence of chaerilids under ultraviolet illumination

Scorpions are well-known for their captivating fluorescence when exposed to 320–450 nm UV light (Lopez-Cabrera et al., 2020: fig. 8b), emitting a glow within the 440–550 nm range (Liu et al., 2024), a phenomenon attributed to specific chemical compounds in their cuticle (Tang & Liu, 2024). This feature has greatly aided researchers in detecting scorpions in the field. However, the fluorescence can vary in its chromatic expression, with darker species typically emitting a bluish glow, while lighter species fluoresce in a greenish hue. Within the same individual, fluorescence intensity can also differ due to variations in regional cuticle thickness or base color patterns. Furthermore, some dark, matte species of genus *Scorpiops* exhibit weaker overall fluorescence as a result of their intricate, reticulated configurations of cuticular microstructures varying in their fluorescence intensity under the UV light (cf. UV photos in Tang (2022c, 2023)). Certain types of setae are also responsive to UV illumination (e. g., Kovařík et al., 2016a: 17, figs. 68–70; Tang, 2022c: figs. 10–11; Kovařík et al., 2022b: 11, figs. 97–98), while other setae and metallic regions, such as denticles, distal aculeus (but see Lowe (2024)), and unguis, are inactive under UV.

Intriguingly, Lourenço (2012: 3) stated that at least some species of *Chaerilus* are non-fluorescent under UV light. This unprecedented finding misled the current author for some time until live specimens of this genus became available for study. Upon observation, all specimens examined (including *C. hofereki* Kovařík, et al., 2014, *C. stockmannorum* Kovařík et al., 2018, *C. variegatus*, and one unidentified species from Vietnam, in addition to the species listed below) turned out to be visibly fluorescent under UV. However, their fluorescence

Figures 7–11: Figures 7–10. Effects of measurement inconsistency on deriving ChL/W; pixel length and width obtained automatically in Photoshop with the plugin “Specs”. Each photo, when considered individually, may reasonably (though subjectively) serve as the basis for calculating the ratiometrics. The row axis of the chela was neither distinctly tilted upward nor downward in any of the photos, nor was it strictly leveled, so as to account for the accuracy randomness encountered in practice when dealing with small-sized species. Adult female *Chaerilus* cf. *wrzecionkoi* (same as in Figs. 5–6) data: DSC 8/8, PTC 3/3, sternite VII (examined under UV) granular and acarinate (which put it within the set comprising *C. pseudoconchiformus*, *C. tryznai*, and *C. wrzecionkoi*). Figures 7 and 8 may be considered more appropriate, but they nonetheless show a difference of nearly 0.2, which is exactly the sexual difference recorded for *C. wrzecionkoi*. **Figure 11.** Diagram showing the pedipalp chela carination terminologies and measurement of ChL and ChW in this study (*Chaerilus stockmannorum*).

was indeed to some extent weaker than the general intensity observed in other scorpions, approximating that of most Yunnan *Scorpiops*. Although my species list does not contain those studied by Lourenço (2012: tab. 1), it is evident that at least the cuticle of some *Chaerilus* species undoubtedly show positive optical reaction to the UV light. In fact, prior to the publication of this paper, a recent study conducted by Lowe & Fet (2024) had already demonstrated UV fluorescence in *Chaerilus* at the light microscopic level (*op. cit.*: figs. 865–882; see also, Lowe, 2024). Their study also showed several intra- and interspecific differences of fluorescence profile in *Chaerilus* (*op. cit.*: figs. 871, 873, 880, 882), substantiating that the observed weak fluorescence in *Chaerilus* species is due to the structural and optical properties of the cuticle, not the absence of fluorophores.

After scrutinizing the figure and descriptions in Lourenço (2012), this apparent discordance of observations could have been explained. All the specimens examined by Lourenço had been preserved in 75% ethanol with an upper bound of preservation age of 5 years. Fluorescence in deceased scorpions is known to undergo intensity reduction over time. If a scorpion is already weakly fluorescent under UV when alive, its fluorescence will undoubtedly diminish following its demise. Moreover, when comparing preserved specimens of different species, if the rate of fluorescence decay differs among taxa under identical preservation conditions due to unknown factors, it is logically fallacious to claim that the maintenance of strong fluorescence in some taxa guarantees a valid control against the subject of interest belonging to another taxon, or, therefore, an absence of fluorescence in the latter group will suffice to indicate the same condition *in vivo*. In other words, fluorescence intensity comparison between different taxa should only be conducted when they are alive.

In addition, the author asserted that those specimens were photographed against a dark surface, which raised my suspicion upon reviewing his figure 2B. The photograph shows several peripheral regions of a *C. telnovi* Lourenço, 2009 specimen highlighted, such as one side of the mesosoma and the external surface of the pedipalp finger, while the legs appear notably lighter than the rest of the body. Extrapolating from my experience, I surmise that the specimen was in fact placed on a white surface, causing reflectance and transmission of UV light towards the cuticle and through the semi-translucent legs, respectively. If a white background was employed, the camera may attempt to compensate for the bright background by reducing the overall exposure with its automatic algorithms, rendering the object to appear darker. Conversely, placing the object on a black surface might trigger the camera to increase the exposure to capture more light, resulting in the object appearing brighter. This automatic exposure adjustment could explain the apparent reduction in fluorescence intensity observed in the image. Similar results can also be achieved manually by using different shutter speeds. Fortunately, a *Chaerilus* specimen reserved in 75% ethanol for about 5 years was available to me for examination. This specimen exhibited significantly different apparent fluorescence intensities depending on whether it

was photographed against a black or white background (Figs. 5–6). Should my assumption be validated, this optical façade must have had further minimized the perceived fluorescence intensity in the *Chaerilus* specimen examined by Lourenço. In contrast, Lourenço & Ythier (2021: fig. 21) depicted a “non-fluorescent” specimen of *Orthochirus* against a dark background, which aligns with my empirical understanding of optics as the specimen was clearly discernible. In this case, no UV reflectance was visible, except for the glabrous dorsal surface of the metasoma, where UV light illuminated the specimen. Conveniently, the fact that the specimen had been preserved for 46 years was not taken into account this time.

The phenomenon of photobleaching in preserved specimens has been emphasized in previous studies (Lowe & Kovařík, 2022: 35; Kovařík & Lowe, 2022: 18). Photobleaching refers to the irreversible degradation of fluorophore molecules, which lose their ability to fluoresce due to chemical reactions triggered by absorbed light over prolonged exposure. Fluorophores absorb photons of light at one wavelength (excitation) and emit light at a longer wavelength (emission), a property known as fluorescence. During the absorption process, the photon provides the energy to move an electron within the fluorophore to a higher energy level, rendering the excited state (singlet state) of fluorophore, which is typically short-lived. Then, the excited fluorophore may undergo vibrational relaxation, where it interacts with and transfers some energy to the molecular oxygen in the surrounding environment, moving to a slightly lower energy level. If this is followed by the occurrence of intersystem crossing, it transitions to an even lower energy level, the long-lived triplet state. After the electron returns to the ground state, it releases the excess energy as a photon of light, the phosphorescence. While in the vibrational relaxation, the transfer of energy induces the generation of reactive oxygen species, such as singlet oxygen, a process known as the photooxidation. This can initiate oxidative damage to the fluorophore, converting it into non-fluorescent compound, as the reactive oxygen species can cause covalent modifications in the fluorophore, where the covalent bonds within the molecule may break or undergo chemical reactions, leading to irreversible changes. Over time, continued exposure to excitation light accumulates damage, causing photobleaching.

Live scorpions can regenerate fluorophores and recover their fluorescence (Kloock, 2009), otherwise there will theoretically be a negative correlation between the fluorescence intensity and development stage, which has not been observed. However, it remains to be verified if such regeneration ability declines with age in scorpions. On the other hand, such recovery cannot be achieved by preserved museum specimens, rendering the photobleaching as an irreversible and cumulative process. Lowe & Kovařík (2022: 35) noted the heterogeneity of fluorescence intensity in a specimen of *Teruelius limbatus* (Pocock, 1889) where a localized photobleaching was present, suggesting that the rate of fluorescence decline is influenced by various factors, such as the fixation method, preservative composition, and storage duration. Moreover, if the specimen was preserved

shortly after its recent ecdysis, the fluorophore concentration in the epicuticle may not have reached its maximum level. If preservation conditions and prior states are not controlled identical for specimens used in comparison, any conclusions about fluorescence intensity may be biased. However, Lourenço remains confident in his findings of fluorescence absence in *Chaerilus* species, repeatedly citing them in his subsequent publications without providing any UV imaging photographs for those new species (e. g., Lourenço, 2019: 34; Lourenço & Rossi, 2019: 50; Lourenço et al., 2020: 22; Lourenço, 2023: 8). These unsubstantiated statements further beguiled the current author, who, as an amateur, naively succumbed to the ad verecundiam fallacy.

If the superficial absence of fluorescence can be explained by long-term storage in preservatives, a further conundrum arises in the case of *C. chubluk*, which was also reported as non-fluorescent (Lourenço et al., 2020: 22) despite being described from a fresh immature specimen (*op. cit.*: fig. 15). The same “non-fluorescence” statement was also made for *C. honba* (Lourenço, 2019: 34). While these species are not available for my examination, a plausible explanation is the sclerotization deficiency in newly molted specimens that led to weaker fluorescence, which is particularly probable for the case of holotype male *C. chubluk* given its coloration. It is most likely that those authors incorrectly equated “weak fluorescence” with “non-fluorescence”. Although my observations negate the idea of fluorescence absence in *Chaerilus*, the notion proposed by Lourenço (2012) that taxa with reduced fluorescence might serve as the media to decipher the function of scorpion fluorescence still holds, and as a taxon with weak fluorescence, *Chaerilus* remains an explanatory candidate as such (and probably likewise for certain *Scorpiops* species). However, the observed correlation between fluorescence intensity and certain biological features could be influenced by numerous potential biases unrelated to the fluorescence, while fluorescence itself may serve distinct functions in different taxa.

Diagnosics applied in the past literature

Species of this genus are often distinguished by the following external morphological characters: presence/absence of ocelli, total length (16–80 mm), color pattern, carapace anterior margin (CAM) shape, chela length to width ratio (ChL/W; especially in adult males) or sexual dimorphism in chela shape, relative length of chelal finger, presence/absence of lobe on movable chelal finger, pedipalp movable finger denticle subrow count (DSC), development of carinae on chelal manus, trichobothrium d_2 and d_3 on pedipalp patella, pectinal tooth count (PTC), texture on sternite VII, granulation of metasoma, development of carinae on metasoma I–II, ratio of metasomal segments, and shape of telson (Kovářik, 2012: 1–3; Kovářik & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 131–133; Kovářik et al., 2014: 11; Kovářik et al., 2015: 14–15, 20; Kovářik et al., 2018: 7, 16, 19, 25; Kovářik, 2019: 9; Kovářik et al., 2020: 3, 9, 13). Several diagnostic characters

will be discussed with specific cases in the next section, but an overview is hereby provided.

Most *Chaerilus* species possess two pairs of lateral ocelli (Type 2A; MLMa and PLMa), although Loria & Prendini (2014: 11, fig. 3A–B) also reported the third anomalous ocelli in *C. variegatus* Simon, 1877. Reduction or loss of ocelli (median, or lateral, or both) are reported in several species (Prendini et al., 2021: 123–124): *C. agilis* Pocock, 1899 (median and lateral reduced), *C. chapmani* Vachon & Lourenço, 1995 (median and lateral reduced), *C. sabiniae* Lourenço, 1995 (median and lateral absent), and *C. telnovi* Lourenço, 2009 (median absent, lateral reduced). Asymmetric loss of a single ocellus (MLMa) on the right side was further documented in *C. chapmani* (Loria & Prendini, 2014: 11, fig. 3E). Interestingly, cavernicolous species do not always manifest loss of ocelli as part of their troglomorphism: *C. adrianoi* Lourenço & Ythier, 2024, *C. agnellivanniorum* Lourenço & Rossi, 2019, *C. cavernicola* Pocock, 1894, *C. pathom* Lourenço & Pham, 2014, and *C. spinatus* Lourenço & Duhem, 2010.

Total length, like in other scorpions, is a continuous character that can be limited in its utility for distinguishing species of similar sizes, as is the case for many Chinese *Chaerilus* that ranges from 30–40 mm. Another factor to consider is the different size classes within adult individuals of the same species (as already seen in *Scorpiops*; Tang, 2022c: figs. 86–88, 184–185, 218–219). Even when such variables are accounted for, interpreting the data poses challenges: what difference threshold qualifies as diagnostic for species delimitation? Some authors have utilized total length to differentiate their new species from others, but often fail to provide justification for its diagnostic reliability based on statistical significance (see below in the section of *C. pseudoconchiformis*). Theoretically, deriving total length requires measuring the lengths of carapace, each tergite, each metasomal segment, and the telson. Carapace length is relatively straightforward to measure. On the other hand, measuring the tergites individually to obtain a mesosoma length could lead to under- or overestimation since those sclerites are not regular rectangles. Similarly, metasomal segments are irregular at their anterior and/or posterior margins. In addition, the annular or cylindrical base of each metasomal segment (which is partially concealed by its anterior segment when the metasoma is contracted) extends beyond the main segment proximally along the row axis. Some authors may select one of their measurement points on the proximal margin of this base, while others choose both landmarks on the main segment. The irregular contour of the metasomal segment itself also contributes to measurement discrepancies, depending on whether lengths are taken from ventral, lateral, or dorsal views, since the preferred landmarks could vary subjectively on different surfaces. Measuring the telson can also present difficulties, especially when the aculeus is long and curved. This requires one to first level the telson by its dorsal margin, before auxiliary lines orthogonal to the level line can be used to derive the telson length. However, the dorsal surface can be curved, preventing its

leveling. Moreover, when the telson is straightened along the metasomal axis, part of its length overlaps with the posterior section of metasoma V. This can lead to an overestimation of the true total length—one yielded by a naturally straightened scorpion—if the telson length is measured independently. Although these considerations may seem overly meticulous to some, it essentially depends on how one intends to utilize the total length as a diagnostic criterion to justify their new species. When comparing similarly sized species, accurate measurements are essential for conducting meaningful statistical tests to detect significant differences. Conversely, a crude range may suffice for a general understanding of the size of a species.

Color pattern is an occasionally useful but meanwhile variable character for genus *Chaerilus*. Brightness can vary among adults of the same species (cf. Kovařík et al. (2014: fig. 30) vs. Kovařík et al. (2015: fig. 46), and Kovařík et al. (2018: figs. 37, 40)). Crucially important is the common ontogenetic variation where juveniles may exhibit distinctly paler and more variegated or maculated color patterns comparing to their adult counterparts, a contrast particularly pronounced in dark species. These phenomena had been historically overlooked, leading to descriptions of false new species (see below in the section of *C. pictus*). The shape of the anterior margin of carapace has been employed to distinguish several species and can be roughly categorized into three states: convex (outward curvature), straight, and concave (inward curvature). In fact, most *Chaerilus* show a nearly straight margin with minor fluctuations. As a qualitative character, its description largely hinges upon the author's subjective empirical assessment on the degree of the convexity or concavity. Notably, this character has also been applied to distinguish two buthid scorpions, *Mesobuthus mongolicus* (Birula, 1911) and *M. thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839), in which the latter was described with a weakly concave margin as opposed to the straight or weakly convex margin in the former (Sun & Sun, 2011: 71). Upon examining 64 adult specimens, no consistent differences were confirmed, and margin shape varied within the same population (for photographic evidences, see iNaturalist obs. ID = 108739616, 108740310). The former species is now a junior synonym of the latter (Kovařík et al., 2022a). Similar variations have also been observed in another buthid, *Butheolus gallagheri* Vachon, 1980 (Kovařík & Lowe, 2012: figs. 77–85). Hence, this character will be evaluated for its reliability within *Chaerilus* in the current study. However, given the limited taxa available, I do not unreservedly negate its utility in distinguish *Chaerilus* species; rather, I consider it a caveat against diagnostic justification based on limited sample size (e. g., $n \leq 3$). Qualitative (subjective) descriptions for cuticle granulations (e. g., those on carapace, tergites, and intercarinal surfaces of metasoma) typically lack comparative visuals and fail to account for intraspecific variability (see below in the section of *C. pictus*). The placement of pedipalp patellar trichobothria has been used to differentiate some species, but many share the same

condition, and, for trichobothrial pattern itself, intraspecific variation can occur, with anomalous trichobothria straddling adjacent carinae in certain species of other genera (Lowe & Kovařík, 2019; Kovařík et al., 2022b).

Several other unquantified traits are more reliable but confined to a few unique species. For example, the relative length of chelal finger is a definitive character that features male *C. ceylonensis* Pocock, 1894, *C. cimrmani* Kovařík, 2012, and *C. hofereki*, all of which have notably short fingers (Kovařík, 2019: figs. 40–41, 44). Likewise, the presence of a finger lobe is diagnostic for male *C. terueli* Kovařík, 2012 (Kovařík, 2019: fig. 56). The number or essentially, the development of chelal carina can also distinguish species, as seen in *C. tricostatus*, lacking the D_3 carina. *Chaerilus* species typically possess up to 8 carinae (per Soleglad & Sissom, 2001), as indicated in the 'Methods' section. However, Kovařík et al. (2016a: 96), while acknowledging this pattern (*op. cit.*: 89), described *C. ceylonensis* with 9 carinae, likely recognizing an obsolete ventromedian carina (= V_2), based on their figure 448. Finally, the uniquely elongated telson in male *C. pictus* differs from all other *Chaerilus*.

Chela shape is a valuable diagnostic tool for discriminating many *Chaerilus* species, particularly among adult males. Sexual dimorphism in this trait may also serve as a diagnostic feature. However, its quantified counterpart—albeit not entirely, since shape is a more complex geometry (hence it is more effective to provide comparative visuals, as exemplified by Kovařík (2019: figs. 37–58))—ChL/W, is marred by notable deficiencies. The relevant problems have been extensively discussed in Tang (2023). To illustrate the major concern, the measurement inconsistency, Figs. 7–10 show the the distinct ChL/W derived from different views of the chela. In practice, even when the angle is fixed, repeated measurements may as well yield different values. Minor numerical differences are frequently interpreted by some authors as evidence of interspecific distinction, supporting the proposal of new species. However, these differences often mirror the same absolute values obtained from repeated measurements on the same specimen (see below in the section of *C. tessellatus*). This issue also extends to the ratiometrics of metasomal segments, which face similar challenges, as previously discussed regarding total length measurements. Essentially, any ratiometric system employed for species differentiation is impeded by measurement inconsistencies and intraspecific variability. These two sources of bias are critical when relying on small numerical differences to justify species as distinct.

In this study, several other diagnostics, namely DSC, texture on sternite VII, and metasomal carinae, will be evaluated. The meristic PTC alone is ineffective for distinguishing Chinese species (and probably most *Chaerilus* species, given the limited total variation range, 3–8, and this range alone applies to *C. variegatus*). Some additional criteria, including the number of denticles on the ventral sides of cheliceral movable and fixed fingers and the relative length of the pedipalp femur, have been mainly restricted to Indian

and Chinese publications. To reduce confusion and increase simplicity, several terminologies used in previous literatures are altered to the following expressions: “minute teeth on cheliceral fingers” are termed “ventral accessory denticles” as per Soleglad & Fet (2003b), “rows of granules on the cutting edge of pedipalp finger” are termed “denticle subrows” as per Tang et al. (2024a), “weakly granulated” or “with some small granules” are abbreviated to “subgranular”, the adjective “obsolete” encompasses both itself and “vestigial” given the subjective nature of the qualification, and “pedipalp femur longer or shorter than carapace” is quantified as “femur length to carapace length ratio $>$ or $<$ 1” in order to be incorporated into Table 1.

Literature review on the Chinese *Chaerilus* species

Chaerilus assamensis Kraepelin, 1913

(Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:BEA6DB62-1A10-4ADF-AA7A-24C758187ECB>

Chaerilus assamensis: Kraepelin, 1913: 141, 144–145; Takashima, 1945: 101; Pérez, 1974: 31; Kovařík, 1998: 129; Fet, 2000: 324; Kovařík, 2000: 39–40, 42, 66, 69, 72; Di et al., 2009: 131–133; Di, 2009: 99; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97; Sun, 2010: 101–102; Kovařík, 2012: 2; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 131–133; Di et al., 2013: 52, 75; Di et al., 2014: 5; Tang, 2022a: 54; Tang, 2022b: 2, 3, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

Chaerilus dibangvalleyicus: Bastawade, 2006: 451–454; Di et al., 2009: 131–133; Di, 2009: 98, 101–102; Sun, 2010: 101, 103–104; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 133; Di et al., 2013: 55, 57, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 4, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42, 48–49; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022b: 2, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

= ?*Chaerilus dibangvalleyicus* Bastawade, 2006 (syn. Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 133) <http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:10E079A1-B6B7-40CC-9AC7-6197BF3AF0B7> TYPE MATERIAL (Bastawade, 2006: 454). **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Zayü County [“**India, Arunachal Pradesh State**, Dibang Valley District, Mayodia or Mayudia”], 28°51'48.2"N 95°57'00.3"E (approximated), 6♂5♀, 2 juvs, NZSI.

TYPE MATERIAL (Kraepelin, 1913: 144). **India, Assam State**, 1♂, 1 juv. ♀, NZSI.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. None.

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 31.5–41.5 mm for ♂ and 36.75 mm for ♀. General color reddish to dark brownish; legs pale brown; telson reddish brown. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular, stronger in ♀; CAM arched (or weakly concave?) in ♂, straight in ♀; sternite III–VI smooth, VII granular and tetracarinate. Metasoma I–V

with carinae 10-8-8-8-7. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 4–5 in both sexes. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers 4–5/8–10. Pedipalp chela slender in ♂ (?), ChL/W ca. 3.25 in ♂; manus with D_1 , D_{3-5} , E , and V_{13} present, smooth (?) to granular, I obsolete; D_3 mostly obsolete (?), indicated distally and proximally; DSC of movable finger 7–8 (?), dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid; but its synonymy with *C. dibangvalleyicus* remains dubious.

REMARKS. Kraepelin (1913: 144–145) roughly characterized *C. assamensis* based on an adult male (31.5 mm, PTC 5/5) and a juvenile female (22 mm, PTC 4/4) from Assam, India. He noted that this species differs from all other congeners of the time by a distinctly arched (*vs.* straight) CAM in the male, which is flatter in the female (“...*einen stärker gekrümmten Kreisbogen bildende Rundung des Stirnrandes...*”; *op. cit.*: fig. 3a–b). All carinae on the pedipalp manus were described as developed and almost smooth, except for the “secondary inner keel” (= D_5 ; *op. cit.*: fig. 2) being somewhat granular (“...*Handkiele alle entwickelt und alle fast glatt, nur der sekundäre Innenrandkiel etwas zackig körnig...*”). This species has never been revised based on any materials since then. Another character later emphasized by Kovařík (2000: 42) was the presence of 7–8 subrows of denticles on the pedipalp chela movable finger (Kraepelin, 1913: “...*Schrägreihen des beweglichen Scherenfingers (bezw. der äußeren Seitenkörnchen mit Einschluß des Endkörnchens) nur 7–8...*”, “...*Beweglicher Finger mit sieben Schrägreihen...*”), a count then observed only in *C. tryznai* from China (now known to occur in several other *Chaerilus* species).

Bastawade (2006: 451) described *C. dibangvalleyicus* based on a number of adult specimens and two juveniles. Although the description was more detailed, several issues hinder a clear understanding of this species. Most importantly, he did not clarify the sex of the specimen illustrated. While the pectines showed 3 teeth (*op. cit.*: fig. 6), rendering it more likely a female, the presence of a pair of genital papillae (cited in the description) suggests it was a male. However, the author calculated 4 teeth for males and 5 for females. Moreover, he initially mentioned the presence of 4 and 8–9 ventral accessory denticles on cheliceral movable and fixed fingers (*op. cit.*: 451), but then shifted these counts to 5 and 10 in his interspecific comparison (*op. cit.*: 454). The illustration (*op. cit.*: fig. 4) showed 9 accessory denticles on the fixed cheliceral finger.

Kovařík (*in* Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 133) synonymized *C. dibangvalleyicus* with *C. assamensis* based primarily on geographic proximity and identical DSC, albeit examining no specimens. The current investigation further discovered that the descriptions of both species documented sexual dimorphism in the tergal granulation development, where it is weaker in males. Kovařík considered the carapace illustration in Bastawade (2006: 452, fig. 1) pertained to the female paratype, yet the original author did not explicate the sex in either description or figure caption. If one assumes

that all depictions were of the male holotype (as that of the pectines), then the male *C. dibangvalleyicus* clearly shows a weakly concave CAM. Another discrepancy between the two species lies in the metasomal carinae. Kraepelin (1913: 144) described the male *C. assamensis* as lacking inframedian (= median lateral) carinae (“*untere Mediankiele*”) on metasoma I–II. On the contrary, Bastawade (2006: 451) claimed that in *C. dibangvalleyicus*, all carinae on metasoma I are well-developed, but the “laterals” on metasoma II–IV are not, suggesting a carina formula of 10-8-8-8 for metasoma I–VI. In addition, Kraepelin (1913: 144) briefly characterized the sternites of *C. assamensis* as matt and agranular (“...*Bauchplatten matt, ungekrönt...*”), contradicting the granular and carinate sternite VII described for *C. dibangvalleyicus*, though it is unclear if Kraepelin’s qualification applies to all sternites. There was no indication from Kraepelin of a reduction in D_3 on the chela carinae, while the opposite appears to be the case in *C. dibangvalleyicus* (Bastawade, 2006: fig. 14). Kraepelin also did not provide enough metrics, but noted that the pedipalp finger was shorter than the manus in both sexes (“...*F[inger]. : H[inter]hand beim ♂ = 3,5 : 5, beim ♀ 2,5 : 3...*”) and a length to width ratio of manus for both sexes (“...*Verhältnis von Länge der Hinterhand zur Handbreite beim ♂ = 5 : 3, beim ♀ = 3 : 2...*”). He described the chela as “rather narrow” (“...*Hand ziemlich schmal...*”) without specifying any difference between sexes, which could suggest either a weak sexual dimorphism (as also indicated by the manus ratio) or an ontogenetic variation (i.e., juvenile female had narrower manus than its adult counterpart). Bastawade, on the other hand, noted that male *C. dibangvalleyicus* are more slender than females. This further suggest that his original figures were more likely depicted for the male holotype, where a narrow chela was illustrated. A crude measurement based on his figure 14 yields a ChL/W of 3.25.

In any case, the taxonomic status of both species is currently unclear. Given the morphological incongruence in some aspects between the two species, *C. dibangvalleyicus* may in fact be a valid species. However, whether synonymous or not, the decision largely depends on the reliability of the characters discussed (i.e., whether they are intraspecifically stable in the two species): CAM, pedipalp and metasomal carinae, sternite, and ChL/W.

The earliest mentioning of *C. assamensis* as a member of the scorpiofauna of China appears to be in Di et al. (2009: 132–133), who cited Kraepelin (1913: 144) and Kovařík (2000: 42, tab. 2) in the bibliography under this species. This is baffling as neither work considered this species to be distributed in China or Arunachal Pradesh, since only two specimens of this species have been known for the whole time. *Chaerilus dibangvalleyicus* was also included in their Chinese checklist, which was not synonymized with *C. assamensis* at that time. It is likely that the authors misread the table 2 in Kovařík (*op. cit.*: 72). This error perpetuated until Di et al. (2013: 52) and Di et al. (2014: 5) corrected it. Di et al. (2013: 55) considered the type locality of *C. dibangvalleyicus* to be located in Mêdog County. According to the 2023 version

administrative division map of Nyingchi City provided by the Department of Natural Resources of the Xizang Autonomous Region, the Dibang Valley District covers both Mêdog and Zayü counties. Approximated coordinates based on Bastawade (2006: map 1) place the type locality within Zayü (Fig. 1), though rather near the border with Mêdog. It, however, would not be surprising that this species occurs in both counties. On iNaturalist, one observation record (obs. ID = 219229842) from Mêdog (28°50'12.0"N 95°52'25.9"E) featured an apparently young adult male *Chaerilus* species, close to the type locality of *C. dibangvalleyicus* (ca. 8 km). The specimen matches Bastawade’s description for the coloration, as well as a narrow chela with obsolete D_3 . A weakly concave CAM can also be observed from the fourth photograph. To secure the record, photographs are reproduced with permission in Figs. 2–4. Another observation (obs. ID = 258985048) was recently uploaded for the same record (same date and coordinate).

Di et al. (2013: 57) also noted that “...*Both sexes of C. conchiformis, C. dibangvalleyicus and C. tryznai have anterior margin truncated, but only females of C. mainlingensis have same anterior margin of carapace as C. dibangvalleyicus...*”, which is bewildering. Only one sex (presumably male) of *C. dibangvalleyicus* has been illustrated, which shows a weakly concave CAM, not “truncated” (= straight). *Chaerilus mainlingensis* is known only from females, and the original authors (with the senior author being Z.-Y. Di, who made the above statement) also described its CAM as “weakly concave” (Di & Zhu, 2009: 98). Therefore, while their second sentence holds true, it contradicts with the first where the CAM was regarded straight for *C. dibangvalleyicus*. In their dichotomous keys, Yin et al. (2015: 49) characterized this species as “...*carapace with anterior margin straight with a median notch...*”, an eccentric description. A notch refers to an abrupt concavity seen in, for example, all *Scorpiops* species, which is not observable in Bastawade’s illustration. A straight margin with a median notch suggests the concavity is not gradual, but prominent. However, the original depiction shows a smooth inward curvature.

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from the type locality; Zayü County (“Mayodia”), in Nyingchi City.

***Chaerilus conchiformis* Zhu, Han & Lourenço, 2008**
(Figures 12–19; Tables 1–2)
<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:5726EDCE-209E-42B7-B2F8-4075F5D3F8D1>

Chaerilus pictus (misidentification): Qi et al., 2005: 34–38; Yang, 2008: 18–19, 46–48, 76.

Chaerilus conchiformis: Zhu et al., 2008: 37–43, 50; Di et al., 2009: 131–133; Di, 2009: 99–101, 189–193; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97, 101; Sun, 2010: 101–103; Kovařík, 2012: 2; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 131–132, 136; Di et al., 2013: 52, 55, 57, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 4, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42–43, 46, 48–49; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 12, 21, 54–55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2023: 20; Tang, 2025: 13, 16.

Figures 12–13. Adult male *Chaerilus conchiformis*, fresh specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (12) and ventral (13) views, under white light; record included in the map.

TYPE MATERIAL (Zhu et al., 2008: 39) [lost]. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Bayi Town, 29°41'N 94°21'E (type locality), 1♀, MHBUS; Nyingchi City, Bayi District, hill behind the Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University (specified in Di, 2009: 99), 1 juv. ♀; Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Baishuwang Town, 29°34'N 94°30'E, 6♀, MHBUS; Nyingchi City, Mainling City, Zhaxiraodeng Township (“Pai Town”?), 29°12'N 94°06' E, 1♂, MHBUS.

OTHER MATERIAL. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Bayi Town, 1 juv., MHBUS (Qi et al., 2005: 34); Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Bayi Town, 29°41'N 94°21'E (= type locality), 1♂3♀, 1 juv. (Di, 2009: 99); Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Bayi Town, hillside north of Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University, 29°39'50.6"N 94°20'35.4"E (approximated), 2♀, 7 juvs (Di, 2009: 99); Nyingchi City, Mainling City, 1 juv. (Di, 2009: 99). One ♀ reported in Yin et al. (2015: 46).

Figures 14–19. Adult male *Chaerilus conchiformis*, carapace (14), pectines (15), sternite VII (16), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (17) under white light, and left (18) and right (19) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

MATERIAL EXAMINED (VT). China, *Tibet Autonomous Region*, Nyingchi City, Mainling City, Milin Town, 29°12'51.6"N 94°12'46.2"E, 2936 m a. s. l., 21st November 2022, 1♂, leg. Yiyang Xu (Figs. 12–19).

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 43.47 mm for ♂ and 32–41.04 mm for ♀. General color reddish brown to dark brown. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular, stronger in ♀; CAM straight; sternite III–VI smooth, VII subgranular and tetracarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10–10–8–8–7. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 5 in ♂ and 3–4 in ♀. VADC of

cheliceraral movable/fixed fingers 5–6/5–6 (8?). Pedipalp chela not strongly sexually dimorphic, rounded in both sexes, ChL/W ca. 1.77 in ♂ and 1.6–1.9 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{3-5} , and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular, E and I obsolete; DSC of movable finger 7–8, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid, but pending the designation of a neotype.

REMARKS. Qi et al. (2005: 34–38) misidentified 1 adult female and 2 juvenile *Chaerilus* from Bayi Town (in Bayi District)

as *C. pictus*. The same adult female (17th August 2002) was later used as the holotype for describing *C. conchiformis* (Zhu et al., 2008: 38–39), and one of the juveniles (6th August 2003) was listed as a female paratype, while the other juvenile (sex not specified; 2nd August 2002) was neglected from the type series. Qi et al. (2005: 34) used the name “Bayizhen town” for the origin of the adult female, which was changed to “Bayi Town” in Zhu et al. (2008: 39), in accordance with the two original juveniles. The Pinyin “zhèn” (镇) is semantically synonymous with “town” in English, hence this name constitutes a tautological toponym. Zhu et al. (*op. cit.*) further listed 6 female paratypes (July 2006) from Baishuwang (“Cypress King”) Town (in Bayi District) and 1 male paratype (30th July 2006) from “Pai Town” (in Mainling City). However, the coordinates they provided for “Pai Town” traces to Zhaxiraodeng Township (in Mainling City) according to Google Maps, located ca. 80 km southwest of Pai Town (29°30'16.0"N 94°51'03.9"E). Later, in Di's (2009: 99) dissertation, a total of 1 male, 6 females, and 10 juveniles were reported from Bayi Town; also included was a juvenile (7th August 2003) from Mainling City. Among the 17 specimens from Bayi, based on the collection date, one was the holotype female. The single male, 1 juvenile, and 3 females were collected by Z.-Y. Di on 12th July 2008, but they all share exactly the same coordinates with the holotype female (29°41'N 94°21'E). The name of their locality was given as “Dabaishu Scenic Spot” (大柏树风景区), which is most likely what is now called “Baishuwang Scenic Spot” (柏树王景区). In the remaining 11 specimens, the neglected juvenile (2nd August 2002) reappeared. Finally, 2 females and 8 juveniles were collected near Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University by different collectors on two different dates. However, one of these juveniles appears to be the paratype female (6th August 2003) chosen from Qi et al. (2005) by Zhu et al. (2008), given the identical date and collector. The other 9 new specimens were collected by Zhu et al. on 2nd August 2006, with coordinates approximated above (Fig. 1). Additional records are cited from iNaturalist as follows: Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Xianjin Town, 29°47'29.0"N 94°22'20.9"E (iNaturalist obs. ID = 196900795), 29°39'47.7"N 94°20'09.4"E (iNaturalist obs. ID = 248548420); Nyingchi City, Mainling City, Milin Town, 29°12'50.7"N 94°12'31.0"E (iNaturalist obs. ID = 142538526; same collector of the adult male examined herein).

While the materials reported for *C. conchiformis* are puzzling, this species is fairly distinctive within all Chinese congeners due to its strongly dilated and somewhat flattened pedipalp chelae in both sexes, dorsally adorned with conspicuous and subgranular carinae. The pedipalp feature alone renders it unique and easily recognizable. Nevertheless, confusions persist when comparing descriptions by Qi et al. (2005: 34) and Zhu et al. (2008: 39–40). All sternites were described as smooth in the earlier work, but Zhu et al. (2008) noticed the subgranular and tetracarinate sternite VII. Qi et al. (2005) documented 10 carinae on metasoma I–VI, with a pair of “lateral” (likely “median lateral”) carinae gradually

fading out on segment II–IV. On the other hand, Zhu et al. (2008) described the metasoma carina formula as 10-10-8-8 for segment I–VI, mentioning the distal reduction of “lateral carinae” on segment II, yet without explaining the condition on III–IV. Qi et al. (2005) enumerated a VADC of 8 for both movable and fixed cheliceral fingers, a count decreased to 6 in Zhu et al. (2008), without providing any explanation. It is worth reiterating that both works, which M.-S. Zhu coauthored, were based on the very same female specimen.

Perplexity extends to the measurement of this same specimen—all values are virtually different. Zhu et al. (2008) claimed that TL in *C. conchiformis* is 32–41.04 mm in females and 43.47 mm in male. They wrote in their table caption that the metrics pertained to the holotype female (also noted within the table), yet it is apparent that those values correspond to the paratype male. The TL was given as 43.47 mm (\neq 39.89 mm in Qi et al.) and the PTC was given as 5/5, contradicting with their female description (3/4, *op. cit.*: 39) but instead matching that of the male (*op. cit.*: 42). Amusingly, in Di's (2009: 151) dissertation, his table 5 listed the male paratype as the holotype, while the largest female (41 mm) was degraded to the paratype. In this case, FL/CaL is less than 1 for male *C. conchiformis* (4.5/5.3), and so is the female (3.6/4.95). In the dichotomous keys provided by Di et al. (2009: 132), the lower bound of ChL/W of *C. conchiformis* was declined to 1.6, a value recycled in Di et al. (2013: 88) and Di et al. (2014: 14). This appears to be derived from the “paratype female” measured in Di's dissertation (7.7/4.8). In the original description, both holotype female and the single male were given a ChL/W of 1.8; calculation from the table 1 in Zhu et al. (2008) yields a ChL/W of 1.77. This suggests that either the value attributed to the female was erroneous, or this female was not the “paratype female” studied by Di (indeed, 41 \neq 39.89, unless one admits the mensurational inconsistency). These confusions were long overlooked, as the data were all concealed in their Chinese dissertations, which had never been published. In Yin et al. (2015: 46), measurement based on a new female specimen (deposited in USTC, without collection details) increased the upper bound to 1.9 for ChL/W of *C. conchiformis*. The authors provided a range of 1.6–1.9 for female *C. conchiformis* in their dichotomous keys (*op. cit.*: 49), yet listing the value as 1.8–1.9 in their table 3 (*op. cit.*: 48), while considering the ChL/W of males unknown. Yin et al. (*op. cit.*) recorded their new female with a DSC of 7 in table 2, which was then increased to 8 in table 3. This is because they used two different meristics—RN (“number of granule rows on the movable finger of the pedipalp”) in table 2, and RF (“row number of denticles on the fixed and movable fingers of the chelae”) in table 3 (but why adopting both “granule” and “denticle”?)—since the target finger considered differed. Clearly, RF represents a larger set ({fixed DSC, movable DSC}) than RN ({movable DSC}), yet the authors entirely ignored their count for the movable finger.

DISTRIBUTION. Bayi District and Mainling City, in Nyingchi City.

Chaerilus mainlingensis Di & Zhu, 2009

(Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/lid:zoobank.org:act:E41C0B04-03B5-4D11-9167-88BD35CE1BA3>

*Chaerilus mainling**: Di, 2009: 98, 102–103; Sun, 2010: 101.
Chaerilus mainlingensis: Di, 2009: 131–133; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97–101; Sun, 2010: 104–105; Kovařík, 2012: 2, 13; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 131–132, 138; Di et al., 2013: 52, 55, 57, 88; Di et al., 2014: 5, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42, 48, 49; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

*Di's dissertation (2009) was submitted on 24th May while Di & Zhu (2009) was published on 13th December, so “*C. mainling*” is not an ISS.

TYPE MATERIAL (Di & Zhu, 2009: 97) [lost]. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mainling City, Milin Town, Gongbuwang Manor, 29°15'30.0"N 94°17'54.3"E (approximated), 2♀, MHBHU.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. None.

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 40.36–40.72 mm for ♀; ♂ unknown. General color reddish brown to blackish brown. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular; CAM weakly concave; sternite III–VI smooth, VII subgranular and tetracarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10-8-8-8-7. PTC 3–4 in ♀. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers 7–8/6. Pedipalp chela ChL/W ca. 2.4–2.75 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{4-5} , and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular, E and I obsolete; D_3 highly obsolete as an unridged dark stripe; DSC of movable finger 7, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid, but pending the designation of a neotype.

REMARKS. The description of this species was based on only two adult females, which remain the sole specimens known to date. Consequently, the available information is largely confined to the original description, and subsequent publications have been predominantly misleading. However, confusions nonetheless present in the original paper itself. Di & Zhu (2009: 98) described the chela of *C. mainlingensis* as “...*dorsal internal*[= D_5], *digital*[= D_1], *dorsal external*, *ventral internal*[= V_3], *ventral external*[= V_1] *carinae with smooth granular*, *external secondary*[= E], *external and interomedian*[= I] *carinae obsolete or vestigial*...”. In a different section on the same page, the authors stated that “...*dorsal secondary carinae*[= D_3] *of the chela obsolete as a black stripes without ridges*...”, suggesting that the correct description should likely read: “*dorsal secondary*[= D_3], *external secondary*[= E] and *interomedian*[= I] *carinae obsolete or vestigial*”. This leaves their “dorsal external” carina as “dorsal marginal” carina (= D_4). In contrast, Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro (2013: 138) diagnosed this species with “8 granulated carinae”, and reduced its PTC to 3 (3–4 in Di & Zhu (2009: 98)).

In their dichotomous keys, Di et al. (2013: 88) differentiated this species from *C. dibangvalleycus* by one of the two characters (the other being pedipalp femur longer than carapace in *C. mainlingensis*, and the opposite in *C. dibangvalleycus*) as follows (recycled by Di et al. (2014: 14) and Yin et al. (2015: 49)):

“...8–9 minute teeth on inner ventral margins of movable and immovable fingers respectively...*C. dibangvalleycus*”

“...7–8 minute teeth on inner ventral margins of movable and immovable fingers respectively...*C. mainlingensis*”

They used “respectively” to refer to the movable and fixed fingers while providing only one range for both, which is puzzling. At first glance, this description seems to pertain to the chelicerae, as the terms “minute teeth” and “inner ventral margins” are typically used to describe cheliceral dentition (VAD; pedipalp movable fingers do not have dentate inner ventral margins). However, they cited Bastawade (2006: fig. 5) and Di & Zhu (2009: fig. 11), both depicting the **movable finger of pedipalp** chela. This is rather baffling as Bastawade did not provide the DSC of fixed pedipalp finger. In Bastawade (2006: 451, right column), the author merely mentioned that “...Pedipalp...*immovable finger*...*provided below*[below] *with double row of minute dentition*; *movable finger*...*provided with double row of minute dentition*...”. On page 454 (*op. cit.*, left column), the author provided a DSC of 7–8 for the **pedipalp movable finger** of *C. dibangvalleycus*. In Di & Zhu (2009: 98, left column), the authors stated “...*dentate margins of fixed and movable fingers of pedipalp chela with seven rows of granules*...” for *C. mainlingensis*. Neither datum accords with the keys originally provided by Di et al. (2013). However, if one attempts to locate those values in the respective papers, it can be found that in Bastawade (2006: 451, left column), the author stated “...**Chelicera**... *four and eighth[eight] to nine minute teeth on inner ventral margins of movable and immovable fingers respectively*...” (though he later shifted these counts to 5 and 10 in his interspecific comparison; *op. cit.*: 454), and in Di & Zhu (2009: 98), the authors stated “...**Chelicerae**...*ventral inner edges of movable finger with six medium-size teeth and one or two obsolete small teeth*...” (i.e., 7–8 VAD for cheliceral movable finger). Additionally, their figure 4 showed **six** VAD for the **fixed** cheliceral finger of *C. mainlingensis*. If Di et al. (2013) in fact referred to those values, they would essentially be comparing the VADC of fixed cheliceral finger of *C. dibangvalleycus* against that of the movable cheliceral finger of *C. mainlingensis*, which is inscrutable, as the senior author of that paper was the same author described *C. mainlingensis*. To clarify, the correct meristics for the two species are as follows (movable/fixed): (1) *C. dibangvalleycus*: cheliceral finger, 4–5/8–10, pedipalp chelal finger, 7–8/?; (2) *C. mainlingensis*: cheliceral finger, 7–8/6, pedipalp chelal finger, 7/7.

Despite this, *C. mainlingensis* itself is well distinguished according to the original data alone. The original authors compared it with *C. insignis*, *C. pictus*, *C. truncatus*, and *C. tryznai* based on mostly valid characters, particularly the DSC, which effectively differs it from *C. insignis*, *C. pictus*,

and *C. truncatus*. Both *C. insignis* and *C. truncatus* are also geographically distant from the Tibetan region where *C. mainlingensis* occurs. The absence of D_3 and carinate sternite VII corroborates its distinctions from the geographically closest *C. tryznai* within this set of congeners. The diagnostic table summarized herein highlights these two characters as key differentiators between the two species. Within Tibetan *Chaerilus*, absence of D_3 is so far observed in *C. dibangvalleycus*, *C. mainlingensis*, and *C. tricostatus*. Based on the original data, *C. tricostatus* can be easily separated from *C. mainlingensis* by a higher DSC alone, while *C. dibangvalleycus* is supposedly distinguished by its higher VADC on both cheliceral fingers and slightly higher female PTC. However, it is also worth mentioning that the denticle subrows of movable finger illustrated for *C. mainlingensis* might be either abnormal (cf. Figs. 128–129) or inaccurate, as no clear imbrication could be discerned between most adjacent subrows, and several subrows appeared atypically elongated. If DSC turns out to be an erroneous diagnostic, the validity of *C. mainlingensis* might still be defended by its slightly lower female PTC (no pectinal anomaly was observed in the original illustration). Although the current investigation revealed that *C. conchiformis* is the geographically closest species (Fig. 1), the two species can be readily differed by the pedipalp chela alone. Nevertheless, since no photograph was provided for this species, further investigations are warranted to definitively confirm its validity, particularly against *C. dibangvalleycus*.

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from the type locality; Gongbuwang Manor of Milin Town, Mainling City, in Nyingchi City.

***Chaerilus pictus* (Pocock, 1890)**

(Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:0B2EE7A0-5DFB-437A-8C64-ACF469E52E22>

Uromachus pictus: Pocock, 1890: 250–252.

Chaerilus pictus: Kraepelin, 1894: 142–144; Kraepelin, 1899: 159; Pocock, 1900: 59–62; Kraepelin, 1913: 151–153; Takashima, 1945: 100; Pérez, 1974: 31; Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 319, 332–339; Kovařík, 1998: 129; Fet, 2000: 327; Kovařík, 2000: 38, 40, 53–54, 57, 59, 70–72; Kovařík, 2001: 84; Zhu et al., 2004: 113–114; Bastawade, 2006: 449–450; Zhu et al., 2008: 37–40, 43–44, 48; Di et al., 2009: 131–133; Di, 2009: 98, 104; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97–98, 101; Sun, 2010: 101, 106, 208; Lourenço & Duhem, 2010: 14, 21, 23; Kovařík, 2012: 3; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 132–133, 139, 144; Di et al., 2013: 52, 55–56, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 4, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42, 48, 50; Di et al., 2015: 111; Lourenço, 2020: 5; Tang, 2022a: 55; Tang, 2025: 13, 16.

Chaerilus gemmifer: Pocock, 1894b: 81; Kraepelin, 1899: 159–160; Pocock, 1900: 60–61; Kraepelin, 1913: 151–153; Takashima, 1945: 100; Pérez, 1974: 31; Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 319, 346–351; Kovařík, 1998: 129; Fet, 2000: 326; Kovařík, 2000: 38, 40, 53–54, 57, 71;

Bastawade, 2006: 449–450; Tang, 2025: 13, 16.

= *Chaerilus gemmifer* Pocock, 1894b: 81 (syn. Kovařík, 2000: 53). <http://zoobank.org/?lsid=urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:A4557E07-5FBA-48BF-8E71-B46D9E53B2AF> TYPE MATERIAL (Pocock, 1894b: 81). **Bangladesh, Sylhet Division**, Sylhet District, Sylhet City, 2♀, NHMUK.

Chaerilus pictus var. *gemmifer*: Kraepelin, 1913: 153.

Chaerilus pictus: misidentification; see *C. conchiformis*.

TYPE MATERIAL (Pocock, 1890: 252). **Bangladesh, Sylhet Division**, Sylhet District, Sylhet City, 2♂, NHMUK.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. None.

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 38–65.7 mm in both sexes (?). General color reddish brown to reddish black, strongly variegated; mesosoma yellowish brown with a yellow posteromedian stripe on each tergite, flanked by a pair of transverse yellow bands; telson reddish. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular, coarser in females; CAM weakly concave; sternite III–VII smooth, VII acarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10-8-8-8-7. Male metasoma and telson strongly elongated. PTC 5–6 in males and 3–4 in females. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers 8/4–5. Pedipalp chela slightly slender in ♂, ChL/W ca. 2.53 in ♂ and 2.39 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{3-5} , E , and $V_{1,3}$ present and subgranular; DSC of movable finger 13–14, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid.

REMARKS. This species was originally treated in a new genus by Pocock (1890), who named it as *Uromachus* (literally “tail warrior”) due to its markedly elongated metasoma and telson in the type specimens. The specific epithet denotes its dark variegation on a reddish brown base. The holotype male was recorded with a TL of 62 mm and a PTC of 5/5 (Pocock, 1890: 252). Pocock considered it to be closely allied to *Chaerilus* except for the abnormal metasoma morphology, presuming it to be a sexual dimorphism—which it is, and characteristic of adult males. This trait alone makes the species unique within the entire genus. Kovařík (*in* Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 144) documented his captive rearing of two males from Tripura, India, from immaturity to adulthood. The drastic elongation of the metasoma and telson was observed to occur only after the final ecdysis, with one male increasing its total length by 1.81 times (from 37 to 67 mm), while the metasoma and telson length increased by 1.91 and 2.18 times, respectively.

Pocock (1894a: 91) subsequently suspected that *Uromachus* was synonymous with *Chaerilus* considering the absence of other differing characters, but he did not formally synonymize the two genera or transfer *U. pictus* to the latter genus. Kraepelin (1894: 143–144) directly referred to this species as *C. pictus* and provide another brief description, likely based on the same holotype male given the identical

TL and PTC. Later that same year, Pocock (1894b: 81) described *C. gemmifer*, a species he considered related to *C. margaritatus* Pocock, 1894 (= *C. truncatus* Karsch, 1879). Both specific epithets allude to the coarsely granular cuticle in those species. Pocock's description of *C. gemmifer* was based on two dried females from Sylhet, Bangladesh, the same locality as *C. pictus*. The holotype female was recorded with a TL of 38 mm and a PTC of 3–4. In his general review of this genus, Kraepelin (1899: 159–160) briefly summarized both species, again providing a similar description for *C. pictus*. He listed several distinctions in granulation, carinae, and telson between the two species, yet speculating that *C. gemmifer* might represent the female of *C. pictus*. Similarly, Pocock (1900: 60–62) redescribed both species, but this time he provided a description of a female *C. pictus*, which was based on an immature specimen (TL 32 mm, PTC 5). How Pocock identified this immature female as *C. pictus* remains dubious, as adult females were unknown at the time, and determining the species would have required observations of copulatory behavior in the wild or detailed ontogenetic data. He noticed several similarities with *C. gemmifer*, such as coloration (albeit paler, which is typical for young *Chaerilus*), relative length of carapace and metasomal segments, telson vesicle, and chela shape. In his dichotomous keys (*op. cit.*: 56), he differentiated the two species merely by the density of granulation on carapace, tergites, and intercarinal space on metasoma, and coloration.

Kraepelin (1913: 151–153) studied 3 adult males, 10 adult females, and 1 juvenile male from seven different localities. While he discovered variation in color, no morphological distinctions were found, as female specimens with paler color also had coarse granulation (“...es waren demnach sämtliche zehn weiblichen Exemplare in Hinblick auf die grobe Perlkörnelerung der Rückenplatten als *Ch. gemmifer* anzusprechen, nicht nur die dunkelbraunen, in Übereinstimmung mit Pocock's Angabe, sondern auch die einfarbig gelbroten...”). Initially, Kraepelin suspected that these color variations might indicate different “races (Rassen)” of the species, characterized by features such as the presence or absence of an interocular sulcus and differences in chelal carinal granulation. However, he abandoned this idea upon finding specimens in the same jar exhibiting both states. He also briefly considered whether the lighter-colored specimens should be referred to as “var. *gemmifer*”. Kraepelin, given the sparse granulation on the female *C. pictus* described by Pocock, suspected it to be characteristic of an immature female specimen. However, after examining a young male showing sparse granulation, he recognized that the female studied by Pocock was also a juvenile male, given the relatively long metasoma and higher PTC. This observation aligned with the typical sexual dimorphism in *Chaerilus* species, where males tend to have sparser granulation than females. Consequently he considered the purported interspecific differences to be of sexual nature, and regarded *C. gemmifer* as conspecific with *C. pictus*, though he still did not synonymize the two species. He characterized male *C. pictus* with a PTC of 5–6 and female of 3–4.

Tikader & Bastawade (1983) continued to treat *Chaerilus pictus* and *C. gemmifer* as separate species without offering any justifications. Inferring from the references they cited, it seems likely that they did not consult Kraepelin's (1913) work. Their dichotomous keys (Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 319) differentiated the two species on the basis of relative aculeus length (with respect to vesicle length) in females, relative position of median ocelli, and interocular surface morphoscultures—traits that were not demonstrated to be intraspecifically stable. They redescribed both species in a more detailed manner, providing a DVAC for movable/fixed fingers of 8/5 and 8/4 for male *C. pictus* and female *C. gemmifer* (*op. cit.*: 336, 348), respectively. Since Pocock's (1890: 251) original description, the sternites of this species have been described as smooth, and no carinae were noted for sternite VII. In Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 338), the sternites were numbered two digits lower (i.e., VII was referred to as V), but they similarly described the sternites as smooth and acarinate. Kovařík (2000: 53–54) examined the type materials of *C. pictus* and *C. gemmifer* alongside several other specimens, and formally synonymized the two species. He characterized this species with a TL of 38–65.7 mm, a DSC of 13–14, and a PTC of 3–6. In his table 1, he provided measurements for ChL and ChW of holotype male *C. pictus* and lectotype female *C. gemmifer*, from which a ChL/W of 2.53 and 2.39 can be calculated respectively. The length to width ratio of telson for the holotype male derived from the data originally provided by Pocock (1890: 252) is 4.68 (11.7/2.5), but based on Kovařík (2000: tab. 1) it increased to 5.24 (11/2.1). According to the same table, the female lectotype *C. gemmifer* had a ratio of 2.62 (5.5/2.1). Pocock (1890: 251) described the pedipalp manus with ten complete, subtubercular to granular carinae, but both Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 336, 348) and Kovařík (2000: 53) reckoned only 7–8 carinae. The descriptions and data in those works were later followed by Zhu et al. (2008: 38–39, 48), Di et al. (2009: 133), Di (2009: 98, 104), Di & Zhu (2009: 98), Sun (2010: 101, 106), Kovařík (2012: 3), Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro (2013: 132, 139), Di et al. (2013: 88), Di et al. (2014: 14), and Yin et al. (2015: 48, 50). These subsequent works do not contain new information regarding the two species beyond what was already mentioned, except for the contributions of Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro (2013) to the ontogenetic observation under captive condition.

This species was first reported from China by Kraepelin (1913: 153) based on a male from Daphla Hills. Misidentification by Qi et al. (2005: 34–38) is discussed above. According to the map in Bastawade (2006: 450), the following localities are approximated: Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, 27°39'20.0"N 94°24'55.0"E (as *C. pictus*); Shannan City, Tsona City, 26°59'56.3"N 93°27'32.8"E (as *C. pictus*), 27°34'40.0"N 94°06'04.2"E (as *C. gemmifer*). Due to distortions in the map, it was not possible to accurately approximate the two records near Zayü County (Nyingchi County), which were listed under both species names. However, the map suggested that these records came from an area south of Lohit District, which has never been part of China, leading to their exclusion in this context (Fig. 1). One of these records was, however,

Figures 20–21. Adult male *Chaerilus* cf. *pseudoconchiformis*, fresh specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (20) and ventral (21) views, under white light; record included in the map.

cited by Di & Zhu (2009: fig. 17). Inferring from the contours in Bastawade's (2006) map, this record likely corresponds to a location in Changlang (27°53'16.0"N 96°38'42.4"E), within the territory of India. The single male mentioned by Kraepelin (1913: 153) from Daffla Hills is approximated to be located in Tsona City (27°19'59.9"N 93°29'43.1"E). In addition, another iNaturalist record (obs. ID = 97191848) of this species was also reported from Tsona City (27°01'48.5"N 92°49'43.0"E).

When considering characteristics of both sexes, *C. pictus* stands out as one of the most disparate species within either the Chinese species or the entire genus. However, species differentiation may be hindered by the lack of specimens of

both sexes, making it crucial to prioritize sex-independent characters in diagnoses. The high DSC (13–14) relates it to *C. tessellatus* (11) and *C. tricostatus* (10–12), from both of which it can be supposedly differentiated by the absence of carinae on sternite VII and a slightly lower VADC of cheliceral fixed finger (4–5 vs. 7–8). It further differs from *C. tricostatus* by the presence of D_3 , and probably from *C. tessellatus* by the presence of only 8 carinae on metasoma II (vs. 10; however, this character may be ambiguous).

DISTRIBUTION. Mêdog County in Nyingchi City, and Tsona City in Shannan City.

Figures 22–27. Adult male *Chaerilus* cf. *pseudoconchiformis*, carapace (22), pectines (23), sternite VII (24), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (25) under white light, and left (26) and right (27) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

Chaerilus pseudoconchiformis Yin, Qiu, Pan, Li & Di, 2015

(Figures 20–35; Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:569B23FC-86FB-4E16-8487-047B100BF9DC>

Chaerilus pseudoconchiformis: Yin et al., 2015: 41–50; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 12, 21, 55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2023: 20; Tang, 2025: 16.

TYPE MATERIAL (Yin et al., 2015: 43). **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bayi District, 2♂9♀, USTC.

MATERIAL EXAMINED (VT) [putative]. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Layue Township, 29°59'46.6"N 94°53'01.5"E, 2412 m a. s. l., 23rd November 2022, 1♂1♀, leg. Yiyang Xu (Figs. 20–35).

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 32–37.4 mm for ♂ and 32.5–39 mm for ♀. General color dark reddish brown. Two pairs of lateral ocelli

Figures 28–29. Adult female *Chaerilus* cf. *pseudoconchiformis*, fresh specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (28) and ventral (29) views, under white light; record included in the map.

and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular; CAM straight; sternite III–VI smooth, VII granular and acarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10-8-8-8-7. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 5 in ♂ and 3–4 in ♀. VADC of cheliceral movable finger 2–9. Pedipalp chela slender in ♂, ChL/W ca. in 3.2–3.4 ♂ and 2.3–2.6 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{3-5} , E , and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular; DSC of movable finger 8–9, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid, but species characterization requires refinement.

REMARKS. This is the most recently described Chinese *Chaerilus* species and has not been reviewed. Yin et al. (2015: 43) characterized this species based on 2 adult males and 9 adult females from an unspecified locality in Bayi District. They differentiated this species from other congeners by a composite of TL (30–40 mm), CAM (straight), ChL/W (average 3.3 in ♂ and 2.5 in ♀), DSC (8–9), and PTC (5 in ♂ and 3–4 in ♀), further considering *C. conchiformis* and *C. wrzecionkoi* to be the most morphologically resemblant congeners on the basis of similar TL and DSC. This is misleading as TL is hardly a diagnostic character for Chinese *Chaerilus* with the exception

Figures 30–35. Adult female *Chaerilus* cf. *pseudoconchiformis*, carapace (30), pectines (31), sternite VII (32), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (33) under white light, and left (34) and right (35) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

of *C. pictus* and *C. tricostatus* that can easily exceed 40 mm, and DSC alone would also include *C. assamensis* (and/or *C. dibangvalleycus*), *C. mainlingensis*, and *C. tryznai* within this set of similar congeners if one were to allow for 1 digit of intraspecific variation (i. e., DSC = 7–9). ChL/W was used as

the primary character to distinguish *C. pseudoconchiformis* from *C. conchiformis* and *C. wrzecionkoi*, which is particularly effective for the first congener of comparison. In their Etymology section, they regarded *C. pseudoconchiformis* as “very similar” to *C. conchiformis*. In fact, their new species

<i>Chaerilus</i> species	TL	PTC	DSC	VADC (M/F)	ChL/W	FL/CaL	CAM	CG	D_3	SVII	MIIC
<i>C. assamensis</i> * <i>C. dibangvalleyceus</i>	♂ 31.5 ^[3] –41.5 * ^[6] ♀ 36.75 * ^[6]	♂ 4 * ^[6] –5 ^[3] ♀ 4 ^[3] –5 * ^[6]	7–8 ^[3] 7–8 * ^[6]	4–5/8–10 * ^[6]	♂ 3.25? * ^[6] ♀ ?	♂ <1 * ^[6]	♂ \wedge ^[3] ♂ \vee * ^[6]	SC * ^[6]	0 * ^[6,11]	G, 4 * ^[11]	8 * ^[6]
<i>C. conchiformus</i>	♂ 43.47 ^[7] ♀ 32–41.04 ^[7]	♂ 5 ^[7] ♀ 3–4 ^[7]	8 ^[7] 7 ^[12]	♂ 5/5 ^[7] ♀ 6/6 ^[7] 8/8 ^[5]	♂ & ♀ 1.8 ^[7] ♀ 1.6 ^[8] 1.9 ^[11]	♂ <1 ^[7] ♀ <1 ^[7]	— ^[11]	SC ^[7]	1 ^[7]	SG, 4 ^[7]	10 ^[7]
<i>C. mainlingensis</i>	♂ ? ♀ 40.5–40.7 ^[9]	♂ ? ♀ 3–4 ^[9]	7 ^[9]	♂ ? ♀ 7–8/6 ^[9]	♂ ? ♀ 2.4–2.75 ^[9]	♂ ? ♀ >1 ^[9]	\vee ^[9]	S ^[9]	0 ^[9]	SG, 4 ^[9]	8 ^[9]
<i>C. pictus</i> * <i>C. gemmifer</i>	♂ 62 ^[1] ♀ 38 * ^[2] ♂ & ♀ 38–65.7 ^[4]	♂ 5 ^[1] ♀ 3–4 * ^[2] 3–6 ^[4]	13–14 ^[4]	8/4–5 ^[7]	♂ 2.53 ^[4] ♀ 2.39 * ^[4]	♂ <1 ^[1]	\vee ^[1]	SC ^[1] C * ^[2]	1 ^[1]	S, 0 ^[1]	8 ^[1]
<i>C. pseudoconchiformus</i>	♂ 32–37.4 ^[11] ♀ 32.5–39 ^[11]	♂ 5 ^[11] ♀ 3–4 ^[11]	8–9 ^[11]	♂ 2–3/? ^[11] ♀ 3–9/? ^[11]	♂ 3.2–3.4 ^[11] ♀ 2.3–2.6 ^[11]	♂ >1 ^[11] ♀ <1 ^[11]	— ^[11]	D ^[11]	1 ^[11]	G, 0 ^[11]	8 ^[11]
<i>C. tessellatus</i>	♂ ? ♀ 35.3–51.66 ^[7]	♂ ? ♀ 5 ^[5]	11 ^[7]	♂ ? ♀ 6/? ^[5] 8/7 ^[7]	♂ ? ♀ 2.2 ^[7]	♂ ? ♀ <1 ^[5]	\vee ^[7] — ^[11]	DC ^[5] S-Sm ^[7,11]	0 ^[8] 1 ^[7,11]	S, 4 ^[5]	10 ^[5]
<i>C. tricostatus</i>	♂ 48–52.1 ^[4] ♀ 55.3 ^[4] –59.2 ^[8]	♂ 5–6 ^[4] ♀ 4–6 ^[8]	10–11 ^[6] 11–12 ^[4]	7–11 ^[8] /7–8 ^[6]	♂ 3.71 ^[4] ♀ 2.21 ^[8] –2.43 ^[4]	♂ >1 ^[4] ♀ <1 ^[4]	— ^[12]	♂ S ^[4] ♀ D ^[4,8]	0 ^[8]	S, 4 ^[4] SG ^[8] G ^[11]	8 ^[4]
<i>C. tryznai</i>	? 30 ^[4] ♂ 32.3 ^[4] ♀ 30.74 ^[7] ♀ 38.9 ^[4] –44 ^[11]	♂ 4 ^[4] ♀ 3–4 ^[4]	8 ^[4]	6/4 ^[7]	♂ 3.12 ^[4] ♀ 2.91 ^[4] ♀ 2.08? 2.2? ^[7] ♀ 2.6–2.8 ^[12]	♂ >1 ^[4] ♀ <1 ^[4]	— ^[4]	SC ^[7]	1 ^[11]	G, 0 ^[4]	8 ^[4]
<i>C. wrzecionkoi</i>	♂ 33–37? ^[10] ♀ 39–41? ^[10]	♂ 4–5? ^[10] ♀ 3–4? ^[10]	8 ^[10] 9 ^[11]	?	♂ 2.57 ^[10] ♀ 2.37 ^[10]	♂ >1 ^[10] ♀ <1 ^[10]	— ^[10]	SC ^[10]	1 ^[10]	G, 0 ^[10]	8 ^[10]

Table 1. Conventional diagnostics for Chinese *Chaerilus* species retrieved from: [1] Pocock (1890); [2] Pocock (1894); [3] Kraepelin (1913); [4] Kovařík (2000); [5] Qi et al. (2005); [6] Bastawade (2006); [7] Zhu et al. (2008); [8] Di et al. (2009); [9] Di & Zhu (2009); [10] Kovařík (2012); [11] Yin et al. (2015). If there is no difference between the original (or earlier) description and subsequent studies, only the original (or earlier) paper is cited; otherwise, only the next paper is cited if it does not differ from later studies. **M/F:** movable and fixed cheliceral fingers. **CAM states:** \wedge , slightly convex; \vee , slightly concave; —, straight. **CG states:** S, sparse; D, dense; SC, sparse and coarse; DC, dense and coarse; Sm, nearly smooth; N/A, not applicable (not qualified in the same set of terms). **D_3 states:** 0, absence; 1, presence. **SVII states:** G, granular; SG, subgranular; S, smooth; 0, acarinate; 4, tetracarinate.

barely resembles *C. conchiformus*. The overall morphology would place *C. pseudoconchiformus* into a set comprising *C. tryznai* and *C. wrzecionkoi* sharing the following characters: TL ca. 30–40 mm, PTC 3–5 (3–4 in ♀), DSC 8–9, CAM straight, D_3 present, sternite VII granular and acarinate, metasoma carinae 10-8-8-8-7.

The authors further used two confounding ratiometric terms, “length ratio of pedipalp (LRP)” and “length ratio of total length (LRT)”:

“...*C. pseudoconchiformus* sp. n. has more slender pedipalps than *C. wrzecionkoi*...in other words, the length ratio of pedipalp (LRP) is distinctly larger than the length ratio of total length (LRT) of *C. pseudoconchiformus* sp. n. and *C. wrzecionkoi*: 1.14 (LRP), 1.01 (LRT) in male holotypes; 1.08 (LRP), 0.95 (LRT) in female allotypes of *C. pseudoconchiformus* sp. n. and *C. wrzecionkoi* (Table 1)...”

This is almost incomprehensible at first glance (particularly confusing is the diction of “the length ratio of total length”). Since the authors considered *C. pseudoconchiformus* to have slender pedipalps relative to a

reference system, if they were referring to the ratio of pedipalp length to TL, the results based on their table 1 are as follows: (1) *C. pseudoconchiformus*, 0.557 (or the inverse, 1.794) in ♂ (note: summation of carapace, mesosoma, metasoma, and telson lengths results in a TL of 37.5 mm, not 37.4 mm as given by the authors) and 0.464 (or the inverse, 2.16) in ♀; (2) *C. wrzecionkoi*, 0.495 (or the inverse, 2.022) in ♂ and 0.41 (or the inverse, 2.438) in ♀. However, the ratios provided by the authors were close to 1, suggesting similar values of numerator and denominator. An epiphany soon dawned upon me—they were dividing the pedipalp length (or TL) of *C. pseudoconchiformus* by that of *C. wrzecionkoi*: (1) between holotype males, pedipalp length ratio = 20.9/18.3, TL ratio = 37.4/37 (which should be 37.5 for the numerator); (2) between paratype females, pedipalp length ratio = 17.2/16, TL ratio = 37.1/39. A more intelligible phrasing would be “the pedipalp length ratio (PLR) between *C. pseudoconchiformus* and *C. wrzecionkoi* is distinctly greater than their total length ratio (TLR): between holotype males, PLR = 1.14, TLR = 1.01”. Yet, this calculation approach is nonetheless rather bizarre, which hindered my immediate understanding. If their initial

<i>Chaerilus</i> species	Distribution records within China						Arunachal Pradesh	
	Bayi (LZ)	Bomê (LZ)	Mainling (LZ)	Mêdog (LZ)	Zayü (LZ)	Cuona (SN)	Extends to	Limited to
<i>C. assamensis</i>					✓			✓
<i>C. conchiformis</i>	✓		✓					
<i>C. herta</i> sp. n.				✓			?	
<i>C. mainlingensis</i>			✓					
<i>C. pictus</i>				✓		✓		✓
<i>C. pseudoconchiformis</i>	✓							
<i>C. tessellatus</i>	✓		✓	✓				
<i>C. tricostatus</i>				✓	✓	✓	✓	
<i>C. tryznai</i>		✓		✓			✓	
<i>C. wrzecionkoi</i>		✓						

Table 2. Distribution of Chinese *Chaerilus* species. For clarification, “Bayi” refers to “Bayi District”, and “Mainling” refers to “Mainling City”. Abbreviations: LZ, Nyingchi City; SN, Shannan City.

purpose was to compare the relative “slenderness” (which pertained to the length, not length to width ratio) of the pedipalp between the two species, then the pedipalp length should be used as the numerator to be compared against (i.e., standardized by) the same category of denominator (e. g., TL) across different species, but with the value taken from the same individual—as suggested by the initial assumption for their calculation above. What does the ratiometric derived from one character (e. g., pedipalp length or TL) of two individuals (e. g., holotype males) of two species tell? And what insight can be gleaned from comparing two such ratiometrics? The authors likely implied that, under similar TL (ratio near 1, in males) or when their new species is smaller (further below 1, in females), *C. pseudoconchiformis* has proportionally longer pedipalps (above 1) than *C. wrzecionkoi*. This complicates the problem and is clearly only feasible for paired comparison. What if there are 5 males and 7 females for *C. pseudoconchiformis* and 3 males and 9 females for *C. wrzecionkoi*? Each of the 5 males from the first group has to be paired respectively with the 3 males from the second group to derive a ratiometric, and the same goes for the females. Eventually, one demands 5×3×2 (pedipalp length and TL) ratiometrics for the between-male comparison and 7×9×2 for the between-female comparison. However, a much simpler method would only require 5+3 and 7+9 ratiometrics respectively, as the pedipalp length of each specimen is standardized by its own TL.

Once the conundrum is resolved, one moves on to question if the interspecific differences in those ratiometrics (1.14 vs. 1.01 for males and 1.08 vs. 0.95 for females; virtually, for both, equivalent to comparing 1.1 vs. 1.0) suggested by the authors are stable (who considered the differences to be “distinct”). Although they examined 2 males and 9 females for their new species, this difference they leveraged was based only on a single pair of adults and therefore

did not account for intraspecific variations. Moreover, the resultant value heavily hinges upon mensurational accuracy and consistency. Based on the Table 1 summarizing the diagnostics in this study, *C. pseudoconchiformis*, *C. tryznai*, and *C. wrzecionkoi* are only differentiable by ChL/W (VADC of either or both cheliceral fingers lacking for some species, and subjectively qualified granulation density is not reliable in the absence of sufficient comparative photographs). However, utilizing distinctions in ChL/W to differentiate those species would either require specimens of both sexes, or be obstructed by potential overlap or intermediacy in practice due to intraspecific variations and measurement inconsistencies. For readers’ convenience, the ChL/W of the three species are listed as follows: *C. pseudoconchiformis* (3.2–3.4 ♂, 2.3–2.6 in ♀; sample size, 2♂9♀), *C. tryznai* (3.12 in ♂, 2.6–2.91 in ♀; sample size, 1♂14♀, type series, plus the two females examined by Yin et al. (2015)), and *C. wrzecionkoi* (2.57 in ♂, 2.37 in ♀; sample size, 2♂2♀). Nevertheless, it is beyond my scope to verify if all data were based on all reported specimens. Another matter worth noting is the considerable variation in the VADC of movable finger indicated by Yin et al. (*op. cit.*: 49), where the 9 females yielded a total range of 3–9, unprecedented in any other Chinese congeners (Table 1). This might challenge its diagnostic utility, especially since the VADC data for other Chinese *Chaerilus* are unlikely based on adequate samples. Last but not least, those authors might as well forgo illustrating the denticle morphology of the chelicerae if what they observed amounts to nothing more than arbitrary zigzag serrations (*op. cit.*: figs. 7–10), which appears to be a shared problem across multiple Chinese papers where hand-drawn illustrations were favored.

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from the type locality; Bayi District (formerly as “Nyingchi County”), in Nyingchi City.

Chaerilus tessellatus Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005

(Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:0C5F0557-1B6D-4BFE-A2E3-9A2CA9789B39>

Chaerilus tessellatus: Qi et al., 2005: 1, 30–34, 38; Yang, 2008: 8, 46, 48–50, 76; Zhu et al., 2008: 37–38, 40, 44–46, 50; Di et al., 2009: 131–133; Di, 2009: 98, 104–106, 193–195; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97, 101; Sun, 2010: 101, 106–107; Kovařík, 2012: 3; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 132–133, 141; Di et al., 2013: 52, 56, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 4, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42, 48, 50; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

TYPE MATERIAL (Qi et al., 2005: 30) [lost]. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Drepung Township (?), 29°02'N 95°03'E (type locality), 1♀, MHBU; Nyingchi City, Mêdog County (incorrectly given as “Bomê County”), 29°08'N 95°07'E (Drepung Township?), 2♀, MHBU & MNHN; Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, 1♀, MHBU.

OTHER MATERIAL. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, same locality as holotype, 1 juv. ♀ paratype? (Yang, 2008: 48); Nyingchi City, Bayi District (incorrectly given as “Bayi Town to Bomê County”), Sejila Mountain (“Mt. Sela”), 29°37'38.3"N 94°39'28.4"E (approximated), 1♀, MHBU (Zhu et al., 2008: 44; Di, 2009: 105); Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Dongjiu Village, 29°49'46.6"N 94°44'35.6"E (approximated), 2 juv. ♀, MHBU (Zhu et al., 2008: 44); Nyingchi City, Mainling City, 1 juv. (♀?; Di, 2009: 105).

MATERIAL EXAMINED. None.

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 35.3–51.66 mm for ♀; ♂ unknown. General color dark brown, variegated; chelal manus and telson reddish brown; legs pale brown (MNHN-RS-RS8623). Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites smooth or granular (MNHN-RS-RS8623); CAM weakly concave to straight; sternite III–VII smooth, VII tetracarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10-10-10-8-7. PTC 3 (MNHN-RS-RS8623) or 5 in ♀. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers 6–8/7. Pedipalp chela ChL/W ca. 2.2 in ♀; manus with D_1 , $D_{3(?)5}$, and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular, **E** and **I** obsolete; DSC of movable finger 11, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Dubious and pending the designation of a neotype; the status of paratype RS8623 is indeterminate (the specimen on which the minimum TL of 35.3 mm was based was not explained in their description, but it could possibly be this paratype). See also discussions under ‘7. Taxonomic conclusion’.

REMARKS. This species was the second *Chaerilus* described from China, by Qi et al. (2005). The type series included 4 adult females from Mêdog County, with the type locality

allegedly situated in Drepung Township. Qi et al. (*op. cit.* 30) incorrectly attributed one paratype locality to Bomê County, an error eventually repeated for eight years by Zhu et al. (2008: 44), Di et al. (2009: 133), and Di et al. (2013: 56). It is noteworthy that the Drepung Township (ca. 29°14'15.9"N 95°10'33.7"E) is much closer (ca. 13 km) to the coordinates they provided for this locality than to the type locality (ca. 26 km), which enters Arunachal Pradesh. In his dissertation, Yang (2008: 48) included an additional juvenile female (regarded as a paratype) allegedly collected alongside the holotype, and modified the type locality coordinates to “N29.11 E95.10”, which do not even align with the original ones in decimal form (29.03, 95.05). If these new coordinates are in decimal form, they are now closer to Drepung Township (ca. 16 km); if in DMS form (29°11'N 95°10'E), the distance would be even smaller (ca. 6 km). He also added another adult female collected by M.-S. Zhu from “Mt. Sejila” (色季拉山), which seems to be located in Bayi District (originally given as “Bayi Town to Bomê County”). These changes were later adopted by Di (2009: 105) in his dissertation, who documented a new juvenile collected by himself from an unspecified locality in Mainling County. In their redescription of this species, the record from Mt. Sejila was changed into “Bomi County, Mt. Sela” (Zhu et al., 2008: 44), and two additional female juveniles were reported from Dongjiu Village (Bayi District). All specimens, except for the female “paratype” juvenile (Yang, 2008: 48), and one juvenile from Mainling (Di, 2009: 105), were finally listed in Di et al. (2013: 56).

Problems with this species extend to inconsistencies in its morphological characterization. Qi et al. (2005: 30) described this species based on the female holotype (incorrectly referred to as “male holotype”) and provided a VADC of 6 for the cheliceral movable finger. Zhu et al. (2008: 44, 47) redescribed this species based on the same specimen but changed the count to 8 again without any explanation, adding a new VADC (7) for the fixed finger. Measurements for the holotype female also differed between the two works; for instance, TL was measured as 48.93 in Qi et al. (2005: 30) but as 51.66 in Zhu et al. (2008: tab. 1). Especially intriguing is their measurement for ChW, whereas Qi et al. (2005: 34) recorded 4.21 mm, Zhu et al. (2008: tab. 1) increased it to 5.22, a substantial difference. This is entirely understandable, yet it simultaneously reinforces my concern regarding the measurement accuracy (reproducibility) in scorpion taxonomy. However, the authors did not give any clarification for their data incongruence. In addition, both Qi et al. (2005: 30, 33) and Zhu et al. (2008: 46–47) recorded and illustrated a pair of pectines each with 5 teeth in the female holotype and suggested no intraspecific variation, but the paratype female (MNHN-RS-RS8623) shows only 3 teeth on either pectine. More recently, Yin et al. (2015: tab. 3) characterized the CAM of this species as “straight”, contradicting with Zhu et al. (2008: 44, “weakly concave”). In the paratype female (RS8623), however, the CAM is very weakly undulate and asymmetrical.

The most prominent discrepancy lies in the qualitative description of tergal granulation, signifying yet another “taxonomic Rashomon effect”—a term coined herein, referring to the phenomenon where different subjective interpretations are derived from the morphology of the same specimen and hence its taxonomic position. For the same specimen, Qi et al. (2005: 30) stated “...*Carapace...with densely coarse granules...Tergites are coarsely granular...*”, while Zhu et al. (2008: 38, 44, 47) claimed, respectively, “...*carapace almost smooth on lateral and posterior margins...*”, “...*Carapace is almost smooth on lateral and posterior margins...Mesosomal tergites smooth...*”, and “...*Carapace covered with sparse granules of unequal size on inner portions of lateral carinae almost smooth on lateral and posterior margins...Mesosomal tergites not lustrous and almost smooth...*” The stark contradiction in their descriptions, particularly in adjective terms, can be considered diagnostic for different species in some cases. This highlights the subjectivity in qualitative descriptions and underscores the importance of including detailed photographs in species descriptions. After scrutinizing the photograph of the paratype female (RS8623) deposited in MNHN, I corroborate the presence of a large, triangular, relatively smooth area on the lateral sides near the posterior surface on carapace. Current examination reveals that reduction of granulation on the lateral surfaces of carapace is a common condition in Tibetan *Chaerilus* species. However, only *C. tessellatus* has been described as such in previous papers (Table 1), where this character was applied diagnostically. On the other hand, the same photograph shows dense granulation on nearly all tergite surfaces, as indicated by the reflections of those granules. Nonetheless, this could simply imply different conditions present in the holotype and paratype females. Subsequently, Di et al. (2009: 133) characterized this species with even more generalized phrasing in their dichotomous keys as follows (recycled in Di et al. (2013: 88), Di et al. (2014: 14), and Yin et al. (2015: 50)): “...*Carapace, tergites nearly smooth in adults...*” Similarly, both Qi et al. (2005: 30) and Zhu et al. (2008: 47) implied that sternite VII was “smooth” in this species (at least the holotype female, since they provided no comments on other materials): “...*Sternites are smooth; segment VII has two pairs of dentated carinae...*”, “...*Sternites smooth; sternite VII with two pairs of dentated carinae weakly developed...*” However, evident granules can be observed on the lateral sides and posterior region of sternite VII in the paratype female (RS8623). These confusions raise doubts about the accuracy of those authors’ qualitative description.

Despite the above complications, the presence of 11 subrows of denticles on its pedipalp movable finger presumably secures its validity (Table 1), a count shared only with *C. tricostatus* (10–12), from which *C. tessellatus* can be, theoretically, most reliably distinguished by the presence of D_3 (Yin et al., 2015: tab. 3; but see ‘7. Taxonomic conclusion’). Its distinction from *C. pictus*, a species recorded with a similar DSC (13–14), is discussed above.

DISTRIBUTION. Drepung Township (“Beibengxiang”) of Mêdog County, Dongjiu Village (“Dongjiucun”) and Sejila Mountain of Bayi District, and Mainling City, in Nyingchi City. However, most localities are dubious, as no descriptions were provided for specimens originating from those regions.

***Chaerilus tricostatus* Pocock, 1899**

(Figures 36–43, 212; Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:4D9B559C-2C6C-44C4-AF26-6227F8635F21>

Chaerilus tricostatus: Pocock, 1899: 266–267; Pocock, 1900: 54, 59–60; Henderson, 1913: 131–132; Kraepelin, 1913: 142, 146; Takashima, 1945: 100; Pérez, 1974: 31; Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 318, 320–326; Bastawade, 1985: 260; Kovařík, 1998: 129; Fet, 2000: 327; Kovařík, 2000: 40, 57, 61–62, 70, 72; Bastawade, 2006: 450, 454; Di et al., 2009: 131–137; Di, 2009: 98, 106; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97; Sun, 2010: 101, 108; Kovařík, 2012: 3; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 132–133, 142; Di et al., 2013: 52, 56, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 4–5, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42, 48, 50; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

TYPE MATERIAL (Pocock, 1899: 267). **India, Assam State**, Tinsukia District, Sadiya Town (?in Khasi Hills), 2♂, NHMUK.

OTHER MATERIAL. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Abor Hills, 28°07′58.2″N 95°07′26.7″E (approximated), 1♀, ZMNH (Henderson, 1913: 131); Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, 29°20′N 95°20′E, 3♀, 4 juv. ♀, MWUH (Di et al., 2009: 133).

MATERIAL EXAMINED (VT). **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, June 2024, 1♀, purchased dried specimen, collector unknown (Figs. 36–43, 212).

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 48–52.1 mm for ♂ and 55.3–59.2 mm for ♀. General color dark blackish brown. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular, denser in females; CAM straight; sternite III–VI smooth, VII smooth to granular and tetracarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10-8-8-8-7. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 5–6 in ♂ and 4–6 in ♀. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers 7–11/7–8. Pedipalp chela notably slender in ♂, ChL/W ca. 3.71 in ♂ and 2.21–2.43 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{4-5} , and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular, E and I obsolete; D_3 highly obsolete an unridged dark stripe, indicated distally and proximally; DSC of movable finger 10–12, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid.

REMARKS. The Chinese population of *C. tricostatus* was first reported by Henderson (1913: 131) as an adult female from “Upper Rotung” in “Abor country” (a record cited by Kovařík

Figures 36–37. Adult female *Chaerilus tricostatus* (= ? *C. tessellatus*), dried specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (36) and ventral (37) views, under white light; record not included in the map.

(2000: 62)), which refers to the Abor Hills north of Rottung Village in Siang District. Again, this location is situated in the disputed territory (“Arunachal Pradesh, India” or “South Xizang, China”). Di et al. (2009: 133) later provided the first illustrated description for a female *C. tricostatus* from Mêdog County, alongside information on 6 more females. In 2023, a friend of mine, Tongtong, collected another adult female from approximately the same location (29°19'20.6"N 95°19'48.4"E; iNaturalist, obs. ID = 196900793). Based on the map in Bastawade (2006: 450), the following additional localities are approximated (Fig. 1): Nyingchi City, Zayü County, 28°32'55.2"N 96°07'09.7"E; Shannan City, Tsona City, 27°18'16.4"N 92°32'36.4"E, 27°41'34.0"N 93°52'57.4"E. One record from iNaturalist (obs. ID = 117892140) was reported from Mêdog County (28°06'14.1"N 95°00'19.4"E), near the first reported Chinese female by Henderson (1913). The specimen was identified as a male *C. tricostatus* by me based on the rectangular and elongated manus as well as the absence of D_3 (Pocock, 1899: 266).

As indicated by the species name, the dichotomous identification of *C. tricostatus* has been primarily relied upon the presence of only three “costate” carinae (D_1 , D_4 , D_5) on the dorsal surface of its pedipalp chela (e. g., Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 318; Kovařík, 2000: 70; Kovařík, 2012: 3; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 132; Di et al., 2013: 88; Di et al., 2014: 14). This species was described based on two males from by Pocock (1899: 266–267), who measured a TL of 48 mm for the holotype male, which increased to 50 mm and 52.25 mm in its redescrptions by Pocock (1900: 50) and Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 322) respectively. The type materials were said to be from “Sadi, in the Khasia Hills”, likely referred to the Khasi Hills in the Meghalaya State of India. However, Pocock (1900: 50) subsequently changed the locality to “Sadiya, Assam”. In a more detailed redescription by Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 326), they included both localities, selecting the second as its type locality (“... Sadiya (Type locality) Assam; Khasia hills, Meghalaya...”). Henderson (1913: 131) was the first to describe the female

Figures 38–43. Adult female *Chaerilus tricostatus* (=? *C. tessellatus*), carapace (38), pectines (39), sternite VII (40), left chela (right chela fixed finger basally deformed) in dorsoexternal view (41), and left (42) and right (43) D_3 carinae under white light.

of this species based on 4 specimens from “Abor country”. He noticed a sexual dimorphism in ChL/W and carapacial granulation density, which was followed by Kovařík (2000: 62), and the dense granules in females were also concurred by Di et al. (2009: 133). The selected female for description measured 53 mm in TL (Henderson, 1913: 132). The largest female was recorded with a TL of 59.2 mm in Di et al. (*op. cit.*: tab. 1), who also documented the lowest known female ChL/W (13.7/6.2). All sternites were originally described as smooth except for the presence of 4 carinae on VII in Pocock (1899: 266), followed by Henderson (1913: 131), Kovařík (2000: 62), and Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro (2013: 142). In the redescription of this species, Di et al. (2009: 136) described the sternite VII as “...with some small granules on

posterior portion...” (note that this does not refer to the four granular carinae), suggesting an equivalent state of “weakly granular” or “subgranular”. However, Yin et al. (2015: tab. 3) simply described it as “granular” (logically, a larger set), while they also employed the more specific descriptor, “weakly granular”, for other congeners (*C. conchiformis* and *C. mainlingensis*).

Kovařík (2000: 62) provided a PTC range of 5–6 without specifying the sex, likely combined the male count (5–6) in Pocock (1899: 267; 1900: 60; however, Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 324) described the male holotype with 5/5 pectinal teeth) and the female count (5) in Henderson (1913: 132), whereas Di et al. (2009: tab. 1) further recorded one female pectine with a count of 4. Tikader & Bastawade (1983:

Figures 44–45. Adult female *Chaerilus cf. tryznai*, fresh specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (44) and ventral (45) views, under white light; record included in the map.

324) were the first to enumerate the cheliceral VAD in this species, providing a count of 8/7 for movable/fixed fingers of the holotype male. Later, Bastawade (2006: 454) reported a range of 8–9 and 7–8 VAD for the cheliceral movable and fixed fingers respectively. Di et al. (2009: 137) recorded a total range of 7–11 VAD on the movable finger for the 7 females they examined.

Pocock (1899: 267) initially mentioned 11 subrows of denticles on the movable finger of this species based on the holotype male, but then erroneously recorded it with 4

subrows in his redescription (Pocock, 1990: 60). Henderson (1913: 132) reported 10 subrows based on 4 new female specimens from “Abor country”. Kraepelin (1913: 142) subsequently keyed this species with as DSC of 10–11 (“...*Schrägzeilen des beweglichen Fingers 10–11...*”), but later in the same work (*op. cit.*: 146) diagnosed it as “... *die Zahl der Schrägzeilen des beweglichen Fingers beträgt 11–12...*” (“the number of oblique rows of the movable finger is 11–12”). Tikader & Bastawade (1983: 324) did not directly provide the count, but illustrated a finger of the

Figures 46–51. Adult female *Chaerilus* cf. *tryznai*, carapace (46), pectines (47), sternite VII (48), and left chela (right chela movable finger broken) in dorsoexternal view (49) under white light, and left (50) and right (51) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

male holotype showing 11 subrows (*op. cit.*: 916), if based on the division by larger granules. Kovařík (2000: 62) accepted the count of 11–12, which was later consistently adopted in Di et al. (2009: 133), Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro (2013: 142), Di et al. (2013: 88), Di et al. (2014: 14), and Yin et al. (2015: tab. 3). The count of 10–11 was first followed by Bastawade (2006: 454) in his interspecific comparison of *C. dibangvalleycus*. In his dissertation, Di (2009: 98) keyed this species with a DSC of 10–12, but then (*op. cit.*: 106) diagnosed it as 11–12 (as per Di et al. (2009: 133)), citing Bastawade’s description in the section of *C.*

dibangvalleycus on page 101. The exactly same scenario is found in Sun’s (2010: 101, 103, 108) dissertation. In fact, the two dissertations are generally identical (and both listed *C. mainlingensis* as their new species).

Chaerilus tricostatus is one of the most unique Chinese *Chaerilus* species (alongside *C. conchiformis* and *C. pictus*) for its relatively large size, essentially dark blackish color, and absence of *D*₃. The strongly sexually dimorphic pedipalp is also distinctive, with males showing long, cuboid chela. According to the diagnostic table summarized herein (Table 1), the presence of 10–12 subrows of denticles on pedipalp movable finger

would only associate it with *C. pictus* and *C. tessellatus*, whose distinctions have been discussed above. The lack of D_3 places it closer to *C. dibangvalleyicus* and *C. mainlingensis*, from which it can be separated by its higher DSC (*vs.* 7–8 in those two species). It is worth clarifying that D_3 is still observable in the moistened specimen with the aid of light from proper angles (*pers. obs.*; cf. Di et al., 2009: fig. 1). What gives rise to its apparent absence is but a significant reduction in the relative size of its constitutive granules (Figs. 42–43). However, the slightly concave intercarinal surfaces between D_1 and D_3 , as well as D_3 and D_4 , contribute to identifying the residual presence of D_3 .

DISTRIBUTION. Nyingchi City (Mêdog and Zayü counties) and Shannan City (Tsona City).

***Chaerilus tryznai* Kovařík, 2000**

(Figures 44–51; Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:00E2C268-AC3C-4B38-8801-9992CE905FDF>

Chaerilus tryznai: Kovařík, 2000: 38, 41–42, 58, 65–66, 69, 72; Kovařík, 2001: 82; Soleglad & Fet, 2003: 7, 33; Yang, 2008: 8, 50, 76; Di et al., 2009: 131–133; Di, 2009: 98, 106–108, 196–198; Di & Zhu, 2009: 97–98, 101; Sun, 2010: 101, 108–109; Kovařík, 2012: 2, 13; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 132, 142; Di et al., 2013: 52, 57–58, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42, 46, 48, 49; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

Chaerilus triznai [ISS]: Zhu et al., 2008: 37–40, 44, 47–51.

TYPE MATERIAL (Kovařík, 2000: 65). **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County, 29°52'N 95°45'E, 1♂12♀, 1 juv., FKCP.

OTHER MATERIAL. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County (incorrectly given as “Nêdong District, Shannan City” in Di (2009: 106) and Sun (2010: 108)), Hanmi Village, 29°02'N 95°03'E (extends to Arunachal Pradesh), 2♀, MHBU (Zhu et al., 2008: 47); Nyingchi City, Bomê County, 4♀ (Di, 2009: 106). Two ♀ reported in Yin et al. (2015: 46).

MATERIAL EXAMINED (VT) [putative; misidentified as *C. wrzecionkoi* in Tang (2024b)]. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County, Tramog Town, 29°51'32.5"N 95°46'03.4"E, 2859 m a. s. l., 27th July 2023, 1♀, leg. Tongtong (Figs. 44–51).

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 32.3 mm for ♂ and 30.74–44 mm for ♀. General color blackish brown to black. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular; CAM straight; sternite III–VI smooth, VII granular and acarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10–8–8–8–7. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 4 in ♂ and 3–4 in ♀. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers 6/4. Pedipalp chela slightly slender in ♂, ChL/W ca. 3.12 in ♂ and 2.6–2.91 in ♀; manus

with D_1 , D_{3-5} , and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular, *E* and *I* obsolete; DSC of movable finger 8, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid, but species characterization requires refinement.

REMARKS. This species was the first *Chaerilus* described from Tibet, on the basis of 1 adult male, 12 adult females, and 1 juvenile. It was contrasted only with *C. assamensis* given the unique count of finger denticle subrows (8) at the time. The single differential character utilized was the CAM shape (straight in *C. tryznai*, arched in *C. assamensis*). After reviewing the original description of *C. dibangvalleyicus* (presumed synonym of *C. assamensis* as per Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013), the two species further differ in the VADC of cheliceral fixed finger, D_3 development, and sternite VII (Table 1). However, those differences hold true only if *C. dibangvalleyicus* is indeed synonymous with *C. assamensis*. Nevertheless, the opposite outcome does not logically negate the difference (based solely on the paper descriptions) between *C. dibangvalleyicus* and *C. tryznai*. Yin et al. (2015: 46) studied two new female specimens (deposited in USTC, without collection details), increasing the upper TL bound to 44 mm while decreasing the lower ChL/W bound to 2.6. Additional comments for the interspecific difference are given under *C. pseudoconchiformis* and *C. wrzecionkoi*.

Zhu et al. (2008: 47–51) redescribed this species based on the same female from Hanmi Village, Mêdog (Fig. 1), later reported in Di's dissertation (2009: 106) who mistakenly stated that it was from Nêdong District (in Shannan City) despite providing the same coordinates; illustrations and measurements of the female are identical in Zhu et al. (2008: figs. 45–59, tab. 1) and Di (2009: figs. 48–50, tab. 5), and the former paper will be referenced to henceforth. Zhu et al. (*op. cit.*) also listed another female collected one day before from the same locality as the female examined, and the two records were followed by Di et al. (2013: 57). Di (2009: 106) further mentioned 4 females from Bomê without coordinates. All six females were fully documented in Sun's dissertation (2010: 108), but Di et al. (2013: 57) excluded the four females from Bomê.

Not much useful information can be retrieved from the redescription as the key characters were generally identical with the original description. However, Zhu et al. (2008: 50) provided a ChL/W of 2.2 for the female they examined, but measurements from their table 1 would give a value of 2.083 (6.75/3.24). A crude measurement based on their figure 47 yields, on the other hand, a ChL/W of 2.54 (to derive width in pixels, a constraint rectangle was applied to the chela figure *in situ*, i.e., no rotation, and the length was obtained from the pixel distance between fingertip and the most proximal, angular granule on the external margin). This is closer to the original metrics (2.9), and even more so to the lower bound value (2.6) given in Yin et al. (2015: tab. 3).

DISTRIBUTION. Hanmi Village of Mêdog County, and Bomê County, in Nyingchi City.

Figures 52–53. Adult female *Chaerilus* sp. (cf. *herta* sp. n.) from Mêdog (purchased), dried specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (52) and ventral (53) views, under white light; record not included in the map.

***Chaerilus wrzecionkoi* Kovařík, 2012**

(Figures 5–10, 68–75; Tables 1–2)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:C097EF9A-B8A7-4BF1-A6BC-3E5416EF9B29>

Chaerilus wrzecionkoi: Kovařík, 2012: 1–2, 11–13; Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro, 2013: 132, 143; Di et al., 2013: 53, 57–58, 88, 95; Di et al., 2014: 5, 9, 14; Yin et al., 2015: 42–44, 46, 48, 50; Di et al., 2015: 111; Tang, 2022a: 55; Tang, 2022b: 3, 14; Tang, 2025: 16.

TYPE MATERIAL (Kovařík, 2012: 11). **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County, Tongmai Town, 30 km west of “Donjung”, 30°06'06.4"N 95°04'47.5"E (approximated), 2♂2♀, FKCP.

MATERIAL EXAMINED (VT) [putative; misidentified as *C. tryznai* in Tang (2024b)]. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County, Tramog Town, Nyingchi City, Bomê County, 29°58'23.1"N 95°39'31.9"E, 3849 m. a. s. l., 22nd July 2019, 1♀, leg. Tongtong (Figs. 5–10, 68–75).

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 33–37 mm for ♂ and 39–41 mm for ♀. General color dark brown to blackish. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular; CAM straight; sternite III–VI smooth, VII granular and acarinate. Metasoma I–V with carinae 10-8-8-8-7. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 4–5 in ♂ and 3–4 in ♀. Pedipalp chela slightly slender in ♂, ChL/W ca. 2.57 in ♂ and 2.37 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{3-5} , and $V_{1,3}$ present and granular, *E* and *I* obsolete; DSC of movable finger 8, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Valid, but species characterization requires refinement.

REMARKS. This species was rather tersely by two pairs of adults. Kovařík (2012: 11) diagnosed this species with a PTC of 3–5, but then detailed in his description with a note “...(females 3x4, 1x4; males 1x4, 3x5)...”. This could be a typographical error, where the first digits represent the number of pectines, aligning with the total pectine count for the four specimens. Therefore, the second digits likely represent the

Figures 54–59. Adult female *Chaerilus* sp. (cf. *herta* sp. n.) from Médog (purchased), carapace (54), pectines (55), sternite VII (56), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (57) under white light, and left (58) and right (59) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

PTC, possibly indicating that one or three female pectines had 4 teeth, while the others had 3 teeth (according to the range in diagnosis). Yin et al. (2015: tab. 3) considered the DSC of the male holotype to be 9, based on Kovařík (2012: fig. 64). The finger illustrated at a low resolution was covered with dirt, preventing a confident enumeration. I reckon at least 8 rows of denticles based on the inner denticles, concurring with Kovařík (*op. cit.*: 11).

Kovařík (*op. cit.*: 13) briefly compared *C. wrzecionkoi* with *C. mainlingensis* and *C. tryznai*, which were the only resemblant Tibetan congeners at the time (now also *C. pseudoconchiformis*). A single character was leveraged, the carinae on sternite VII, which are present in *C. mainlingensis* but absent in *C. wrzecionkoi*. However, a more reliable character appears to be D_3 , which is absent in *C. mainlingensis* but present in *C. wrzecionkoi*. The comparison between *C.*

wrzecionkoi and *C. tryznai* was referenced to the dichotomous keys (No. 19, *op. cit.*: 2), in which males of *C. tryznai* possess proportionally narrower chela than *C. wrzecionkoi* (> 3 vs. < 2.6). Based on Kovařík (2000: tab. 1), females of *C. tryznai* also have narrower chela (2.91 vs. 2.37). Concerns may arise for the potential overlap when taking intraspecific variation and measurement inconsistency into account since the difference was based solely on one ratiometric. Although he examined multiple specimens of both species, no intraspecific variation was documented, which appears to be the author's regular practice. While experienced authors may defend such a *modus operandi*, particularly when they can demonstrate having the species for comparison, readers cannot confidently accept their conclusions with a rigorous mindset. This approach leaves them hindered by doubtful diagnostic characters (e. g., ChL/W, as indicated in Figs. 7–10). The distinction between these two species are however conspicuous if one were to infer from the presumed adult female specimens examined herein (cf. Figs. 44–51, 68–75).

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from the type locality; Tongmai Town of Bomê County, in Nyingchi City.

Morphological investigations into *Chaerilus* specimens collected from Drepung

Nine adult females and 40 adult males (Figs. 108–109) of an unidentified *Chaerilus* species (all had been preserved in 75% ethanol) were collected from Drepung Township, Mêdog County, the type locality of *C. tessellatus*. Congeneric species recorded in proximity also include *C. tricostatus* and *C. tryznai* (Fig. 1). A cursory examination swiftly ruled out *C. tricostatus* as a potential match given the well-developed D_3 in all specimens. According to the summarized diagnostics (Table 1), *C. tessellatus* and *C. tryznai* should ideally be differentiated by DSC, sternite VII, and metasoma II carinae, since males of *C. tessellatus* remain unknown. For the purpose of providing a general review of diagnostic traits previously used to differentiate Chinese *Chaerilus* species, the following characters were examined for the 40 Drepung males: PTC, DSC, ChL/W, CAM, sternite VII, and metasoma II–III carinae. The ventral accessory denticles (VAD) on the cheliceral fingers were not assessed, as the ridged segmental membrane in some specimens hindered manipulation of these structures, which appear to be either variable or non-diagnostic (interspecifically overlapped or with unknown intraspecific variation). Nevertheless, several other examined materials of *Chaerilus* are provided with photographs of VAD on their cheliceral movable fingers (Figs. 92–107). It seems that the varying development degree of those denticles can obstruct unambiguous enumeration.

The current analyses were founded upon two assumptions to eschew biases stemming from interspecific and ontogenetic variations: all males were (1) conspecific and (2) adult. Conspecificity was recognized upon observing no potentially meaningful morphological discrepancies apart from size and ChL/W (which will be further analyzed). Maturity was verified

based on the coloration (uniformly dark brownish black, except for several evidently discolored specimens), carinae and granule development, and most importantly, the presence of hemispermatophores confirmed from several smallest males, ensuring the absence of any large juveniles that overlap with small adults in size. Given my utter lack of experience with this genus and the specimens' long-term storage in ethanol that prevented perfect anatomy, identification on the hemispermatophores of small males was inferred from their similarity with the unambiguous hemispermatophores retrieved from the largest male (Figs. 110–116).

1. Methodologies

(1) Carapace length as the primary proxy for total length and the secondary proxy for body size

Conceptually, “size” is hereby defined as the volume an object occupies within physical space, representing a composite metric that incorporates length, width, and height. For scorpions, size theoretically refers to the total volume of all their segments, including minuscule structures such as setae. In contrast, “body size (BS)” exclusively pertains to the combined volume of the prosoma, mesosoma, metasoma, and telson, collectively denoted as the “body”. However, the visual impression of a scorpion's size can be influenced by the relative size of its pedipalps or leg span. For instance, many hormurid species possess massive pedipalps in relation to their body size. Thus, BS is not necessarily an exhaustive representation of the scorpion's overall size. “Total length (TL)”, or “total body length” as in Sissom et al. (1990: 217), is the linear measurement along the longitudinal axis of the body (i.e., somatic axis). For practical purposes, TL is frequently used as the primary proxy for BS, as it represents the largest dimension (or “principal component”) contributing to the total volume of the scorpion body. The inclusion of chelicerae in body length measurements is predominantly observed in amateur scorpion-rearing circles and occasionally in academic studies (e. g., recently in Sanchez-Piñero et al. (2024: 190)). While excluding the telson is well justifiable, as this division is not regarded as a true body segment in scorpions (Hjelle, 1990: 8; Lourenço, 2018: 4), chelicerae, being highly movable appendages, cannot reliably guarantee a standard or consistent measurement of body length. Moreover, the degree of cheliceral protrusion varies depending on the state of the specimen, both *in vivo* and *in vitro*.

The derivation of scorpion TL varies among authors and/or depends on the specific research objectives. A crude, expedient method is to simply measure the linear distance between carapace anterior margin (CAM) and telson tip. The evident issue with this method is that the TL of specimens with an inflated or contracted mesosoma will be either overestimated or underestimated. A more meticulous way entails taking 14 independent segment measurements from carapace to telson, treating each cuticular component separately for mesosoma and metasoma. However, this method can inadvertently amplify the total error due to ambiguities in selecting the initial

Figures 60–61. Adult female *Chaerilus* sp. (cf. *herta* sp. n.) from Mêdog (purchased), dried specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (60) and ventral (61) views, under white light; record not included in the map.

and terminal points for measurement on each sclerite, as well as the unavoidable imprecision inherent in manual operations. This error becomes evident during repeated measurements of the same specimen by the same practitioner. Suppose each measurement has an associated uncertainty (or variation, error) arising from measurement imprecision, denoted as δ , the total uncertainty in the sum (Δ) is given by:

$$\Delta = \sqrt{\sum_i^n \delta_i^2}$$

where n is the number of measurements, and δ , is the uncertainty in the i -th measurement. Assuming all measurements share the same δ , the formula simplifies to $\Delta = (\sqrt{14}) \cdot \delta \approx 3.74 \cdot \delta$. To ensure there is no Δ between two independent measurements on the same specimen, one would need either to eliminate the individual δ entirely, or ensure that all δ cancel each other out. To control Δ under a given threshold k (in mm), each δ must be smaller than $k/3.74$ mm (e. g., for $k = 1$, δ must be less than approximately $267 \mu\text{m}$). Achieving this level of precision is highly challenging, if not practically impossible. Owing to the absence of a standardized protocol for accurate linear measurement, and the fact that some specimens exhibited contraction in the mesosoma, the carapace length (CaL) was used in this study as the proxy for TL to avoid cumulative uncertainties propagated through sequential measurements of individual body segments (measurement conducted manually with the aid of a digital caliper by carefully confining the anterior and posterior carapacial margins). Ergo, CaL represents the secondary proxy for BS.

In the context of studying intersexual differences, Fox et al. (2015: 14) suggested that CaL itself may exhibit sexual dimorphism and thus be less reliable, recommending the use of metasoma I width (met1W) as the TL indicator. It is worth noting that the accuracy of width measurements may also vary depending on the species under study, particularly when the segment lacks nearly parallel bilateral surfaces. Given that the current objective focuses on a single sex and crude visual inspection revealed no significant somatic ratiometric discrepancies among individuals, CaL was chosen as the secondary—with TL being the primary—BS reference, as it is less flexible than carapace width, which is more prone to transverse deformation in preserved specimens, particularly among small species having less rigid cuticle (cf. Tang et al., 2023: fig. 91).

However, for multispecies comparisons, CaL can be an unreliable proxy for either TL or BS due to the distinct morphologies (essentially the somatic ratiometrics) exhibited by different species, particularly when compared between sexes if significant sexual dimorphism is present. TL itself, being a one-dimensional linear variable, also does not effectively translate into size (or more precisely, volume), which is a three-dimensional variable. Predictably, few would contend that a 31 cm long cotton thread with a diameter of 2 mm is comparable in size to a 12-inch pizza or a cylindrical water bucket with a volume of $16^2 \times 31\pi \text{ cm}^3$. Overly simplified reduction leads to the significant loss of numerous crucial morphological (profile) information.

Figures 62–67. Adult female *Chaerilus* sp. (cf. *herta* sp. n.) from Mèdog (purchased), carapace (62), pectines (63), sternite VII (64), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (65) under white light, and left (66) and right (67) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

A species may have a large TL, but this could essentially be the result of a disproportionately elongated metasoma, while the combined volume of its prosoma and mesosoma may be smaller than that of another species sharing the same TL, as the two species may differ in the relative width of mesosoma. For example, both adult female *Androctonus gonneti* Vachon, 1948 and adult male *Lychas scutillus* can reach ca. 85 mm in TL, yet the latter appears considerably smaller as a result of its overall slenderness; similarly, both adult male *Androctonus turkiyensis* Yağmur, 2021

and *L. scutillus* may have a CaL of ca. 6.6 mm, but the former reaches only 56 mm in TL (Tang, pers. obs.; see the figure gallery of this paper on ResearchGate). Their size discrepancy becomes even more pronounced *in vivo* when metasoma is curled over mesosoma. This is one of the many fundamental errors made by Forde et al. (2022) (e. g., failing to account for the different sources of LD₅₀ values and intraspecific variations in morphometrics, and neglecting to include many other non-medically significant species with smaller sizes and chelae, which would virtually nullify their

Figures 68–69. Adult female *Chaerilus cf. wrzecionkoi*, 75% ethanol preserved specimen (same as in Figs. 5–10), habitus in dorsal (68) and ventral (69) views, under white light; record included in the map.

result; it is also questionable regarding how they quantified the size of the chela), who argued that there is a negative correlation between scorpion “body size” and venom potency. In a multispecies context, TL, as a biased BS proxy, could potentially be corrected by a weighted average width (W_{avg}). One may partition the scorpion body into two halves, with the upper half comprising prosoma and mesosoma, and the lower half being metasoma. Telson is excluded for convenience in this method, and the redefined TL is denoted as TL'. The weighted average width is hence given by:

$$W_{avg} = \frac{L_1 \hat{W}_1 + L_2 \hat{W}_2}{TL'}$$

$$\hat{W}_1 = \frac{W_{ca} + W_{cp} + W_{tm}}{3}$$

$$\hat{W}_2 = \frac{W_{min} + W_{max}}{2}$$

where L_1 is the upper length, L_2 is the lower length, \hat{W}_1 is the estimated mean upper width, \hat{W}_2 is the estimated mean lower width, W_{ca} is the anterior width of carapace, W_{cp} is the posterior width of carapace, W_{tm} is the maximum width of tergite, W_{min} is the minimum width of metasoma, and W_{max} is the maximum width of metasoma. TL' can be normalized based on the width contribution. One way to correct the TL' for comparison is to use the ratio of weighted average widths:

$$M = TL' \times \frac{W_{avg}}{W_{avg,tot}}$$

$$W_{avg,tot} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_{avg,i}}{n}$$

where M is the metric (corrected TL') later used for multispecies comparison, and $W_{avg,tot}$ is the mean weighted averaged width of all species under comparison, which is calculated by dividing the sum of all W_{avg} for each (i -th) species by the number of species (n). This correction method implies that it is tailored for specific comparative contexts.

Since proxies are utilized for their practical convenience at the expense of compromising precision or accuracy, authors may opt to derive TL' by directly measuring the linear distance from CAM to the lateral anal lobe of metasoma V. L_2 , attained from the more unstable metasomal segments, can also be obtained by simply subtracting L_1 from TL'. Additionally, to derive the mean upper width, individual measurements for the anterior and posterior widths of the carapace and each tergite may not be necessary. I propose to use only the anterior and posterior widths of the carapace and the maximum tergite width (e. g., width of tergites IV, V, or VI) for estimation. Similarly, for the mean lower width, it may be sufficient to measure the two metasoma with the minimum and maximum widths, after leveling the segment and applying a constraint rectangle to determine each value. Apparently, this simplified calculation would likely indicate its unsuitability in assessing species with prominently disproportionate metasomal segments (e. g., *Apistobuthus* Finnegan, 1932, some *Microbuthus* Kraepelin, 1898, and adult male *Jaguajir pinto* (Mello-Leitão, 1932)).

Be that as it may, the final decision hinges on the practitioner's judgement regarding the tradeoff between time investment and precision.

Nevertheless, comparisons (in mm) between true mean metasoma widths (W_2 , based on all segments) and min-max-averaged metasoma widths (\hat{W}_2) suggested that even for species like *Microbuthus* spp. and adult male *J. pinto*, the simplified calculation proposed herein would not lead to significant deviation from the true mean metasoma width: (1) *M. gardneri* Lowe, 2010: W_2 2.106 (vs. \hat{W}_2 2.115) in holotype male and 2.342 (vs. 2.335) in paratype female (Lowe, 2010: 8–9); (2) *M. kristensenorum* Lowe, 2010: W_2 2.146 (vs. \hat{W}_2 2.175) in holotype female and 1.316 (vs. 1.325) in Wadi Shuwaymiyah female (Lowe, 2010: 15); (3) *J. pinto*: W_2 6.32–7.54 (vs. \hat{W}_2 6.25–7.4) in two males and 5.94–6.76 (vs. 5.9–6.7) in two females (Teruel & Tietz, 2008: tab. 1). However, such deviation was notably exaggerated in *A. susanae* Lourenço, 1998, resulting in overestimations of the true mean metasoma width: W_2 6.622 (vs. \hat{W}_2 7.465) in Bostan male and 6.81 (vs. 7.435) in Omidiyeh female (Navidpour & Lowe, 2009: tab. 2). The degree of amplification ($A = \hat{W}_2/W_2$) is 0.98–1.01 for *Microbuthus* and *J. pinto*, but approximately 1.1 (1.09–1.13) for *Apistobuthus*. The within-group difference is minimal at around 0.03 for {*M. gardneri*, *M. kristensenorum*, *J. pinto*}, whereas this difference increases ca. 3- to 4-fold to 0.09–0.12 when this group is compared against *A. susanae*. The A variation range for {*M. gardneri*, *M. kristensenorum*, *J. pinto*} falls within the general variability (mean \pm SD = 1.005 \pm 0.019, $n = 172$) derived from several buthid species—as other families tend to exhibit even less variability in their metasomal segment widths (most possessing relatively slenderer metasoma)—that exhibit no conspicuously disproportionate metasomal segments: *Aegaeobuthus galliano* (Ythier, 2018), *Ananteris ochoai* Botero-Trujillo & Flórez, 2011, *Anomalobuthus rickmersi* Kraepelin, 1900, *Androctonus kunti* Yağmur, 2023, *Androctonus sumericus* Al-Khazali & Yağmur, 2023, *Barbaracurus exquisitus* (Lowe, 2000), *Buthacus amitaii* Cain et al., 2021, *Butheoloides nuer* Kovařík, 2015, *Butheolus harrisoni* Lowe, 2018, *Buthus castellano* Teruel & Turiel, 2022, *Centruroides caribbeanus* Teruel & Myers, 2017, *Chaneke hofereki* Kovařík et al., 2016, *Charmus saradieli* Kovařík et al., 2016, *Compsobuthus satpuraensis* Waghe et al., 2022, *Gint banfasae* Kovařík & Lowe, 2019, *Grosphus angulatus* Lowe & Kovařík, 2022, *Heteroctenus tureli* Teruel & Yong, 2023, *Hottentotta gibaensis* Kovařík, 2015, *Ischnotelson peruassu* Esposito et al., 2017, *Isometrus kovariki* Sulakhe et al., 2020, *Janalychas granulatus* Mirza, 2020, *Lanzatus huluul* Kovařík & Lowe, 2021, *Leiurus macroctenus* Lowe et al., 2014, *Lychas mucronatus* (Fabricius, 1798), *Mesobuthus bogdoensis* (Birula, 1896), *Microchasmus antongil* Lourenço et al., 2019, *Microtityus adriki* Moreno-González et al., 2024, *Neobuthus amoudensis* Kovařík et al., 2018, *Odontobuthus persicus* Barahoei & Shahi, 2024, *Olivierus gorelovi* (Fet et al., 2018), *Orthochiroides somalilandus* Kovařík & Lowe, 2022, *Orthochirus fomichevi* Kovařík et al., 2019, *Parabuthus robustus* Kovařík et al., 2019, *Physoctonus debilis* (C. L.Koch, 1840), *Pseudouroplectes*

Figures 70–75. Adult female *Chaerilus* cf. *wrzecionkoi*, carapace (70), pectines (71), sternite VII (72), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (73) under white light, and left (74) and right (75) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

jacki Lourenço, 2021, *Razianus farzanpayi* Tahir et al., 2014, *Reddyanus jayarathnei* Kovařík et al., 2016, *Rhopalurus ochoai* Esposito et al., 2017 (one female paratype metasoma IV width corrected to 4.9), *Somalibuthus sabae* Kovařík & Njoroge, 2021, *Somalicharmus whitmanae* Kovařík, 1998, *Teruelius haeckeli* Lowe & Kovařík, 2022, *Thaicharmus lowei* Kovařík et al., 2007, *Tityobuthus mariejeanneae* Lourenço et al., 2018, *Tityopsis rolandoi* Kovarik et al., 2024, *Tityus (Tityus) achilles* Laborieux, 2024, *Tityus (Atreus) moralensis* Moreno-González et al., 2022, *Tityus (Caribetityus) schrammi* Teruel & Santos, 2018, *Tityus (Archaeotityus) wachteli* Kovařík

et al., 2015, *Troglophopalurus translucidus* Lourenço et al., 2004, *Trypanothacus barnesi* Lowe et al., 2019, *Uroplectes malawicus* Prendini, 2015, *Xenobuthus xanthus* Lowe, 2018, and *Zabius gaucho* Acosta et al., 2008 (raw width data retrieved from their respective original or redescription papers, assuming no severe errors). It turned out that the investigated buthids generally tend to increase their metasoma width progressively in both directions, or show slight dilation at segment III or VI, facilitating quick visual determination of the two segments selected for calculating the estimated mean metasoma width in practice. It can also be noticed that some data provided by

Figures 76–77. Adult male *Chaerilus variegatus*, fresh specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (76) and ventral (77) views, under white light.

the authors were affected by manual imprecision based on their discordance with the illustrations, or the relatively high intraspecific fluctuations (maximum A difference ~ 0.08 seen in *M. adriki*, followed by 0.06 in *T. translucidus*); achieving precision is important as a few authors often leverage ratiometric differences in metasoma for species delimitation. The overall fitness (Pearson's $r = 0.9996$, RMSE = 0.048, MAE = 0.036; WSR $p = 0.1006$, effect size = 0.1245; non-normal dataset ($p < 0.0001$), $n = 180$, including *Microbutus* and *Jaguajir*) supports \hat{W}_2 as a relatively suitable estimator for true mean metasoma width.

In extreme cases such as *Apistobuthus* spp., a possible approach is to treat the enlarged segment (metasoma II) as a separate entity for calculation. This would entail dividing the

lower half into segments II and {I, III, IV, V}, measuring the length of segment II (as only this measurement is required), and calculating their respective mean widths. Based on the empirical data (the same *A. susanae* data as before), this approach, albeit reducing overestimation to some extent, still led to deviations from the true mean metasoma width (true values: $L_2\hat{W}_2$ 314.2 in male, 322 in female; basic estimation: $L_2\hat{W}_2$ 354.2 in male, 351.5 in female; revised estimation: $L_2\hat{W}_2$ 328.9 in male, 332.3 in female). An alternative correction involves applying an empirical scaling factor, k , to $L_2\hat{W}_2$ in the basic formula. This factor can be determined by the inverse of A , which equals 0.887 in the male and 0.916 in the female. Averaging these values gives $k = 0.9$. Multiplying $L_2\hat{W}_2$ by k results in 318.8 for male and 316.4 for female.

Figures 78–83. Adult male *Chaerilus variegatus*, carapace (78), pectines (79), sternite VII (80), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (81) under white light, and left (82) and right (83) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

The above methodology does not factor in the variability in somatic depth across different species for two primary reasons: (1) the depth of the prosoma or mesosoma is highly flexible and influenced by the individual scorpion's condition (e. g., states of gestation, starvation, and hydration); and (2) depth generally contributes less to the total volume of the scorpion, with the exception of certain dorsoventrally compressed and/or lithophilic crevice dwellers (e. g., genera *Chiromachetes* Pocock, 1899, *Hadogenes* Kraepelin, 1894, *Hormurus* Thorell, 1876, *Hormiops* Fage, 1933, *Liocheles* Sundevall, 1833, *Palaeocheloctonus* Lourenço, 1996, etc.). In the absence of other information, CaL or TL alone cannot be regarded reliable for representing the actual BS of a species

of a random sex in a comparative context. Further studies are needed to assess how sensitive multispecies comparison results are to these biases and whether similar mathematical corrections can mitigate them. A more laborious approach would involve measuring all segments of the scorpion, followed by the use of dimension reduction algorithms (e. g., Principal Component Analysis) to obtain the first principal component, which captures the majority of the information contributing to BS. Alternatively, since metasoma tends to be more morphologically erratic within the order, the estimation of BS (under another definition) could be confined solely to the more conservative prosoma and mesosoma. In any case, a refined measurement protocol for each body segment is

Figures 84–85. Adult female *Chaerilus variegatus*, fresh specimen (now preserved in 75% ethanol), habitus in dorsal (84) and ventral (85) views, under white light.

requisite before obtaining the raw values that are used to further calculate the TL or mean widths.

When the present paper was in press, a meticulous study on various size predictive proxies for scorpions while taking phylogenetic relationships into account was published. Foerster (2025: 9) demonstrated that the length of metasoma V (met5L) was the best proxy for TL in buthids, followed closely by CaL (RMSE difference = 0.05; *op. cit.*: tab. 2). The general accuracy of using met5L as a TL predictor was confirmed for both sexes, also with no significant interaction with sex observed among other studied predictors (*op. cit.*: fig. 3). The primary potential concern is the methodological discrepancy in measurements (as also acknowledged by the author; *op. cit.*: 4), since most morphometric data were sourced

from past taxonomic studies by different authors. According to his diagram (*op. cit.*: fig. 1), met5L was measured dorsally based on the visible anterior and posterior boundaries of the segment. While the posterior boundary may be consistently represented by the lateral lobe of the anal arch among authors (unless some pivoted to leverage the ventral boundary of the anal arch), the anterior boundary can vary depending on the specimen's orientation, leading to different measurements. As discussed earlier, each metasomal segment has a base section that can be partially concealed within its anterior segment. The least biased point is likely the most proximal end (or anywhere near it that is located more proximally) of the median lateral carina for metasoma V (and the dorsolateral carina for I–IV). Although these technical considerations may

Figures 86–91. Adult female *Chaerilus variegatus*, carapace (86), pectines (87), sternite VII (88), and right chela in dorsoexternal view (89) under white light, and left (90) and right (91) pedipalp movable fingers under UV light.

seem overly fastidious, the potential measurement bias they introduce might have contributed to the slight difference in TL prediction accuracy between met5L and CaL. In practice, CaL is easier to measure given the clearer boundaries compared to the more irregular metasomal segments.

(2) Protocol for the enumeration of pedipalp movable finger denticle subrows

The “rows of granules” on the dorsal dentate edge of pedipalp movable finger are frequently employed as a diagnostic character across various scorpion lineages. These meristics

generally fall into two categories: the number of denticles and the number of denticle subrows. As clarified already, “granules” have been replaced by “denticles”, and “rows” by “subrows” in this study, following Tang et al. (2024a: 11–12). This choice of terminology is grounded on two reasons: (1) “denticle” more suitably describes the sharp, apically metallic protrusion which functions to fixate on a target; (2) in certain species, the finger denticle row is not subdivided into multiple sections, but it is nonetheless homologous with the rows in all other species; hence, the entire series is referred to as the “row”, and in the presence of subdivision, each section is termed a “subrow”. The denticle subrows can be clearly defined in some species, or highly intricate in others. The various configurations can be diagnostic at species or genus levels.

While the denticle subrow count (DSC) has been regularly applied as a diagnostic in *Chaerilus*, the exact protocol for such enumeration was never established, thus leading to the differing interpretations of the count in certain species by some authors (e. g., Yin et al., 2015). In light of the preliminary nature of this study and the absence of comparative research into the homology of finger denticles in scorpions—Soleglad & Sissom (2001) focused only on several families within Iurida (Caraboctonidae, Chactidae, Euscorpidae, Iuridae, Scorpidae, Superstitioniidae, Troglotayosicidae, Typhlochactidae, and Vaejovidae)—the denticles in *Chaerilus* will not be categorized into any subtypes (e. g., median, outer, inner, accessory) at present. After examining all available species under UV light, the general denticle configuration in *Chaerilus* can be described as follows:

- (1) the finger denticle row is divided into multiple (usually ≥ 7) highly imbricated subrows, forming a spiral pattern where each anterior subrow flanks external to its adjacent posterior subrow;
- (2) median to large denticles present internal to the subrows in another large-spaced series (= inner denticle, in the case of genus *Scorpiops*);
- (3) a short (denticle number ≤ 3) apical subrow (which can be termed as “subterminal denticles”) may present posterior to the terminal denticle;
- (4) each subrow typically begins distally with a slightly enlarged (occasionally) denticle (= internal accessory denticle, in the case of genus *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987) and ends proximally in another enlarged denticle (= external accessory denticle, in the case of genus *Olivierus*);
- (5) additional small denticles may present anterior to the enlarged distal denticle within each subrow, occasionally complicating the arrangement;
- (6) the most proximal subrow differs from the others, usually comprising fewer denticles that gradually decrease in size towards the proximity.

From a homology perspective (with reference to the buthid condition), the enlarged distal denticle (EDD) within each subrow is considered associated with the subrow anterior to it. However, in many instances, this denticle is positioned closer to or well within the subrow posterior to it. While no additional denticles are found external to the main subrow series, the frequent emergence of several

small-sized denticles on the inner side contributes to the complex configuration seen in some species. In such cases, it may be challenging or subjective to definitively identify which inner denticles belong to a given subrow, preventing the determination of its trajectory by lining up the associated denticles. Consequently, an analogous protocol is proposed for genus *Chaerilus* in alignment with the considerations for genus *Olivierus* (Tang et al., 2024: 14, figs. 169–187): two types of subrows are defined, a complex subrow and a simple subrow. The complex subrow always includes an enlarged proximal denticle (EPD; as per (4) above), while the simple subrow refers to the most proximal subrow (as per (6) above). The absence of additional denticles on the outer side facilitates the identification of the EPD for each subrow, which can be viewed as an indicator for the presence of a subrow. Therefore, the DSC can be formulated as the number of EPD plus one (being the most proximal subrow). It is noteworthy that the apical subrow should not be counted alongside.

Anomalies can impede accurate enumeration and eclipse the authentic count. For instance, in the right movable finger of an examined adult male *C. conchiformis* (Fig. 19), the most distal (1st) subrow (not the apical subrow) is unusually elongated. While the left movable finger exhibits 7 complex subrows as indicated by EPDs, only 5 EPDs are present on the right. This discrepancy may result from the absence of two EPDs and the fusion of the first through third subrows on the right finger. Such anomalous counts should not be considered diagnostic for species identification; therefore, practitioners must assess each specimen on a case-by-case basis, relying on their expertise and experience to make informed judgments. It may be a subject of debate regarding whether future practitioners should report the corrected DSC in such cases. However, it is recommendable to document the count as it is (a principle adopted henceforth), while providing either textual or photographic descriptions to notify the readers about the anomalous count.

(3) Protocol for the measurement of pedipalp chela length and width

Problems associated with measurement of irregular objects are often neglected in scorpion taxonomy, with many authors either failing to clarify their mensurational methods or allegedly adhering to outdated, poorly defined guidelines (e. g., Stahnke, 1970; Sissom et al., 1990). In a better scenario, some authors provide diagrams for their own set of protocols (e. g., Cain et al., 2021: figs. 11–13). However, the major deficiency in any of the protocols proposed is the arbitrary selection of the initial and terminal points of a distance. Although their diagrams appear quite reasonable in terms of the distance selected for measurement, consistent results are hardly reproducible even if one attempts to adopt the same method owing to the lack of objective, universal landmarks for determining those points. Forde et al. (2022: fig. 3) used even more unreliable mensurational methods. For ChL, they placed one end of the measurement on a flexible segment, the

Figures 92–107. Ventral accessory denticles of cheliceral movable finger in the examined *Chaerilus* species. **Figures 92–93.** Adult male *C. conchiformus*, left (92) and right (93) fingers. **Figures 94–95.** Adult male *C. pseudoconchiformus*, left (94) and right (95) fingers. **Figures 96–97.** Adult female *C. pseudoconchiformus*, left (96) and right (97) fingers. **Figures 98–99.** Adult female *C. sp.* (cf. *herta sp. n.*), left (98) and right (99) fingers. **Figures 100–101.** Adult female *C. sp.* (cf. *herta sp. n.*), left (100) and right (101) fingers. **Figures 102–103.** Adult female *C. cf. tryznai*, left (102) and right (103) fingers. **Figures 104–105.** Adult male *C. variegatus*, left (104) and right (105) fingers. **106–107.** Adult female *C. variegatus*, left (106) and right (107) fingers.

movable finger tip. For ChW, their diagram indicated it was essentially equivalent to chela depth, as it was measured from the external view, also without providing an explanation of the reference system for orientation.

Tang (2023) has elaborated on the chela measurement in the case of *Scorpiops* species and introduced several protocols for obtaining the chela width (ChW). The most preferred one was termed the “condyle method”, in which the condylar axis functions as the pitch axis of the chela. Once this axis is defined, two opposing surfaces orthogonal to it can be used to detect the highest points on the external and internal surfaces, thereby deriving the width (*op. cit.*: figs 93–94). In *Scorpiops*, the pertinent issue is complicated by the presence of a strong ventromedian carina (= V_2 ; Sologlad & Sissom, 2001). However, all *Chaerilus* species lack this carina, presenting instead a planar or slightly convex ventral surface defined by V_1 and V_3 . This seemingly allows one to align the chela’s ventral surface with a horizontal plane, from which its width can be determined using two vertical lines that constrain it bilaterally. Nevertheless, when viewed under higher magnification from the front of the chela, it becomes evident that the condylar axis forms an angle with the ventral plane (Fig. 11). Despite this, the condyle method persists as a viable ChW-deriving approach for all scorpion species given the universal presence of a pair of condyles at the movable finger base. As a result, the current measurement of chela length and width follows the same protocol defined for genus *Scorpiops* in Tang (2023).

ChL/W has frequently been adopted as a quantitative diagnostic character for discriminating congeners across various scorpion genera. The numerical difference, whether between individual values or value ranges, is thus employed to justify species delineation. Since within-practitioner measurement inconsistency is fundamentally unavoidable, it is prudent to account for this variability when making morphology-based species delimitation decisions. One straightforward method to estimate this variation is to determine the human-induced within-specimen measurement error. Practitioners can conduct repeated measurements on a set of specimens, potentially of the same species, with at least a one-day interval between measurements. The greatest numerical difference observed between paired measurements of the same specimen is then considered as an error term (ϵ) attributed to anthropogenic bias. For example, if readers find both Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 reasonable for calculating ChL/W, the interspecific differentiation may not be reliable if the two species being compared exhibit a raw ratiometric difference of 0.2. The ChL/W variation range of the target species, [min, max], can be derived from the averaged measurements of each unique specimen. By applying the error term as a correction factor to the range, [min- ϵ , max+ ϵ] is rendered as a metric for between-species comparison. This conservative approach maximizes the variation under all potential scenarios of repeated measurement. However, a major concern may be the time investment required for the procedure. Species differentiation leveraging ChL/W ultimately entails

confirming that the between-species difference exceeds the within-species variation. A distinction is confirmed if the maximum value of the other species is less than min- ϵ or its minimum value is greater than max+ ϵ , reducing the risk of recognizing false positives due to human errors. Without doubt, this morphological distinction alone may not suffice to justify species separation if a greater actual gradient is present within the target population.

Another critical consideration pertains to the sample size required for reliable conclusions on species characterization, represented by the intraspecific variation. The exact threshold is inherently arbitrary or empirical, depending on the specific taxa under study. For scorpions, which exhibit an evolutionarily conserved body plan and relatively limited intraspecific variation, a large sample size may be impractical or unnecessary. Historically, many scorpion species have been morphologically delineated based on a small sample size (although some authors claimed to have examined numerous specimens, the quantitative diagnostics may not reflect the same sample size, as evidenced by the previous literature review), yet many have been subsequently justified via molecular analyses. I propose an arbitrary minimum threshold sample size of 37 scorpion specimens for obtaining statistically meaningful results, given its mathematical and physical beauty: this number is approximately 100 times the inverse of Euler’s number (e), as well as the inverse of the fine-structure constant (α) minus 100. It also exceeds the commonly regarded guideline of 30 specimens, which is based on the central limit theorem in sample size estimation.

2. Assessment of three qualitative characters

The three qualitative characters—shape of the carapace anterior margin (CAM), surface morphosculpture of sternite VII, and development of metasoma II–III carinae—were evaluated for all 40 male Drepung specimens.

The shape of CAM was found to be unstable (Fig. 117), mirroring conditions observed in *Mesobuthus thersites* populations from Xinjiang, China. Some specimens showed a medially convex margin (column 4, row 3), while others were had a concave (column 2, row 6) or straight (column 1, row 8) margin. Granules along or posterior to this margin were also variable in size and density. One specimen manifested malformation (column 4, row 8), exhibiting a triangular lobe on the left side, next to a medial depression. This anomaly may be of congenital nature, or more likely as an inaccurate regeneration following a postnatal injury. The observed intraspecific variation in the contour of CAM potentially undermines its diagnostic utility for Chinese *Chaerilus* species.

Identification of the paired carinae on sternite VII may be ambiguous and subjective. Among the earlier specimens examined in detail (Figs. 12–91), all Chinese species displayed a granular sternite VII, with the adult pair of *C. variegatus* serving as excellent examples of a smooth sternite. Determination of the presence of carinae in Chinese *Chaerilus* is essentially a quest to identify rows of granules that stand out

Figure 108. Dorsal habitus of all 40 male *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., under white light (freshly retrieved from 75% ethanol, hence dark coloration). Subsequent detailed photos follow the same order (M1–40; ordered →↓). Allotypic paratype male, M4.

conspicuously from a surrounding area of granules of unequal size. A carina can be recognized if relatively larger granules are aligned in a row, but this could easily be influenced by a smooth size gradient in granules, or the increased spacing between the enlarged granules. Based on these criteria, conclusions are made as follows: (1) the examined male *C. conchiformis* showed a pair of well-defined external carinae, while its internal pair was partially discontinued (Fig. 16); (2) both sexes of *C. pseudoconchiformis* exhibited indications of vestigial carinae, and three carinae were most developed in the male (Figs. 24, 32); (3) carinae can be observed in the female *C.*

tricostatus owing to its less granular surroundings (Figs. 40); (4) females of *C. cf. tryznai* and *C. cf. wrzecionkoi* displayed more randomized granulation, without definitive carinae (Fig. 48, 72). To enhance accuracy, all 40 male specimens were ultrasonically cleansed in water to remove most adhered dirt. Sternite VII was then examined under UV light, as the highly sclerotized granules fluoresced more brightly than the surrounding cuticle. The carinae on metasomal segments II–III were analyzed with the same approach. Since the primary objective was to assess the reliability of this qualitative character rather than within-individual asymmetry, only the

Figure 109. Dorsal habitus of all 9 female *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., under white light (freshly retrieved from 75% ethanol, hence dark coloration). Subsequent detailed photos follow the same order (F1–9; ordered →↓). Holotype female, F1.

left lateral surface was examined for all male specimens to optimize time investment. *Chaerilus* species typically possess at least 4 pairs of carinae on metasoma II–III (dorsosubmedian, dorsolateral, ventrolateral, and ventrosubmedian; terminology follows Tang (2023: figs. 42–44)). Whether a species shows 10 carinae on its metasoma II–III essentially depends on the development of the median lateral carina. However, it is noteworthy that I have observed an additional symmetrical pair of “granule series” on the dorsal surfaces of all segments, particularly pronounced on segments I – II (cf. inset next to Fig. 190).

Granules on sternite VII exhibited significant variability, irrespective of body size (Fig. 118). A general pattern was the decline of granulation density in anteromedian and submarginal areas (near lateral and posterior margins). The remaining areas were scattered with granules of unequal sizes, which varied in density across individuals—whereas some specimens were adorned with sparse, small granules, others displayed moderate to large granules. In many instances, granules were uniformly small to medium in size. Enlarged granules occasionally emerged in submedian regions, representing precursors to carinae. Where carinae were discernible, only the internal pair (in reference to other *Chaerilus* species with four

carinae) could be identified, forming a “)” (”) shape. However, these carinae could be highly discrete in their constitutive granules, causing disconnections and intrusions by other, smaller denticles. In other cases, vague traces of carinae were visible, though their granules were indistinguishable in size from surrounding granules.

Lateral surfaces of metasoma II–III shared the same condition with sternite VII in the observed specimens (Fig. 119). This was mainly due to the presence of dense, coarse intercarinal granules that obscured the distinctiveness of the supposedly existent median lateral carina. Intercarinal granulation was especially pronounced between the dorsolateral and ventrolateral carinae, with granules varying randomly in size, hence the alignment of enlarged granules was not consistently present. When identified by reference to other carinae on these segments, in the presence of such alignment, the median lateral carina was always restricted to the distal 1/2 to 1/3, with the proximal region invariably smooth. In most specimens, this carina was present, albeit incompletely. When the spacing between its constitutive granules increased, or when granules were indistinguishable from surrounding ones in size, the carina was considered absent. Semantically, “incomplete” is not equivalent to “absent”. However, many

Figures 110–116. Males (M1, 36–40) of *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. dissected for hemispermatophores. **Figure 110.** Males with their retrieved hemispermatophores on their sternites. **Figures 111–116.** Hemispermatophores enveloped within paraxial organs immersed in water retrieved from the males (in the same order), photographed from above water. Hemispermatophores may be incomplete.

authors only include complete carinae in their count, likely due to concerns over the subjective criteria involved in evaluating carinae of varying completeness. Compared with the regional congener *C. tessellatus*, this species has been documented with a metasomal carina formula of 10-10-10-8-7 in both Qi et al. (2005: 30) and Zhu et al. (2008: 47). According to the more detailed description in the latter, a similar condition was described for the median lateral carinae (as “lateral carinae”) on metasoma II–III in that species, which reached 1/2 on segment II and 1/3 on segment III. It is

thus important for authors to clarify their subjective criteria of carina recognition, or provide detailed descriptions and photographs.

Logically, the current observations only reflect the general trend within this specific population examined, which should not be simply extrapolated to other known *Chaerilus* species. However, they nonetheless cast doubts on the reliability of the diagnostics based on those characters in other species, particularly when the presumed interspecific difference is not pronounced.

Figure 117. Anterior margins of carapace (CAM) of all 40 male *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., under white light. Column 1→4; row 1↓10.

3. Results of two meristics

(1) Pectinal tooth count (PTC)

All Drepung specimens had intact pectines for examination, except for one specimen with a distally truncated left pectine showing only 4 teeth. It was thus estimated to have originally possessed 5 teeth, a count used for subsequent analyses. Pectines varied in color (brownish to yellowish, though, may be a result of preservation), dimension, and relative size of teeth. Most specimens exhibited dilations in the most distal pectinal teeth on both sides. Those aspects were not objectively analyzed in a quantitative manner, but several representative specimens are provided with visual references (Fig. 120–123). Incomplete separation of pectinal

teeth was observed in one specimen and the anomalous tooth was considered as two.

Overall raw PTC data ($n = 80$, both sides; mean \pm SD, 5.138 ± 0.347) showed a majority of pectines possessing 5 teeth (69/80, 86.25%), with the remaining having 6 teeth (11/80, 13.75%). Most (31/40, 77.5%) specimens had 5 teeth on both pectines, and only 2/40 (5%) specimens had 6 on both sides. Intriguingly, among the 7 specimens exhibiting PTC asymmetry, 6/7 had 6 teeth on the right pectine. Increase of PTC was not conspicuously size-correlated, although 5/9 specimens possessing 6 teeth on at least one pectine belonged to the upper half of the size range (visually determined). Fisher's exact test on overall

left (mean \pm SD, 5.075 ± 0.267) and right (mean \pm SD, 5.2 ± 0.405) PTC revealed no significant difference ($p = 0.193$). McNemar's test on paired left-right PTC (i.e., within-individual comparison) also suggested the same ($p = 0.125$), as can be readily expected.

(2) Denticle subrow count (DSC)

The apical subrow could hardly be confused with the first subrow as it always composed of no more than 3 denticles. Subrows varied in relative length, especially in the most proximal (ultimate) subrow. Identification of the ultimate subrow may be particularly reliant upon the presence of an externally positioned denticle which serves to divide the subrows (Fig. 126), as this subrow may occasionally be connected with the penultimate subrow, reducing the degree of imbrication and thus confusing the true count. This external divisive denticle could also be partially integrated into the subrow (Fig. 127). Lower count typically stemmed from a similar condition with the absence of such a denticle (Fig. 124–125).

Most (37/40, 92.5%) Drepung specimens had 9 or 10 subrows on either finger; 24/37 (64.9%) had 9 on both sides, 4/37 (10.8%) had 10 on both sides, 6/37 (16.2%) showed a DSC of 9/10, and 3/37 (8.1%) of 10/9. The three outliers possessed 9/8 (Fig. 125, right finger), 7/9 (Fig. 128, left finger), and 8/6 (Fig. 129, left finger) subrows; the case of 6 subrows on the right finger was due to apical breakage. Frequency of 9 subrows was 59/80 (73.75%), and of 10 subrows was 17/80 (21.25%). With the three outliers excluded ($n = 74$, both sides), males showed a mean \pm SD of 9.23 ± 0.424 ; overall left (mean \pm SD, 9.189 ± 0.397) and right (mean \pm SD, 9.27 ± 0.45) DSC were not significantly different (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.581$); paired left-right DSC confirmed with the same non-significance (McNemar's test, $p = 0.508$). Spearman's rank correlation test on left-right averaged PTC and DSC for 37 specimens (with the three DSC outliers excluded) indicated that there was a non-significant small negative relationship ($\rho = -0.255$, $p = 0.127$).

4. Analysis of ChL/W vs. CaL

Given the inevitable inaccuracies in measurement, I will not focus too much on the exact values but instead the overall characteristic of the resultant dataset. I have never been a strong advocate for exact measurement data, nor do I encourage readers to place excessive emphasis on them or the scale bars in the figures. The obtained ChL/W should be interpreted cautiously and not directly compared with existing data from other species. Notably, ChL measurements may be underestimated when specimens possess fixed fingers that are either abnormally curved distally ($n = 2$) or broken ($n = 3$, corrected by inputting the same length as the intact finger).

Mean \pm SD of ChL/W derived from left-right averaged values ($n = 40$) from all 40 males was 3.59 ± 0.178 ; Mann-Whitney U (MWU) test on overall left (mean \pm SD, 3.61 ± 0.184) and right (mean \pm SD, 3.58 ± 0.181) ChL/W were not significantly different ($p = 0.419$; symmetrical); Wilcoxon Signed-Rank (WSR) test on paired left-right ChL/W revealed significant difference ($p = 0.003$; mean \pm SD of left-right

ChL/W difference: 0.036 ± 0.078). The observed within-individual asymmetry might be attributed to the anthropogenic inaccuracies. Scatterplots in Figs. 132–133 visualize the left-right asymmetry in ChL and ChW, which is more conspicuous in ChW.

A cursory examination discovered a notable difference in ChL/W between the largest and smallest Drepung males, with greater relative ChW seemingly confined to smaller males (Fig. 131). To verify whether ChL/W is size-correlated, CaL was measured for all specimens as an indicator of body size (resultant CaL range: 5.33–7.15 mm). Shapiro-Wilk (SW) tests confirmed normality for both CaL ($W = 0.976$, $p = 0.532$) and ChL/W ($W = 0.95$, $p = 0.077$). Pearson's correlation coefficient demonstrated a significantly strong positive relationship ($r = 0.885$, $p = 3.397e-14$), which was similarly corroborated by Spearman's rank correlation coefficient ($\rho = 0.88$, $p = 7.816e-14$) (Fig. 136). This suggests a static allometry between CaL and ChL/W in the adult males of this species. A positive allometry (slope > 1) was observed for CaL vs. ChL, while a negative allometry (slope < 1) was discovered in CaL vs. ChW (Figs. 134–135). This is congruent with the fact that greater relative ChW is present in smaller males.

5. Multivariate analyses on 37 adult male specimens

To assess the probability of this population containing more than one species, a multivariate analysis was performed on 10 variables (putatively diagnostic) for 37 male specimens (excluding the three outliers): CaL, ChL, ChW, DSC, PTC, and sternite VII; bilateral data were used for ChL, ChW, DSC, and PTC. The carina state on sternite VII was subjectively scored as 0 (acarinate) or 2 (bicarinate), based on the presence of enlarged denticles extending almost continuously to the posterior margin, as annotated in Fig. 118. CAM shape was excluded due to the subtle differences between the three states as well as the asymmetry observed in some specimens, and metasomal carinae on II–III were omitted due to their similar degree of development across most individuals. Since the raw dataset included both continuous and binary discrete variables, Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD), combining Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA), was performed using the FactoMineR package (ver. 2.11) in RStudio (Lê et al., 2008).

A SW test was initially conducted on the raw dataset of the five continuous variables (Table 4). Since all variables generally conformed to a normal distribution (symmetrical and mesokurtic), no log-transformation was applied prior to further analyses. As FAMD deploys PCA to analyze continuous variables, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity were performed in advance on the Z-standardized dataset in SPSS. Both tests yielded promising results, confirming sampling adequacy and suitability for PCA: (1) KMO index = 0.825 (> 0.5), indicating high sampling adequacy; (2) Bartlett's test: approximate $\chi^2 = 415.81$, $p = 4.051E-83$, suggesting significant suitability. Since the FAMD algorithm automatically standardizes the variables, the raw

dataset of all ten variables was then directly fed into RStudio, where the binary discrete variables were manually converted into factors by code for FAMD to treat them as categorical.

The scree plot (in Fig. 139) showed a distinct elbow after the first principal dimension (PD1), reflecting a sharp decrease in the magnitude of eigenvalues from PD1 to PD2, with stabilization occurring from PD3 onward. This pattern indicates that the first dimension captures the most significant underlying structures of the raw dataset. PD1 explained 48.238% of the total variance, while PD2 and PD3 explained 16.604% and 11.18%, respectively, together accounting for 76.023% of the total variance. All continuous and discrete variables contributed significantly to PD1 and PD2, respectively (Fig. 139); all continuous variables had high \cos^2 values (above 0.898; particularly for left (0.967) and right (0.972) ChL) and contribution values (~ 20) on PD1. PD3 was predominantly contributed by sternite VII states and left DSC. Scatterplot of the first two PDs showed no clear clusters, and the single specimen positioned outside the 95% confidence ellipse was M7 (Fig. 138). Further cluster analyses were performed in order to reveal potential subgroups.

In OriginPro, a K-Means Cluster Analysis (KMCA) was performed on the principal component coordinate matrix across the five principal dimensions obtained from FAMD (henceforth referred to as “PD matrix”) in RStudio. The optimal cluster number was determined by the elbow method and silhouette scores, suggesting 4 and 2 clusters, respectively. However, given the overall similarity in the morphology of the specimens, the elbow method might have overestimated, thus a cluster number of 2 was adopted in the KMCA parameter setting. The two potential clusters identified showed an Euclidean centroid distance of 3.804, implying some separation (Fig. 140). Among the males examined, 15 specimens (M1–M13, M15–M16) were allocated to Cluster 1, and 22 (M17–M19, M21–M38, M40) to Cluster 2, displaying a clear cut between two size classes. The within-cluster sum of squares was higher for Cluster 2 (123.583) than for Cluster 1 (89.517), indicating greater heterogeneity in Cluster 2 and a more compact grouping around the centroid in Cluster 1. Average (Cluster 1: 2.317, Cluster 2: 2.263) and maximum distances (Cluster 1: 4.121, Cluster 2: 4.016) are generally similar, supporting relatively balanced clustering. To test the statistical significance of the KMCA clusters, the PD matrix was categorized into these two groups (henceforth referred to as “KMCA-based PD matrix”), upon which a PERMANOVA (999 runs) was performed using the ‘vegan’ package (ver. 2.6-8) in RStudio. The algorithm returned a p value of 0.001 ($F = 21.196$), implying significant difference between the two clusters, though a moderate R^2 (0.377) suggested substantial within-group variability, likely due to the similar meristic characters.

This outcome is largely predictable, as the employed continuous variables explain most of the variance and are interdependent. Left and right ChL are strongly positively correlated with each other, and their mean is also positively correlated with CaL (as is ChW). In essence, KMCA partitioned the raw dataset into two clusters corresponding to two size

classes, which show gradient changes within the population. To facilitate readers’ understanding, I have distinguished the two clusters in the CaL vs. ChL/W scatterplot according to the reassignment by KMCA (Fig. 136). Indeed, directly comparison of the specimens assigned to the two clusters confirmed the same significance (MWU), based on raw, unstandardized data (symmetrical in both clusters): **(1)** CaL, $p = 3.892e-7$; **(2)** mean ChL/W, $p = 1.043e-5$; **(3)** mean ChL, $p = 3.605e-7$; **(4)** mean ChW, $p = 5.838e-7$. To provide additional sources of statistical references, I also conducted a parametric alternative (MANOVA in SPSS) for the two clusters, using only the five original continuous variables. Box’s M test verified equality of covariance matrices across groups ($p = 0.409$). Levene’s test based on means confirmed homoscedasticity for all variables (p values ranging from 0.084 to 0.448). The MANOVA returned a large effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.734$), a high observed power (1), and significant p values (< 0.001) for all statistics (Pillai’s Trace, Wilks’ Lambda, Hotelling’s Trace, and Roy’s Largest Root). Between-subjects effects suggested significant difference ($p < 0.001$) for all variables, with partial η^2 ranging from 0.644 to 0.697.

While this appears plausible to justify two distinct groups, the dendrogram generated from the Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) based on the same PD matrix slightly contradicted KMCA (Fig. 142). The analysis was performed with Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic mean (UPGMA) as the linkage method and Euclidean as the distance metric. M4 (CaL 6.9, mean ChL/W 3.68, DSC 10/10, PTC 5/6, sternite VII acarinate) and M18 (CaL 6.22, mean ChL/W 3.65, DSC 9/9, PTC 5/5, sternite VII bicarinate) were respectively identified as the least and most representative specimens. Specimens included in the first (red) and second (green) clusters were generally identical with the two classified by KMCA: 15 specimens were assigned to Cluster 1 (with M7 replaced by M22), while 19 were assigned to Cluster 2 (with the exclusion of M21, M22, and M27). Concordance between the two methods was high, with the Clusters 1 from HCA and KMCA showing 93.3% agreement, and Clusters 2 displaying 86.4% agreement. Direct comparison of the specimens assigned to the first two HCA clusters confirmed another significance (MWU), based on raw, unstandardized data (symmetrical in both clusters): **(1)** CaL, $p = 1.548e-6$; **(2)** mean ChL/W, $p = 4.019e-7$; **(3)** mean ChL, $p = 4.31e-9$; **(4)** mean ChW, $p = 6.504e-6$. Of particular interest is the third cluster (blue) diverged from all other specimens at the basal branching. Cluster 3 grouped three specimens with distinct CaL and/or ChL/W values together (their positions within the gradient are visualized in the scatterplot of Fig. 142), and their diagnostic characters are given as follows: **(1)** M7: CaL 6.88, mean ChL 14.05, mean ChW 3.705, mean ChL/W 3.79, PTC 6/6; **(2)** M21: CaL 6.28, mean ChL 13.25, mean ChW 3.675, mean ChL/W 3.61, PTC 6/5; **(3)** M27: CaL 5.92, mean ChL 13.25, mean ChW 3.605, mean ChL/W 3.43, PTC 6/6. All three had DSC 9/9 and bicarinate sternite VII. This suggested similarities in other features (e. g., meristic characters like DSC and sternite VII) might have affected the specimens’ topological positions within the HCA dendrogram.

Figure 118. Sternite VII of all 40 male *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., under UV light against black cloth. Column 1→4; row 1↓10. Binary carina states annotated in the figure; 0 = acarinate, 2 = bicarinate.

Figure 119. Metasoma II–III on the left side in lateral view of all 40 male *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., under UV light against black cloth. Column 1→4; row 1↓10.

Figures 120–129. Representative pectines (under white light) and pedipalp movable fingers (under UV light against black cloth; red number, complex subrow; green number, simple subrow) of examined males of *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. **Figures 120–123.** Pectines of males showing 5/5 (120), 6/6 (121), 5/6 (122), and 6/5 (123) teeth (note that the left/right PTC in the figures should be switched as such because the specimens are viewed in the current orientation). **Figures 124–125.** Movable fingers showing a loss of an EPD (red circles). **Figure 126.** Movable finger showing an EPD positioned externally to the connected 9th and 10th subrows. **Figure 127.** Movable finger showing an EPD integrated into the 8th and 9th subrows. **Figure 128.** Movable finger showing abnormally elongated 1st and 2nd subrows. **Figure 129.** Movable finger showing at least the loss of at least one EPD along the current 2nd subrow.

The notable similarity between the two analyses presumably enhanced the credibility of KMCA, prompting further validation through Canonical Discriminant Analysis (CDA) with default settings in OriginPro on the KMCA-based PD matrix. A single discriminant function explained 100% of the variance, with an eigenvalue of 2.894, a canonical correlation (CC) of 0.862, a Wilks' Lambda (Λ) of 0.257, a χ^2 of 44.179, and a p value < 0.0001. These metrics suggest a substantial difference between the canonical group means (Group 1: mean = 2.004; Group 2: mean = -1.366). Unsurprisingly, univariate ANOVA results indicated that PD1 ($R^2 = 0.718$; $F = 89.012$; $p < 0.0001$) was the strongest contributor to group differentiation. In contrast, the other four PDs showed very low R^2 values (< 0.01), F statistics (< 0.53), and high p values ($0.47 < p < 0.81$).

These results imply that PD1 encompassing all continuous variables was predominant in forming the clusters, consistent with my initial observations of the specimen series which prompted me to identify size classes. However, the partial incongruence between KMCA and HCA classifications prevents a definitive conclusion regarding the allocation of specimens to two potential morphological groups (species?). In addition, the HCA clustering of the specimens based on the PD matrix appeared to be sensitive to the chosen linkage method. When Ward's method was applied instead of UPGMA, three main groups were identified, each containing no less than 10 specimens (Fig. 143). While these three groups generally corresponded to three size classes, minor overlaps were observed. For example, M7 (CaL 6.88)

Figure 130. Sternite VII and metasoma II–III (F9 lost segments posterior to metasoma I) of all 9 female *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. under UV light against black cloth, and pectines of one female (F8) showing 4/5 teeth. Column 1→3; row 1↓6.

and M10 (CaL 6.61) from the larger size class and M33 (CaL 5.8) from the smaller size class were allocated to the median size class, while M26 (CaL 6.19) from the median size class was allocated to the smaller size class. Specimens were reclassified into the three groups, forming a new PD matrix upon which a CDA was performed (not performed on the previous HCA-based PD matrix as Cluster 3 included only 3 specimens). Two canonical variables (CV) were extracted: CV1 (eigenvalue = 6.559, CC = 0.932, $\Lambda = 0.077$, $\chi^2 = 82.218$, $p < 0.0001$) and CV2 (eigenvalue = 0.727, CC = 0.649, $\Lambda = 0.579$, $\chi^2 = 17.491$, $p = 0.002$) contributed respectively 90.02% and 9.98% of the variance. Standardized canonical coefficients revealed that PD1 contributed the most to CV1 (1.163), while PD5 was the major contributor

to CV2 (0.918). Pairwise distances showed that Cluster 1 and 2 were closer to each other (Fig. 144), and Cluster 1 and 3 were the most distant ($d_{1-3} = 42.429$; $d_{1-2} = 10.796$; $d_{2-3} = 16.235$). Group centroids further supported this pattern: Cluster 1 (2.9739) and Cluster 3 (-3.5392) occupied the most distinct positions along CV1, while CV2 contributed minor additional separation (Cluster 1: -0.77396; Cluster 3: -0.64457). Univariate ANOVA results again indicated that PD1 ($R^2 = 0.804$; $F = 69.882$; $p < 0.0001$) was the strongest contributor to group differentiation. In contrast, PD2 ($R^2 = 0.016$; $F = 0.285$; $p = 0.754$) and PD3 ($R^2 = 0.05$; $F = 0.898$; $p = 0.417$) showed moderate contributions, while PD4 ($R^2 = 0.094$; $F = 1.761$; $p = 0.187$) and PD5 ($R^2 = 0.324$; $F = 8.146$; $p = 0.001$) contributed minimally.

To evaluate the significance between the three groups, PERMANOVA was performed in RStudio as before, as the SW test returned significant p-values for Group 2 on PD2 (0.028) and PD5 (0.02), and Group 3 on PD3 (< 0.001) and PD4 (0.017), indicating unsuitability for MANOVA. Significant differences were confirmed for all pairwise comparisons: **(1)** Group 1 vs Group 2: $F = 8.8899$, $p = 0.001$; **(2)** Group 1 vs Group 3: $F = 36.332$, $p = 0.001$; **(3)** Group 2 vs Group 3: $F = 8.8333$, $p = 0.001$. However, this result may reflect overestimation due to the high intraspecific variability in body size and ChL/W. Notable overlap can be observed in the CaL vs. mean ChL/W scatterplot (inserted in Fig. 143), with the three groups indicated (red, Group 1; green, Group 2; blue, Group 3). The F statistic was relatively small between adjacent groups, yet it increased 4-fold between the two extremes. This is similar to removing all the intermediate specimens and comparing only the largest and smallest size classes.

Several additional analyses were performed for reference:

A mixed dataset comprising five Z-standardized continuous variables and five binarized (0/1) discrete variables (DSC 9/10, PTC 5/6, sternite VII 0/2) was input into RStudio without dimensional reduction. An HCA was performed using the R package ‘cluster’ (ver. 2.1.8), applying Gower’s distance metric and the complete-linkage method. Basal branching diverged into two clusters which again showed a general correlation with CaL, ChL, ChW, and ChL/W (Fig. 145).

The KMCA-based PD matrix was shuffled to randomize the membership of specimens between two predefined clusters (upper Cluster 1, $n = 15$, and lower Cluster 2, $n = 22$). This was done in RStudio using the ‘sample()’ function, with ‘set.seed(i)’ (for i in 42:51; arbitrary number) ensuring different randomizations in each iteration. In the shuffled dataset, the upper 15 specimens were reassigned to a new Cluster 1, and the remaining 22 specimens were reassigned to a new Cluster 2. A CDA was performed on each shuffled dataset in OriginPro. This procedure was repeated 10 times independently on the original dataset. The results for the 10 CDA iterations are given in Table 5. In all 10 reshuffled datasets, CDA failed to detect significant differences between the two new clusters, suggesting the robustness of KMCA clustering.

In MATLAB, Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) was employed as a pseudorandom number generator to assess the reliability of the multivariate analysis protocol applied earlier. Variable ranges ([min, max], {min, max}) are predefined based on real-world data of the 37 specimens examined herein: **(1)** continuous variables (‘cont’): CaL [5.3, 7.2], ChL_L and ChL_R [10.6, 15.4], ChW_L and ChW_R [3.2, 4.1]; **(2)** discrete (binary) variables (‘bin’): DSC_L and DSC_R {9, 10}, PTC_L and PTC_R {5, 6}, sternite VII {0, 2}. For continuous variables, synthetic data were generated by the script ‘cont = min + (max - min) * rand(n, 1)’. For binary variables, data were either generated by ‘bin = randi([min, max], n, 1)’, or by ‘bin = randi([0, 1], n, 1)*2’ (for sternite VII, which only takes values of 0 or 2). These scripts construct a uniform distribution for the variables, contrasting with the quasi-normal distribution seen in the

real dataset. Four synthetic datasets (A–D) were generated and analyzed (Fig. 141). Dataset A was semi-stochastic—artificially combined after individually generating each synthetic continuous variable until they all achieved a similar distribution pattern; the discrete variables are independent of the continuous ones, so they were not repeatedly selected. This approach takes into account the correlation between certain pairs of continuous variables observed in the real-world data (Cholesky decomposition can be used to impose restrictions on MCS with given correlations to generate desired synthetic datasets; however, no real correlations were used in this case as that was not the objective). For example, it is unrealistic for the left ChL to display a unimodal Gaussian distribution while its right counterpart shows a concave profile with two peaks at the extremities. The combined dataset was directly used for subsequent analyses. Dataset B used the same data as A but was modified in a descending order for all continuous variables so as to re-establish the gradient or essentially the strong positive correlation between them (cf. Table 6). Dataset C was fully stochastic after simultaneously generating all variables; however, the one used for analyses was subjectively chosen after multiple rounds of simulations in order to maximize its utility (i.e., unstructured randomness) in this study. Dataset D mirrored C except that 37000 specimens were generated, and the final distribution approximated a uniform one. FAMD (on raw datasets to obtain matrices of 5 PDs), KMCA (on PD matrices; 2 groups), PERMANOVA (on KMCA-clustered PD matrices), and CDA (on KMCA-clustered PD matrices) were successively performed on the synthetic datasets as before. **Dataset A:** random contributions to PD1 and PD2 by both variables, overlapped KMCA groups (confidence ellipses weakly to moderately overlapping), significant PERMANOVA results ($p = 0.001$, $F = 8.65$, $R^2 = 0.198$), significant CDA results ($CC = 0.902$, $\Lambda = 0.187$, $\chi^2 = 54.504$, $p < 0.0001$); **Dataset B:** all continuous variables contributed to PD1 while discrete variables contributed to PD2 (similar to Fig. 139), non-overlapping KMCA groups, significant PERMANOVA results ($p = 0.001$, $F = 23.301$, $R^2 = 0.4$), significant CDA results ($CC = 0.872$, $\Lambda = 0.239$, $\chi^2 = 46.476$, $p < 0.0001$); **Dataset C:** random contributions to PD1 and PD2 by both variables, overlapped KMCA groups (confidence ellipses in contact), significant PERMANOVA results ($p = 0.001$, $F = 6.866$, $R^2 = 0.164$), significant CDA results ($CC = 0.852$, $\Lambda = 0.274$, $\chi^2 = 42.126$, $p < 0.0001$); **Dataset D:** random contributions to PD1 and PD2 by both variables, overlapped KMCA groups (confidence ellipses highly disjunct but “data clouds” adjacent and weakly overlapping), PERMANOVA results not available (due to high computational memory requirements), significant CDA results ($CC = 0.815$, $\Lambda = 0.336$, $\chi^2 = 40335.654$, $p < 0.0001$). In addition, an HCA (with Gower’s metric) was performed on the Z-standardized continuous variables and 0/1-binarized discrete variables of Dataset A. The PD matrix was then classified into two groups based on the basal branching of the resultant dendrogram; PERMANOVA returned yet another

Figure 131. Exemplar pedipalp chelae of adult male *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. ranging from the largest to smallest specimens, under white light. Scale bar = 5 mm.

significance ($p = 0.001$, $F = 6.608$, $R^2 = 0.159$), and so did CDA ($CC = 0.846$, $\Lambda = 0.284$, $\chi^2 = 40.945$, $p < 0.0001$). These results confirm that the underlying distribution does not affect the performance of clustering algorithms. Comparison of the KMCA scatterplots between Dataset A and B implies that more strongly correlated variables may lead to clearer group distinctions.

The above outcomes suggest that post-clustering validations with PERMANOVA and/or CDA on the KMCA and/or HCA-based dataset may not be very meaningful, as both clustering algorithms have already optimized for group separation. Those significance tests could be more informative for assessing artificially predefined groups (e. g., species). In addition, results from clustering algorithms like KMCA and HCA do not explicitly constitute any confirmations for the existence of taxonomical groups. On the other hand, while group-comparison tests may validate the distinction between presumed morphospecies, the significant results from those tests based on stochastically generated and biologically meaningless datasets (e. g., A, C, D) add caveats to their interpretation. In this case, multivariate analyses should be viewed as but references, with the researcher's empirical judgment serving as the final guide. Likewise, a statistically significant result should only be seen as a basic requirement rather than as an ultimate measure of importance or an absolute indicator.

In conclusion, the detected clusters most likely simply reflect size-class differences resulting from the various instars at which the scorpions mature (cf. Benton, 1991: fig. 4), rather than the presence of two distinct species, given their sympatry and the lack of other notable morphological differences. It is also doubtful whether body size and ChL/W alone are sufficient to justify distinct species when gradients are present, especially considering the lack of clear groupings in the FAMD graph based on raw component data and the considerable overlap observed in the KMCA plot. More fundamentally, KMCA is dependent upon a subjective choice of the number of clusters. At this stage, I deem it more prudent to treat all male Drepung specimens as conspecific. This hence suggests the high intraspecific variability of body size and ChL/W, which might undermine their utility as morphological thresholds for discriminating Chinese *Chaerilus* species. Therefore, I believe the hereby results at best imply that: (1) intraspecific size classes can be significantly different; (2) sample size is crucial for accurately capturing variation; and (3) the justification for new species based on these continuous metrics must be approached with caution. Consequently, these analyses should be leveraged discreetly when inferring species boundaries on a morphological basis, and more emphases should be placed on non-morphometric characters, if they exhibit unambiguous distinctions (e. g., carina characters in *Scorpiops*).

6. Sexual dimorphism

The 9 adult Drepung females were only examined in detail for their PTC, DSC, ChL/W, and carinae on sternite VII and metasoma II–III; CAM shape can be inferred from Figs. 154 and 211. The results are given below briefly.

(1) PTC:

All 9 females had 4 pectinal teeth on both sides, except for one (Fig. 130, column 3, row 5) showing 5 teeth on its right pectine (frequency of PTC = 4, 94%; frequency of PTC = 5, 6%). Comparison of raw PTC data between males ($n = 80$; both sides) and females ($n = 18$; both sides) indicated significant sexual dimorphism (χ^2 test of independence, $p = 1.643e-08$); left-right averaged PTC data (males, $n = 40$; females, $n = 9$) showed stronger significance (χ^2 test of independence, $p = 5.839e-10$).

(2) DSC:

All 9 females displayed unambiguously 9 or 10 denticle subrows on their movable fingers; one count of 9 was apparently due to the lack of a divisive denticle between the penultimate and ultimate subrows, causing relatively long 9th subrow. Asymmetry in DSC was slightly more ubiquitous: 9/9 ($n = 3$), 10/10 ($n = 1$), 10/9 ($n = 3$), 9/10 ($n = 2$). Comparison of raw DSC data between males ($n = 74$; both sides, excluding the 3 outliers) and females ($n = 18$; both sides) indicated no significant sexual dimorphism (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.23$); left-right averaged DSC data (males, $n = 37$, excluding the 3 outliers; females, $n = 9$) yielded the same implication (χ^2 test of independence, $p = 0.17$).

(3) ChL/W:

Mean \pm SD of ChL/W derived from left-right averaged values ($n = 9$) from all 9 females was 3.03 ± 0.127 ; overall left (mean \pm SD, 3.03 ± 0.146) and right (mean \pm SD, 3.04 ± 0.113) ChL/W were not significantly different (MWU, $p = 1$); paired left-right ChL/W confirmed with the same non-significance (WSR, $p = 1$). Despite the presence of small males with lower ChL/W, overall sexual dimorphism in this character was nonetheless strongly significant (left-right averaged; MWU, $p = 4e-6$). The oscillation of data points around the diagonal line suggests either asymmetry or measurement inaccuracy (Fig. 137), although both sexes showed large overall R^2 (> 0.8 ; that of the males will increase to 0.864 if M13, one with a distally curved fixed finger, is removed).

(4) Carinae on sternite VII and metasoma II–III:

The condition of carina development in females closely parallels that observed in males (Fig. 130), especially on metasoma II–III. However, the granules on sternite VII appeared more prominent in females, with the internal pair displaying a consistently greater degree of continuity. In rare cases, traces of the external pair could be discerned. Nonetheless, these granules never coalesced into a distinct carinal trajectory akin to that of the internal pair. Subjectively, the morphosculpture of sternite VII among the examined females does not match the qualitative characterizations of *C. tessellatus* by Qi et al. (2005) or Zhu et al. (2008), where the females of that species were described with a smooth sternite VII.

7. Taxonomic conclusion

The character combination of PTC 5–6 in ♂ and 4–5 (rarely, 6%, 5) in ♀, DSC 9–10, and well-developed D_3 is unique among all Chinese *Chaerilus* species (Table 1). These characters were consistent across all 49 specimens (40♂, 9♀) examined, barring the subrow anomaly observed in three male

Figures 132–137. Bivariate scatterplots visualizing the correlations between morphometrics in adult *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. **Figures 132–133.** Asymmetry in the left-right measurements of ChL (132) and ChW (133) in 40 males; red line is diagonal. **Figure 134.** Logarithmic plot of CaL (abscissa) vs. ChL (ordinate) in 40 males. **Figure 135.** Logarithmic plot of CaL (abscissa) vs. ChW (ordinate) in 40 males. **Figure 136.** Correlation between CaL (abscissa) and mean ChL/W (ordinate) in 40 males; colors correspond to the two clusters identified by KMCA (Cluster 1, grey, $n = 15$; Cluster 2, red, $n = 22$) and the three DSC outliers (yellow); the trend line pertains to the overall correlation. **Figure 137.** Sexual dimorphism in ChL/W between 40 males (blue) and 9 females (red); grey line is diagonal. The triangle outlier male (M13) had a distally curved right fixed finger.

Figures 138–141. Multivariate analyses on 37 adult males of *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. **Figure 138.** Factorial analysis of mixed data (FAMD) scatterplot based on the first two principal dimensions (explaining 64.84% of the total variance), representing the distribution of specimens in a reduced-dimensional space, where PD1 (abscissa) and PD2 (ordinate) capture the most significant sources of variation in both continuous and discrete variables. Ellipse generated by confidence level (0.95). The specimen external to the ellipse corresponds to M7. **Figure 139.** Scatterplot showing the contributions of continuous (grey) and discrete (red) variables to PD1 (abscissa) and PD2 (ordinate). Inset: scree plot showing the percentage of the total variance explained by the eigenvalues of 5 principal dimensions. **Figure 140.** K-means cluster analysis (KMCA) scatterplot based on the principal component coordinate matrix of 5 PDs, showing the potential groupings of two clusters with convex hulls. The centroid ellipses indicate the confidence regions (95% confidence level). **Figure 141.** Continuous variable (CaL, ChL_L, ChL_R, ChW_L, and ChW_R) distribution bar plots of real-world dataset (1st row) and Monte Carlo synthetic Dataset A&B (2nd row), C (3rd row) and D (4th row), generated in MATLAB. Vertical, probability density; horizontal, values; not shown.

specimens. Comparison of ChL/W data may prove meaningless given the between-author methodological discrepancy and within-author measurement inconsistency. Two species close in both morphology and geography are *C. tessellatus* and *C. tryznai*. If one assumes that the diagnostic data of both species were based on *all* specimens their respective authors studied, then the following conclusions can be made: (1) *C. tessellatus* (4♀, in original description; 1♀, 4 juv. ♀, in subsequent Chinese papers) can be supposedly distinguished by the higher DSC (11) and probably higher PTC (5 in ♀); (2) *C. tryznai* (1♂, 12♀, 1 juv., in original description; 8♀, in subsequent Chinese papers) can be supposedly distinguished by the lower DSC (8) and PTC (4 in ♂ and 3–4 in ♀). Indeed, both Qi et al. (2005: fig. 110) and Zhu et al. (2008: fig. 47) depicted 11 subrows for the holotype female *C. tessellatus*. However,

fraudulent illustrations are not unprecedented in this field (see Kovařík, 2018; Lowe & Kovařík, 2022), and no confident conclusion can be drawn in the absence of photographic evidence. Unfortunately, the type specimen of this species is lost (Tang, 2025: 3).

Uncertainties remain regarding this pivotal presumption, as well as the potential existence of a character gradient between populations and/or greater intraspecific variation. The two female *C. tryznai* reported from Mědog County are suspicious given their distance from the type locality (although many other *Chaerilus* are similarly widespread; Fig. 1) and the lack of photographic documentation. Nevertheless, the reported data (PTC = 3, DSC = 8; Zhu et al., 2008) accorded with the ones originally diagnosed for this species and continue to differentiate them from the 9 unidentified female

Figures 142–145: Dendrograms generated in OriginPro from hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) based on the PD matrix with Euclidean distance. M4 and M18 were consistently recovered as the least and most representative specimens, respectively. Insets: CaL (latitude) vs. mean ChL/W (longitude) correlation scatterplots with colored dots corresponding to the dendrogram clusters. **Figure 142.** HCA based on the UPGMA linkage method. Three subsets recognized at a distance threshold range ca. 4.7–5.2 are colored. **Figure 143.** HCA based on Ward's linkage method. Three subsets recognized at a distance threshold range ca. 17–28 are colored. **Figure 144.** Canonical discriminant analysis (CDA) scatterplot based on Fig. 143, showing the potential groupings of three clusters with convex hulls; group centroids indicated by small rhomboids. **Figure 145.** Dendrogram generated in R from HCA based on Z-standardized metrics and binarized meristics with Gower's distance, coupled with correlation scatterplots with colored dots corresponding to the dendrogram clusters.

specimens examined herein. The other species, *C. tessellatus*, warrants intensive scrutiny, as all current 49 specimens were collected from its type locality, Drepung Township, albeit not sharing the exact coordinates. The key distinguishing character between the two species is DSC. This character is not sexually dimorphic, and hence a consistently lower count of 9–10 in the currently examined specimens is supported by a large sample size ($n = 94$, excluding the three outliers and one broken finger; or $n = 46$, when considering only specimens with both normal fingers) and the resultant data can be regarded as statistically reliable.

Suppose all 9 female *C. tessellatus* had 11 subrows on both fingers (DSC = 11, $n = 18$), the between-female comparison would indicate a statistically significant difference (MWU, exact calculation, $p = 2.204e-10$) from the currently examined female specimens. Conversely, if we challenge the earlier

presumption as false, i.e., the count of 11 denticle subrows in *C. tessellatus* was not consistently supported by all 9 females those Chinese authors examined, then we must take into account the probability of anomaly. Anomalous DSC in the 97 (excluding the broken finger) fingers examined has a frequency of 0.03. If we apply this frequency to *C. tessellatus*, that is, there is a 3% chance of 11 subrows being anomalous, with a 97% probability that the ordinary count is either, perhaps, 10 or 12, we would therefore expect another significant difference between the two groups if the true common value in *C. tessellatus* was even higher than 11. In another case, if 17 out of 18 fingers of *C. tessellatus* displayed 10 denticle subrows, the difference between the two groups (females only) would remain significant (MWU, exact calculation, $p = 7.578e-4$).

Among the 97 intact fingers (both sides, both sexes) examined herein, the overall frequency of DSC = 9 is 72.2%

(70/97), and of DSC = 10 is 24.7% (24/97). Assuming that the 17 fingers of *C. tessellatus* follow the identical pattern, we shall input 9 for $n = 12$ and 10 for $n = 4$, with the remaining 1 finger possibly being either 9 or 10. If this remaining finger takes a value of 9 (DSC = 9, $n = 13$; DSC = 10, $n = 4$; DSC = 11, $n = 1$), the between-female comparison implies a non-significant difference between *C. tessellatus* and the studied population (MWU, exact calculation, $p = 0.65$); if it takes 10 (DSC = 9, $n = 12$; DSC = 10, $n = 5$; DSC = 11, $n = 1$), the non-significance persists and strengthens (MWU, exact calculation, $p = 0.864$). These results are predictable as we are essentially replacing the lower outliers (7, 8) in the current dataset of the unidentified population with a higher, new value (11). What if the DSC indeed tends to be higher in *C. tessellatus*? We can test the significance by reversing the probabilities assigned to 9 and 10 in our imaginary dataset of *C. tessellatus*. If the remaining 1 finger takes 9 (DSC = 9, $n = 5$; DSC = 10, $n = 12$; DSC = 11, $n = 1$), the between-female comparison reveals a slightly non-significant difference (MWU, exact calculation, $p = 0.0685$); if it takes 10 (DSC = 9, $n = 4$; DSC = 10, $n = 13$; DSC = 11, $n = 1$), the significance increases (MWU, exact calculation, $p = 0.03421$).

In fact, two immature specimens were also collected alongside the adult ones (Fig. 202), but they were omitted in previous sections to streamline the narrative. These specimens were identified as females based on their PTC counts (4/4 for the larger specimen and 5/4 for the smaller one; Figs. 203–204). The larger female exhibited 9/9 denticle subrows (Figs. 209–210), while the smaller female showed 9/10 subrows (Figs. 207–208). Notably, one EPD was absent in both fingers of the smaller female, and the count was determined by the EDD. I have acquired two additional adult females from Mèdog County (Figs. 52–67), which appeared to be conspecific with the population examined herein. Both females also had 4 pectinal teeth and 9 denticle subrows. If these data are incorporated into the current variation observed within this population (intact finger $n = 105$; DSC = 9, $f = 73.3\%$ (77/105); DSC = 10, $f = 23.8\%$ (25/105); anomaly frequency = 2.9% (3/105), its distinctiveness would become more pronounced. We may test again the last two assumptions and increase the imaginary dataset to 26 specimens. Case 1 (DSC = 9, $n = 7$; DSC = 10, $n = 18$; DSC = 11, $n = 1$): χ^2 test of independence, $p = 7.883e-3$. Case 2 (DSC = 9, $n = 6$; DSC = 10, $n = 19$; DSC = 11, $n = 1$): χ^2 test of independence, $p = 3.212e-3$. Without doubt, the significance would be much greater if the count of 11 subrows turns out to be a common value in *C. tessellatus* (i.e., replaced by the frequency of 9 or 10 in the stimulated dataset).

The supposed disparity in DSC, combined with the loss of the *C. tessellatus* holotype, has led me to provisionally designate this population as a new morphospecies, characterized below. It is surprising that none of the 51 specimens collected near the type locality of *C. tessellatus* showed 11 denticle subrows. If this count originally recorded for *C. tessellatus* was not anomalous but instead characteristic, this new species may be morphologically

justified while showing strong sympatry with that species. Yet, this is based on the assumption that the distinction in a single meristic substantiates heterospecificity, which is doubtful given the highly limited morphospace defined by a small variation interval of discrete values (9–11), though these variables tend to be more definitive than their continuous counterparts (as seen in the current population, which were also independent of the size class). On the flip side, in the event that this new morphospecies proves to be a subjective junior synonym, all descriptions, illustrations, and data presented here can serve as supplementary information for the senior synonym in question. However, I have also been informed that many type specimens collected by M.-S. Zhu lacked coordinate labels, with their localities being estimated retrospectively after the collection (pers. comm., an MHBU staff member). In addition, according to the collector of the new material, they were unable to proceed further south near the political border, where the type locality of *C. tessellatus* is situated. It is likely that no topotypes could be reliably collected for this species, giving rise to its dubious status. In light of these considerations, it seems more compelling to describe this population as a new species, rather than treating the current characterization as a redescription for *C. tessellatus*. Despite claims by previous Chinese authors to have examined 9 specimens, *C. tessellatus* remains a poorly characterized species as no intraspecific variations were documented, even 17 years after its “redescription”. Perhaps, its original describers have chosen to forsake it. It appears that abandoning their poorly described species for years has been a common practice (e. g., the *Olivierus* species from Xinjiang).

It is worth reiterating that the single female paratype (RS8623) deposited in MNHN possessed only three pectinal teeth on each side, reminding me of the “*C. tryznai*” specimens with PTC = 3 reported from the same county (Zhu et al., 2008: 47). Since both the original description and the redescription failed to address intraspecific variation, coupled with the loss of additional type specimens and the absence of plausible topotypes, I contend that determining whether this paratype belongs to *C. tessellatus* is impractical, as it contradicts the species description. Consequently, it would be more prudent to rely solely on the holotype to evaluate the status of this species, and it serves as the standard for comparison with any given material. Furthermore, significant ambiguities surround the other reported specimens, as the authors provided no information beyond their localities. Nevertheless, in the interest of providing more insights, I have compared my Drepung females with the only two photographs of RS8623. It seems that the pedipalp chela carina D_3 is composed of small, random granules in RS8623, in contrast to the large, sublinear granule series seen in the current females. This distinction may also apply to differentiate the holotype of *C. tessellatus* from the current population, provided that the illustration by Zhu et al. (2008: fig. 32) is credible. However, the D_3 they depicted for *C. tessellatus* highly resembles the condition seen in the female *C. tricostatus* examined herein (cf. Figs. 42–43); yet,

Figures 146–149. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., habitus in dorsal (146, 148) and ventral (147, 149), under white light. Figures 146–147. Female holotype. Figures 148–149. Male allotypic paratype. Scale bar = 10 mm.

according to their description, these authors did not consider it obsolete or vestigial (*op. cit.*: 47). This casts doubt on the validity of *C. tessellatus*, as its key discrepancy from *C. tricostatus* lies in the development of D_3 (Yin et al., 2015: tab. 3). The likelihood of *C. tessellatus* holotype representing a female *C. tricostatus* also aligns with the fact that it had 5 pectinal teeth on each side (cf. Fig. 39) and 11 denticle subrows (Table 1). Another notable and possibly diagnostic character is the centro-posteromedian carina (CPM) on the carapace. Similar to other carinae, CPM is characterized by its constitutive granules, varying in their size, number, spacing, and configuration, and can thus be quantified by particle analyses (Tang et al., 2023). This character also appears to be sexually dimorphic in certain species, with females showing more and larger granules (cf. Figs. 22, 30, 78, 86, as well as Kovařík et al. (2018: figs. 41–42), Kovařík (2019: figs. 5–6), and Kovařík et al. (2020: figs. 7, 9)). The phenotypic variability of this character is illustrated in Figs. 154 and 211 for all 9 Drepung females examined, and two additional, presumably conspecific females (Figs. 54, 62) from the same county, Mèdog. In the current population, all Mèdog females had CPM formed by large, lustrous granules, occasionally extending to the posterior marginal sulcus of carapace, alongside relatively large and moderately dense intercarinal and lateral granules. While Qi et al. (2005) and Zhu et al. (2008) provided no clear description for this character, assuming their illustrations were relatively accurate (Qi et al., 2005: fig. 118; Zhu et al., 2008: fig. 31), this does not appear to be the case in the holotype of *C. tessellatus*, yet again mirroring the condition exhibited by the female *C. tricostatus* examined herein (cf. Fig. 38). On the other hand, their distinction from RS8623 is evident, whose CPM are significantly weaker, comprising small, diffuse granules that barely distinguish from the surrounding granulation.

The differentiation between *C. tessellatus* and *C. tricostatus* later emerged in Di et al. (2009: 133), where the first description of female *C. tricostatus* from China was provided. In their dichotomous keys, both species were grouped together by three shared characters: “...Movable finger of pedipalp with 11–12 rows of granules, telson of male and female without sexual dimorphism, manus lacks 1 dorsal carina...”, and distinguished as follows: carapace and tergites are nearly smooth with agranular **dorsal** surface of chelicerae in *C. tessellatus*, whereas all three are granular in *C. tricostatus*. The keys were later recycled in Di et al. (2013: 88) and Di et al. (2014: 14). Di et al. (2009: 137) stated that their identification was based on Kovařík (2000). Indeed, Kovařík (*op. cit.*: 62) mentioned the following features for *C. tricostatus*: “...The carapace is...densely (the ZMUH female) covered by granules...The chelicerae are also granulated...The mesosoma is granulated...” However, the female Drepung specimens examined herein suggest that the apparent carapace granulation density may be somewhat unstable, partially due to their varying size (Fig. 211); though, density is, by strict definition, a ratio of number of entities to a given surface area. Di et al. (2009) implied that both *C. tessellatus* and *C. tricostatus* lack one carina on the

dorsal surface of chelal manus, most likely pertaining to D_3 as earlier speculated. If this is the case, the paratype RS8623 housed at MNHN must be heterospecific with *C. tessellatus*, which hence raises doubts about the identification of other purported specimens of this species. The dichotomous keys in Kovařík (2012: 3) partitioned the two species at No. 24 by the number of chelal carinae (recycled in Kovařík & Ojanguren-Affilastro (2013: 132–133)), indicating that *C. tessellatus* (dichotomy Nos. 24→25→26→27→31) possesses all chelal carinae, presumably based on the paratype photograph. Intriguingly, in his dissertation, Di (2009: 98) dichotomized the two species as follows (translated herein from Chinese): (1) *C. tessellatus*: pedipalp movable finger with 11 rows of oblique teeth, dorsoexternal surface of chelal manus with tessellations formed by fine granules (though, in Di et al. (2009: 136), he also described similarly for *C. tricostatus*: “...entire tegument of chela manus densely covered with coarse granules, forming some indistinct reticular pattern...”); (2) *C. tricostatus*: pedipalp movable finger with 10–12 rows of oblique teeth, pedipalp chela lacking one dorsal carina and one internal carina (six carinae in total). However, in his more detailed description for *C. tessellatus* (*op. cit.*: 106), he did mention the reduction of D_3 , which is finely granular and not convex. This basically nullified his dichotomous keys. Identical characterizations were unsurprisingly recycled in another dissertation by Sun (2010: 101, 107). Bewilderingly, in the latest Chinese *Chaerilus* study he coauthored, Yin et al. (2015: tab. 3) considered D_3 to be present in *C. tessellatus*. Furthermore, their dichotomous keys (*op. cit.*: 50) reduced the differentiation between *C. tessellatus* and *C. tricostatus* to mere discrepancies in carapace and tergite granulation. The herein examined female *C. tricostatus* from Mèdog County showed clearly granulated cheliceral manus (Fig. 212; albeit to a lesser degree than the Drepung specimens), but its carapace and tergites were indeed subgranular (Figs. 36–38). Based solely on the keys provided by Di et al. (2009: 133), this specimen thus presents an intermediate morphological state between the two species in question. A plausible explanation for the discordance is that Di et al. (2009) may have misinterpreted the descriptions by Qi et al. (2005: 30) and Zhu et al. (2008: 47), both of whom stated, “...Chelicerae...smooth on **ventral** surface...” Alternatively, the earlier descriptions were erroneous and subsequently amended by Di et al. (2009: 133) by altering “ventral” to “dorsal”. The true account remains enshrouded, as no photographs were provided, and the type specimen is lost. It is likely that *C. tessellatus* could be instead distinguished from *C. tricostatus* based on carapace and tergite granulations, provided that there is a clear distinction (i.e., no gradient) between the two species in terms of granule density. However, a differentiation based on this single character is highly doubtful. Since the species characterization of *C. tessellatus* is imbued with self-contradictions, I have opted to identify this specimen as *C. tricostatus*, a species named prior to *C. tessellatus*. Whether it represents a junior synonym of *C. tricostatus* remains dubious at present. If that turns out to be the truth, the current Drepung population would be definitively distinct from *C. tessellatus*.

Dimensions (mm)		<i>Chaerilus herta</i> sp. n.	
		♀ HT	♂ PT
Carapace	L / W	6.83 / 7.1	6.9 / 7.09
Mesosoma	L	ca. 15.29	ca. 15.24
Tergite VII	L / W	3.02 / 6.41	2.63 / 6.22
Metasoma + telson	L	26.64	30.91
Segment I	L / W / D	2.67 / 3.99 / 2.85	3.41 / 4.02 / 2.95
Segment II	L / W / D	3.25 / 3.41 / 2.61	3.85 / 3.45 / 2.62
Segment III	L / W / D	3.39 / 3.19 / 2.54	4.04 / 3.2 / 2.51
Segment IV	L / W / D	3.72 / 2.89 / 2.39	4.51 / 2.94 / 2.4
Segment V	L / W / D	6.62 / 2.57 / 2.19	7.53 / 2.53 / 2.14
Telson	L / W / D	6.99 / 2.51 / 2.21	7.57 / 2.68 / 2.27
Pedipalp	L	24.27	28.48
Femur	L / W	6.06 / 2.51	7 / 2.6
Patella	L / W	5.8 / 2.93	6.57 / 2.64
Chela	L	12.41	14.91
Manus	L / W / D	7.17 / 4.21 / 4.68	9.06 / 4.63 / 4.78
Fixed Finger	L	5.24	5.85
Movable finger	L	7.39	8.37
Total	L	ca. 48.76	ca. 53.05
PTC	Left / Right	4 / 4	5 / 6

Table 3. Measurements of *Chaerilus herta* sp. n. Abbreviations: holotype (HT), allotypic paratype (AT), length (L), width (W, in carapace it corresponds to posterior width), depth (D). Pedipalp length excludes trochanter length.

Systematics

Chaerilidae Pocock, 1893

Chaerilus Simon, 1877

Chaerilus herta sp. n.

(Figures 52–67, 146–210; Table 3)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2F4C89D9-914B-487A-BDCD-3CDF125877F8>

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Drepung Township, from Dergong Village (29°10'45.0"N 95°08'28.6"E; 1702 m a. s. l.) to Gelin Village (29°10'57.7"N 95°08'50.7"E; 1668 m a. s. l.); VT.

TYPE MATERIAL. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Drepung Township, from Dergong Village (29°10'45.0"N 95°08'28.6"E; 1702 m a. s. l.) to Gelin Village (29°10'57.7"N 95°08'50.7"E; 1668 m a. s. l.), June 2024, 1♀ (holotype), 40♂8♀, 2 juv. ♀ (paratypes), leg. AC.

ADDITIONAL MATERIAL. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Drepung Township, Dergong Village (29°10'45.0"N 95°08'28.6"E; 1702 m a. s. l.), June 2024, 1♂ (PTC -/5) 1♀ (PTC 4/4), leg. AC [in 95% ethanol when received, now in 99% ethanol; not examined in detail due to rigidity, will be sent to Czech Republic (FKCP) for molecular analysis]; Mêdog County, June 2024, 2♀, purchased dried specimens, allegedly from a recent expedition to this county, collector unknown (Figs. 52–67).

ETYMOLOGY. The specific epithet is a noun in apposition, referring to the extraordinary female scientist “Herta” from the game *Honkai: Star Rail*. The name is presumably derived from the German goddess “Nerpuz”, meaning “power, vitality, force”, herein alluding to the robustness in both sexes of the new species and the evolutionary tenacity of this genus. The transliterated name of Herta in Chinese (黑塔; hēi tǎ) directly translates to “black tower”, denoting the dark coloration of the new species. Chinese equivalent: 黑塔寇里蝎.

DIAGNOSIS. TL ca. 41–53 mm for ♂ and 44–49 mm for ♀. General color dark reddish to brownish black, pectines yellowish brown. Two pairs of lateral ocelli and one pair of median ocelli. Carapace and tergites granular; CAM slightly concave, or straight, or slightly convex; sternite III–VI smooth, VII granular (except for the anteromedian region) and often bicarinate (coarser and barely tetracarinate in ♀). Metasoma I–V with complete carinae 10-8-8-8-7; median lateral carinae on II–IV restricted to the distal 1/2–1/3. Male telson not strongly elongated. PTC 5–6 in ♂ and 4–5 (rarely 5) in ♀. VADC of cheliceral movable/fixed fingers ca. 6–10/5–7 (pooled range of holotype ♀ and allotypic paratype ♂). Pedipalp chela typically sexually dimorphic, elongated in males (size-correlated), ChL/W (left-right averaged) ca. 3.21–3.92 in ♂ and 2.85–3.22 in ♀; manus with D_1 , D_{3-5} , and $V_{1,3}$ pronounced and granular, *E* obsolete, *I* distally incomplete; DSC of movable finger 9–10, dorsal edge of movable finger straight.

Figures 150–151. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., female holotype, prosoma and mesosoma in dorsal (150) and ventral (151) views, under white light. Scale bar = 5 mm (Fig. 150).

CURRENT ASSESSMENT OF TAXONOMIC VALIDITY. Inconclusive until female topotypes of *C. tessellatus* with a DSC of 11 and a PTC of 5 are available for morphological and molecular analyses; or, valid, if *C. tessellatus* truly lacks D_3 (whether conspecific with *C. tricostatus* or not). The holotype of the new species is designated as female to allow for direct comparison with the holotype of *C. tessellatus* if the latter is ever rediscovered.

DESCRIPTION. Based on the holotype ♀ (Figs. 146–147), and the allotypic paratype male is illustrated in Figs. 148–149, 152–153, 157–159, 169–177, 182–185, 190–192, 198–201. Description for the coloration is omitted as the specimen was preserved in ethanol, albeit lacking pronounced discoloration. All structures were photographed under white light as prolonged UV exposure would further decrease the relatively weak fluorescence in this species, but with additional UV fluorescence imaging applied to the pedipalp movable finger. Metasoma of the holotype female and allotypic paratype male were straightened by inserting a thin needle running through all segments to facilitate photography, which caused exudates at the anus in Figs. 191–192. Detailed structures taken under white light were placed on a grey background to clearly reveal the numerous white, fluorescent setae.

Prosoma (Figs. 150–151, 154, 178–179). One pair of median ocelli situated on a rounded ocular tubercle, lacking interocular sulcus; one pair of Type 2A lateral ocelli (each with a pair of MLMa and PLMa); an amber-colored eyespot present underneath PLMa. Carapace isosceles trapezoid in shape, with distinctly increased width posteriorly; anterior margin essentially straight; surface coarsely granular, moderate granules concentrated anteriorly, enlarged granules constitute a pair of oblique carinae extending medially to posteriorly; two pairs of symmetrical, agranular sulci present anterior and posterior to median ocelli; posterolateral surfaces with larger agranular patches. Coxapophyses I distolaterally expanded and angular; sternum pentagonal with a posterior depression. Chelicerae dorsally granular with dark reticulation, a cluster of thick, long setae present at the base of fixed finger; ventrally densely hirsute, setae thick, long, curved, covering the median area of manus and extending to both fingers; basal denticle absent on the left fixed finger but present on the right.

Mesosoma (Figs. 150–151, 155–156). Tergites densely adorned by fine granules, slightly enlarge posteriorly; symmetrical agranular patches present, variable in shape and coverage; all tergites lack discernable carinae. Genital operculum bipartite, genital papillae absent; pectinal plate with highly convex posterior margin; pectines small, with unpartitioned lamella, well-developed fulcra, and large teeth. Pleural membrane covered with infusate, punctiform microsclerites. Sternites III–IV essentially smooth but matte, except for a few emergent subtle granules present medially to posteriorly, lateral and posterior margins covered by both fluorescent and non-fluorescent setae; sternite V posteriorly with a smooth, reflective, biconvex area; sternite VII granular except for the medial to anterior regions,

with a pair of internal carinae formed by enlarged granules; spiracles small and circular.

Metasoma and telson (Figs. 186–189). *Metasoma*: Sparsely hirsute and granular; segments I–V with 10-8-8-8-7 complete, serrated carinae, formed by enlarged, discrete granules; median lateral carinae partially present distally on II–IV; ventromedian carina distally bifurcate on V; lateral and ventral intercarinal surfaces granular, dorsal surface essentially smooth; anal arch strongly arcuate with extended and flared lateral lobes armed by large, sharp granules. *Telson*: Pyriform and subgranular, with fluorescent microsetae; lateral surfaces of vesicle with a shallow, wide sulcus; vesicle distinctly tappers distally; aculeus smooth and weakly curved.

Pedipalps (Figs. 160–168, 180–181). *Femur*: Essentially with 3 discernable carinae formed by large, discrete granules (retrodorsal, retroventral, proventral), prodorsal carina obscured by prolateral granules; retrodorsal and retroventral carinae proximally internal to a short articular carina; dorsal and ventral surfaces granular, retrolateral surface smooth; 5 and 4 trichobothria on dorsal and retrolateral surfaces. *Patella*: Essentially with 7 discernable carinae formed by large, discrete granules (prodorsal, dorsomedian, retrodorsal, retromedian, retroventral, proventral, promedian), granules larger on retroventral and proventral carinae; prodorsal and retrodorsal carinae distally incomplete, dorsomedian carina proximally incomplete; intercarinal surfaces finely and sparsely granular; dorsal surface with a pronounced distal depression; 3 (*id*, d_{1-2}), 7 (*est*₁₋₂, *esb*, eb_{1-2} , *em*, *et*) and 4 (v_{1-3} , *iv*) trichobothria on dorsal, retrolateral, and ventral surfaces, trichobothrium *id* anterior to prodorsal carina. *Chela*: All 7 carinae (D_1 , D_{3-5} , *E*, $V_{1,3}$, *I*) present but vary in development degree; granules forming D_1 , D_{3-4} , and $V_{1,3}$ larger, flatter, and more continuous; *E* obsolete, formed by small, random granules; *I* fades out distally; intercarinal surfaces finely granular dorsally, externally and internally, weaker ventrally; 3 (*Eb*₃, *db*, *dt*), 8 (Eb_{1-2} , *Est*, *Et*, *eb*, *esb*, *est*, *et*), 1 (*V*) and 2 (*ib*, *it*) trichobothria on dorsal, external, ventral, and internal surfaces; dorsal edge of movable finger without proximal lobe.

Legs (Figs. 194–197). All legs essentially acarinate, sparsely and finely granular; tibial spur absent; tarsomeres with sparse dorsal but dense ventral setae. *Basitarsus*: A retrolateral row of robust spinules present on I–II, reduced in number on III, absent on IV; a ventromedian row of thinner, denser spinules present I–II (flanked bilaterally by two rows of setae), reduced in number on III–IV; a pair of long pedal spurs present on all legs. *Telotarsus*: a ventromedian row of short spinules present on all legs, flanked bilaterally by two rows of setae. *Apotele*: Tarsal unguis stout and curved; dactyl weakly developed.

MEASUREMENTS. See Table 3. Measurements for the mesosoma are largely approximate.

ONTOGENETIC VARIATIONS. The larger immature female displayed a somewhat tetracarinate sternite VII, distinguishable by the stronger fluorescence of the enlarged granules and its relatively

Figures 152–153. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., male allotypic paratype, prosoma and mesosoma in dorsal (152) and ventral (153) views, under white light. Scale bar = 5 mm (Fig. 152).

Figures 154–159. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., carapace (154, 157), pectines (155, 158) and sternite VII (156, 159), under white light. **Figures 154–156.** Female holotype. **Figures 157–159.** Male allotypic paratype. Scale bars = 5 mm (Figs. 154, 157), 2 mm (Figs. 155–156, 158–159).

Figures 160–168. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., female holotype, pedipalp chela in dorsal (160), external (161) and ventral (162) views, patella in dorsal (163), external (164) and ventral (165) views, femur in dorsal (166), external (167) and ventral (168) views, under white light. Scale bar = 10 mm.

smooth surface (Fig. 206). This observation likely suggests that the bauplan of sternite VII in female *C. herta* sp. n. may inherently be tetracarinate, though in adults, the external pair appears obscured by the more developed peripheral granules.

AFFINITIES. Since this population has already been thoroughly examined and compared in the preceding sections, the following discussion will be concise and based solely on the summarized data in Table 1. Overall, a combination of PTC 5–6 in ♂ and 4–5 in ♀, DSC 9–10, and well-developed D_3 is exclusive across the Chinese congeners. The macroscopic morphology and dark coloration place it closely to *C. tricostatus* (cf. Figs. 36–43 and Di et al., 2009: figs. 1–2).

The PTC range in both sexes associates this species with *C. assamensis* (and *C. dibangvalleycus*), *C. pictus*, *C. tessellatus*, and *C. tricostatus*. It can be distinguished from *C. assamensis* (and *C. dibangvalleycus*), *C. pictus*, and *C. tessellatus* by its consistently intermediate DSC. Between males, it can also be differentiated from *C. pictus* by its short telson. From *C. tricostatus*, it differs by its well-developed D_3 . Distinctions in D_3 and CPM from *C. tessellatus* remain indeterminate.

The lower bound in its DSC range associates it with *C. pseudoconchiformus*, from which it can be differentiated by a notably larger body size, slightly higher female PTC, and carinate sternite VII in females. The upper bound associates it with *C. tricostatus*, which has been compared above.

Figures 169–177. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., male allotypic paratype, pedipalp chela in dorsal (169), external (170) and ventral (171) views, patella in dorsal (172), external (173) and ventral (174) views, femur in dorsal (175), external (176) and ventral (177) views, under white light. Scale bar = 10 mm.

Figures 178–185. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., chelicerae in dorsal (178, 182) and ventral (179, 183) views under white light, and left (180, 184) and right (181, 185) movable fingers under UV light. **Figures 178–181.** Female holotype. **Figures 182–185.** Male allotypic paratype. Denticle abbreviations: *dd* = dorsal distal, *vd* = ventral distal, *d* = distal, *sd* = subdistal, *m* = median, *b* = basal, *va* = ventral accessory (only several discernible ones in the figure are indicated). Scale bars = 2 mm (Figs. 178, 182).

Figures 186–193. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., metasoma and telson in dorsal (186, 190), lateral (187, 191) and ventral (188, 192) views, telson in lateral view (189, 193). **Figures 186–189.** Female holotype. **Figures 190–193.** Male allotypic paratype; inset: metasoma II in dorsal view. Carina abbreviations: *dsm* = dorsosubmedian, *dl* = dorsolateral, *ml* = median lateral, *vl* = ventrolateral, *vsm* = ventrosubmedian, *vm* = ventromedian. Scale bars = 10 mm (Figs. 186–188, 190–192), 2 mm (Figs. 189, 193).

The well-developed D_3 associates it with all Chinese congeners except *C. mainlingensis* and *C. tricostatus* (and possibly *C. dibangvalleyicus*). Among the remaining species not previously compared, namely *C. conchiformus*, *C. tryznai*, and *C. wrzecionkoi*, it can be most confidently distinguished by different chela morphology, consistently higher DSC, and carinate sternite VII in females, respectively.

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from the type locality, likely extends to Arunachal Pradesh. However, a recent observation by my friend Tongtong (iNaturalist obs. ID = 196900794; 29°19'30.8"N 95°19'58.9"E) suggests the presence of a presumably conspecific male—identified by its pronounced D_3 carina—just 1 km from the *C. tricostatus* population documented by Di et al. (2009: 133). Due to my friend's busy schedule, I have not personally examined this specimen prior to the publication of this paper.

Discussion

Taxonomy is the sword wrought to sever the tangled threads of life's boundless diversity. Though often devalued by other biological disciplines for the typically short half-life of their stability resulting from constant revisions, it remains an indispensable foundation for all further research by offering an empirical but practical guidance that enables people to resolve concrete problems during the preliminary phase. Science as a whole is iterative, and taxonomy's adaptability ensures it reflects the most faithful understanding of biodiversity. Misconceptions arise when the process of scientific refinement is mistaken for unreliability. Accurate classification facilitates more robust investigations into phylogenetic relationships, lineage and phenotypic evolution, biogeographic history, and other

Figures 194–201. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., left legs I–IV in retrolateral view. **Figures 194–197.** Female holotype. **Figures 198–201.** Male allotypic paratype. Scale bars = 5 mm.

Figures 202–210. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., immature female paratypes. **Figure 202.** Dorsal habitus under white light; cross scale bar axis = 10 mm. **Figures 203–204.** Pectines of the smaller (203) and larger (204) females, under white light. **Figures 205–206.** Sternite VII of the larger female, under white (205) and UV (206) lights. **Figures 207–210.** Left and right pedipalp movable fingers of the smaller (207–208) and larger (209–210) females, under UV light.

enduring fields of study. What forges its blade is not solely the steel in the name of concepts and methodologies, but the relentless strike of logical critique—the anvil and hammer that shape and sharpen its edge. In an era where scholars hasten to leverage newly emerged means to divide the lineage of species, wisdom bids us pause, to peer beneath the veneer of innovation, to weigh the hidden presumptions and veiled biases that may mar the precision of our craft (e. g., Tarkhnishvili (2024), which I recommend reading). Since further molecular investigations are warranted for the genus *Chaerilus*—which lie beyond my capacity in the current work, being an independent researcher—in the first half of the following discourse, I shall provide a literature review based on several outstanding studies recently conducted by colleagues in other fields. The aim is to foster a more rigorous taxonomic mindset among our fellow scorpionologists.

Species delimitation

In an ideal scenario, species studied for comparison would be true, basic units of biodiversity. However, in practice, taxonomists rely on nominal species they identified and named—empirical approximations that represent a hypothetical model of how biodiversity is structured (Vences et al., 2024). This results in a current catalog of organisms that is inherently preliminary, incomplete, and continually evolving as our understanding of taxonomy advances. Despite ongoing debates surrounding species concepts (de Queiroz, 2007), there is general agreement that species represent segments of population-level lineages with distinct, independent, and irreversible evolutionary trajectories. Various operational criteria have been developed for species identification, focusing on biological traits like interfertility

Figure 211. *Chaerilus herta* sp. n., centro-posteromedian carinae (CPM) on the carapace of all 8 adult female paratypes (F2–9; ordered →↓), under white light.

(biological species), monophyly (phylogenetic species), conspecific recognition, phenotypic cohesion, and ecological niche differentiation. However, species delimitation, the process of determining whether a single or multiple species exist within a presumed lineage, remains a contentious issue, arising from differing ontological perspectives on the term “species” and the methods used to integrate and assess data. The ambiguity of species boundaries within the continuous process of speciation, shaped by factors like gene flow and reproductive isolation, further complicates this process. While strict biological species criteria align with full reproductive isolation, the definition has already broadened to include cases of “substantial but not necessarily complete reproductive isolation” (Coyne & Orr, 2004) as hybrid zones exist in reality.

The fundamental lack of consensus on species definition and delimitation, coupled with practical limitations (e. g., available specimens and techniques), has conventionally led to the predominant but often problematic presupposition that “different morphologies justify different species”. While applicable in many cases, it is not validated as a universal rule and has been increasingly challenged. Phenotypic plasticity, polymorphism, and cryptic species (underrepresent genome-level diversification exhibiting minimal morphological differences) highlight the limitations of relying on morphology alone (Wu et al., 2018). The subjectivity in selecting and interpreting diagnostic characters can also contribute to over- or underestimation of diversity, meaning that hypothesized morphospecies under this presumption do not necessarily represent natural evolutionary entities. Therefore, a more integrative approach is

warranted, combining morphological, ethological, ecological, biogeographical, and molecular data to substantiate species distinctiveness (e. g., Monjaraz-Ruedas et al., 2023).

One obvious question arises: what motivated the ancestral population to develop different morphologies? Most phylogenetic analyses have seldom explored the mechanisms underlying genomic differentiation that led to phenotypic divergence or species boundaries. In other words, spatial, temporal, and environmental data should be integrated to assess species delimitation and speciation processes, as ecological speciation (genetic divergence driven by adaptation to different environments, even in the absence of geographic isolation) or secondary contact in the ecotones (where incompletely reproductively isolated but formerly allopatric and genetically distinct lineages interact with each other while maintaining species boundaries despite the presence of gene flow, with selection acting against introgression of certain alleles) could be a main driver of biodiversity (Burbrink et al., 2024). Few taxonomic studies have addressed this issue, likely due to several factors: (1) lack of awareness among authors, many taxonomists remain entrenched in traditional morphological or phylogenetic paradigms; (2) limited data on the target species, either due to reliance on museum specimens or the collection of only a few individuals which have mostly been euthanized; and (3) insufficient funding and time for more comprehensive investigations of wild populations. Take the current taxa as an example: *Chaerilus herta* **sp. n.** differs from its closest morphological and geographical relative, *C. tricostatus*, by possessing a complete D_3 carina. What role does this carina play in the animal's life history and why is it absent in *C. tricostatus*? Could it be because its absence compromises the geometric stability of the chela the least? Why do the two species occur almost sympatrically yet primarily differ in D_3 and DSC? These two morphological distinctions seem empirically robust and reliable for the morphological species delimitation in this genus, but why? Are these simply results of stochastic gene expressions? In some cases, different morphologies can be explained on a bionomic basis. However, the carina, a diverse, crucial, and useful morphosculpture, has rarely been investigated for its ecological significance. Suppose *C. herta* **sp. n.** and *C. tricostatus* indeed share a most recent common ancestor, with chelal muscles and finger denticles playing paramount roles in predation. If this specific carina does not serve a critical ecological function, could its absence be attributed to a superficially random collateral loss of its controlling gene, resulting from a mutation in another gene governing the expression of an ecologically significant phenotypic trait (i.e., genetic pleiotropy), such as DSC? Conversely, could the increase in DSC in *C. tricostatus* be a consequence of the absence of D_3 , assuming that additional carinae enhance muscle attachment within the chela (pending verifications through anatomical studies), thus necessitating compensation for any carina loss through an increase in denticles on the finger? Nonetheless, the consistent and conspicuous phenotypic hiatus in chelal carinae—empirically appearing to be a relatively conservative (hence reliable)

diagnostic character—and marginally overlapping DSC for all currently examined and previously reported *C. herta* **sp. n.** and *C. tricostatus* specimens, seem to vindicate them as two distinct and non-merging taxa within the same geographic range. On the other hand, the present study further demonstrated the limited utility and uncertainty in other morphological characters used for distinguishing *Chaerilus* species, with measurement inconsistencies impacting ratiometric interspecific thresholds. While morphological polymorphism beyond color variations is relatively rare in scorpions, the diagnostic criteria employed for species delimitation still require a good empirical reference. Many contemporary taxonomic works in scorpology continue to rely solely on morphology, which may either stem from a lack of awareness or practical constraints. In such case, taxonomists ought to weigh the significance of perceived differences rather than their mere existence when making decisions. The focus hence shifts toward determining stable thresholds and applying quantitative methods, such as multivariate analyses, to assess the robustness of these differences. Perhaps the least biased approach is to apply unsupervised clustering to raw morphological data without assigning prior groupings, thereby eschewing undue rationalization of previously recognized species. Yet, rigorous quantitative methods with nuanced considerations are often overlooked in scorpion taxonomy, leading to piles of confusions pending clarification. Nevertheless, placing over-reliance on the resultant statistics while ignoring other factors may lead to committing the McNamara fallacy. Taxonomy, after all, is predominantly empirical.

“Taxonomic Rashomon Effect (TRE)”, a concept tangentially introduced in the current paper, gives rise partially to the inconsistencies between different taxonomic works, which is particularly pronounced in those based solely on the morphology. This concept differs from more specific categories such as observer bias or confirmation bias, in that it does not assume subjective preferences stemming from a directional subconsciousness. Qualitative descriptions, in the absence of any reference system, are especially susceptible to such subjective bias. Based on my personal acquaintance with the morphological studies of scorpions, I believe this effect is, to some extent, tied to the epistemological evolution of the practitioner over the course of their research career. In essence, this dynamic reflects an “iterative update” in their subjective definitions of qualitative features for specific morphological characters. With the researcher's exposure to more taxa, the original boundaries between qualitative categories are often challenged, necessitating redefinitions based on newly acquired information. This may lead to the discordance between two works by the same author (“intra-author inconsistency”). A more problematic scenario involves the differing opinions between the author and their audience. As authors gain experience, their ability (“intuition”) to detect minor morphological differences becomes enhanced, enabling them to identify what they believe to be interspecific variation that may be overlooked by another party, who is

Figure 212. Adult female *Chaerilus tricostatus* (=? *C. tessellatus*; same as in Figs. 36–43), dorsal surface of chelicerae (pulled out), under white light.

less experienced. Often, the non-taxonomist audience may fail to perceive these claimed differences, causing difficulties in specimen identification. This hence creates an imbalance between the taxonomic information provided and its practical utility for end-users. Non-taxonomists struggle often with such traits for their lack of training in recognizing minute morphological distinctions, or practical requirements to examine certain characters. More frequently, the problem is complicated by the dearth of visual references in those papers. Even when both parties are experienced taxonomists, TRE remains a significant factor that results in disputes among authors (“inter-author disagreement”). In some cases, the morphological differences perceived by earlier researchers may have been exaggerated due to their heightened detection ability. The reliability of these perceived differences often lacks persuasive substantiation, either due to the absence of visual references or quantitative methods. However, this does not necessarily mean that the earlier authors had erroneously overestimated the differences in reality. TRE, as a form of

subjective bias, persists because of the diverse epistemological trajectories among taxonomists, culminating in their own unique definitions applied during species characterization. For some authors, accumulated experience may instead caution them against placing too much weight on minor morphological differences (“vibes”) that others might emphasize.

The advent of DNA-based methods, leveraging molecular biology and bioinformatics, offer potential to overcome the various obstacles in morphological taxonomy. However, single-locus approaches, such as mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase I (COI) barcoding, come with limitations (Tang et al., 2024b). These markers, often organellar, can be misleading due to phenomena like hybridization or ancestral polymorphism, resulting in cytonuclear discordance. Additionally, these methods typically sample only a small portion of the genome, restricting the ability to test taxonomic hypotheses comprehensively (Vences et al., 2024). Multiple genomic studies have revealed that mitochondrial phylogenies and barcodes can misrepresent phylogeographical diversity, with

issues like mitochondrial “ghost” lineages (highly divergent mitogroups not matching nuclear genome differentiation) or mitochondrial capture (species with foreign mtDNA from past hybridization) skewing results. As no single universal genetic marker exists for species delimitation, combining multigenomic data (nuclear, organellar, and genomic) alongside non-molecular data is recommended (but see Tarkhnishvili (2024)). High-throughput sequencing allows for a more complete genetic analysis based on a plethora of markers throughout the genome, improving our understanding of genealogical relationships and enabling more accurate species delimitation closer to the biological reality. However, this logically leads to another conundrum: whether differences in genetic profiles or other characteristics truly authenticate heterospecificity. At present, it remains an unresolved dilemma. Pragmatists may argue that any taxonomic concept functions as an ontological unit only designed to facilitate our understanding of the world—a simplified, inherently anthropocentric symbol. Seeking true objectivity in taxonomy reflecting the essence of what humans call as “species” may require perfection of more fundamental and intrinsic (as currently perceived) fields, such as mathematics and physics. Despite this, taxonomy should strive for robustness whenever possible to provide a reliable foundation for fields and human activities that rely on it. Put it differently, rigor is necessary but excessive pedantry is uncalled for. This leads to our critiques of molecular biology.

DNA-based species inference largely relies on distinguishing between intraspecific and interspecific genetic variation with predefined thresholds (barcode gap). To recognize this gap, studies must include adequate sampling to capture sufficient intraspecific genetic variation. An integrative framework would combine various lines of evidence, including alternative delimitation methods (e. g., threshold-based, character-based, tree-based, and coalescence-based approaches). Factors intrinsic to species and assemblages, such as fluctuating effective population sizes and the rarity of species, may significantly impact species inference. Haplotype data has been proposed as an unbiased, more objective measure for biodiversity. A haplotype-based approach, independent of species concepts or delimitation methods, is increasingly used in ecological and metabarcoding studies (Ranasinghe et al., 2023). It has proven effective for exploring macroecological patterns in poorly understood biota and predicting large-scale biodiversity using haplotype diversity as a proxy for genetic and species diversity. However, while haplotypes are products of divergence and species often carry multiple haplotypes (or even exhibit heteroplasmy), species patterns are shaped by processes like dispersal, inheritance, introgression, and recombination, which vary in intensity over time and space. Therefore, the concept of species encompasses more complex and integrative meanings than simple diversity measures such as the number of molecular operational taxonomic units (MOTUs).

While genetical species identification is increasingly popular for biodiversity assessments, conflicts among different molecular species delimitation approaches are common and

comparative studies to detect these conflicts and their impacts remain rare. The particular delimitation method selected significantly affects species richness estimates. Methods such as metabarcoding, which use distance-based clustering algorithms for species circumscription, are sensitive to parameter variations. The choice of clustering threshold—typically 3% pairwise distance, or 2% for similar taxa—can significantly impact taxonomic inferences, introducing biases that inflate or deflate diversity estimates. A recent study by Ranasinghe et al. (2023) on phytophagous scarab beetles from Sri Lanka revealed high incongruence in the number of MOTUs derived from different delimitation methods (PTP, TCS, ASAP), ranging from 82 to 129. None of these methods perfectly matched prior morphospecies assignments (101), and the assemblage composition between haplotypes at diverse spatial levels showed substantial dissimilarity. Although the operational entities (haplotypes, morphospecies, MOTUs) between the full assemblage and the cumulative subclade analyses aligned within each species delimitation approach, they differed strongly across methods and from morphospecies assignments. Variations in delimitation results are particularly sensitive to recently separated or currently diverging populations, revealing them as slightly divergent genetic clusters. Morphospecies, with certain characters often evolving more rapidly than mitochondrial DNA due to strong selection, may lead to more clearly defined clusters compared to haplotype-based analysis; in one of my previous studies, a new species was recognized based on consistent morphological disparities, despite a low genetic distance from its closest relative (Tang et al., 2024). Additionally, the absence of a universal genetic threshold for species delimitation complicates the matter, as the barcode gap can vary significantly across taxa. Using a fixed threshold across species with different evolutionary histories may either overestimate or underestimate species diversity.

Multispecies coalescent (MSC)-based methods, which assume no gene flow and hybridization between putative species, face challenges because both are pervasive in nature and can affect species tree topology. The number and type of loci used in these methods also impact the results. Including more loci but fewer individuals can lead to better-resolved species trees with higher confidence metrics. These methods also assume exhaustive geographic sampling representing nearly all populations, which is often difficult to achieve, and inadequate sampling that omits admixed or intermediate populations may lead to overestimates of species richness. This issue is particularly problematic with isolation by distance, where geographically closer individuals are more genetically related due to limited dispersal. Isolation by distance can vary dramatically across species with different reproductive modes, life histories, and dispersal capacities. In the presence of isolation by distance, MSC-based methods can lead to over-clustering, or the incorrect inference of multiple species. In some cases, support for multispecies scenarios may reflect patterns of population structure or geographic sampling bias, rather than true evolutionary divergence. Mason et al.

	Normality	Skewness	Symmetry	Excess kurtosis	Mesokurtosis
CaL	$p = 0.636$	-0.111	$p = 0.774$	-0.737	$p = 0.331$
Left ChL	$p = 0.457$	-0.024	$p = 0.951$	-0.864	$p = 0.255$
Right ChL	$p = 0.477$	-0.091	$p = 0.814$	-0.848	$p = 0.264$
Left ChW	$p = 0.541$	0.011	$p = 0.978$	-0.755	$p = 0.32$
Right ChW	$p = 0.392$	0.298	$p = 0.442$	-0.602	$p = 0.427$

Table 4. Shapiro-Wilk test on the raw dataset of the five continuous variables.

(2020) assessed the sensitivity of MSC-based methods to violations of their assumptions and found that the inclusion or exclusion of genetically intermediate individuals at a single site can significantly affect support for either multispecies or single-species delimitation. Inadequate intraspecific sampling, particularly in continuously distributed populations, can lead to overestimates of species richness if intermediate individuals are overlooked. Such biases may be mitigated when populations are clearly classified *a priori* using subspecific taxonomy, phenotypic variation, or allopatric distributions. Similarly, in their elaborate and critical molecular study, Burriel-Carranza et al. (2023) proposed three potential scenarios of cryptic lineage segregation (3–5 species) within *Trachydactylus hajarensis* (Arnold, 1980) (Squamata: Gekkonidae). However, when applying the genealogical divergence index, none of the lineages were validated. High levels of mito-nuclear discordance were also observed across different delimitation methodologies, likely resulting from introgression.

Joshi et al. (2024) noted that geographically widespread taxa pose significant challenges for species delimitation, especially those with allopatric populations. The observed inter-population difference could indeed be a result of adaptations to different ecological and environmental conditions. However, these populations often exhibit substantial intraspecific variability due to restricted gene flow, which may present genetic divergence that is misinterpreted as species-level divergence, especially when employing MSC-based methods. The gradual differentiation of allopatric populations creates a “gray zone”, subjectivizing taxonomic delimitation. The authors accentuated the need for genomic approaches and multiple genetic markers to accurately assess genetic relationships, emphasizing that reliance on mitochondrial DNA alone may be misleading. Vences et al. (2024) further focused on secondary contact zones where previously allopatric lineages meet and potentially hybridize. These zones are crucial for evolutionary and taxonomic studies, as they test reproductive barriers and reveal whether genetic admixing occurs freely or is limited by these barriers. Their study highlighted the use of hybridization metrics, such as hybrid indices, ancestry coefficients, and allele frequencies, often modeled with sigmoid clines. Wide clines suggest weak reproductive barriers, while narrow clines indicate stronger selection against hybrids. These findings are essential for determining whether lineages represent distinct species or subspecies, based on genetic and reproductive divergence.

Both studies advocate for genomic approaches, accentuating that species delimitation is context-dependent, requiring meticulous interpretation of genetic data across spatial and ecological gradients. Together, they underscore the role of isolation, hybridization, and gene flow in shaping taxonomic boundaries.

The fact that both molecular and morphological distinctions serve merely as indirect arguments of true evolutionary lineages that have reached an irreversible stage of divergence from their closest relatives further stresses the inherently subjective, preliminary, and potentially flawed nature of many taxonomic conclusions. Taxonomic workflows face challenges due to a lack of integrative frameworks to support decisions about whether lineages represent populations, subspecies, or species. High sampling efforts, bioinformatics skills, and the costs of DNA sequencing and laboratory equipment present significant barriers, particularly for traditional alpha-taxonomists, whose numbers are steadily declining. Ranasinghe et al. (2023) suggested that morphospecies are particularly valuable due to their extensive global reference system based on morphology, which offers strong potential for universal and scalable application in approaches utilizing artificial intelligence in combination with molecular data (e. g., Karbstein et al., 2024). Finally, as a personal reflection, I surmise that *reductio ad absurdum* could serve as a valuable ideological perspective in species delimitation. If one were to attempt collapsing previously recognized species into a single species or at least reducing their number, failure to do so would logically validate their heterospecificity. The same underlying principle forms the foundation of statistical testing, yet the potential for extending its application is undeniable.

Scorpiology in China

On another related topic, I contend that it is imperative for the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN) to consider the establishment of a rule whereby insufficiently described senior synonyms—those whose proposed differential characters are either of dubious reliability or lack support through photographic or statistical evidence—should not automatically be granted naming priority in the presence of a well-defined junior subjective synonym. Taxonomy must uphold a sense of responsibility to prevent subpar works that needlessly complicate future studies. For

Reshuffled dataset	1	2	3	4	5
Canonical correlation	0.396	0.291	0.229	0.452	0.321
Wilks' Lambda Λ	0.843	0.915	0.948	0.796	0.897
χ^2	5.539	2.875	1.743	7.433	3.531
p	0.354	0.719	0.883	0.190	0.619
Reshuffled dataset	6	7	8	9	10
Canonical correlation	0.473	0.430	0.308	0.506	0.277
Wilks' Lambda Λ	0.777	0.815	0.905	0.744	0.923
χ^2	8.216	6.631	3.249	9.618	2.595
p	0.145	0.250	0.662	0.087	0.762

Table 5. Canonical discriminant analysis results of the 10 reshuffled KMCA-based PD matrix.

any works failing to meet these standards, this regulation implies a denial of their “endeavor”. The introduction of such a regulation would undoubtedly necessitate a meticulous, case-by-case evaluation, underpinned by unambiguous definitions, but its potential application is indisputable. However, it must be emphasized that should a senior synonym have already achieved widespread application and undergone redescription substantiating its validity, it is allowed to retain its priority. In light of this, I propose that this rule should primarily, if not exclusively, apply to works published during the era in which modern technological tools—such as digital cameras—were readily available (e. g., starting from 2000), while also accounting for the significant advancements in our understanding of species variation and delimitation. Indeed, taxonomy is inherently subjective in practice, as it relies on an empirical threshold to define the boundaries between taxa. This introduces subjectivity into what constitutes a “poor” species description, and therefore such taxonomic names should not take precedence. However, arbitrariness differs from subjectivity. A taxonomic decision (e. g., new species proposal) can be considered arbitrary if it lacks a substantiated rationale (based on logic and/or evidence), or discards counterevidence that challenges it. For example, a well-defined species is one supported by ample evidence that demonstrates a high concordance with the author’s reasoning. Failure to provide such support invites doubt about its validity, rendering the species delimitation more likely arbitrary to a third party whose horizon is often circumscribed by the mere, unilateral assertions declared in the paper. In morphological intrageneric comparisons where the uniqueness of the new species is defended, a claim without support is arbitrary, as is one without verifiable evidence—one that would require sophisticated artificial distortion to fabricate verisimilitude and consistency for academic fraud (e. g., detailed photographs). Only arbitrary species proposals that lack sufficient justification should be disregarded. Although the peer-review process is intended to filter out poor descriptions in advance, its quality varies considerably across journals and/or reviewers, particularly in niche fields such as scorpology. Apparently, with the advancements in artificial intelligence, it will only

be even more onerous for ordinary reviewers or readers in the future to detect potential instances of misconduct by authors whose solitary objective is to proliferate the number of species they describe.

The current predicament with Chinese *Chaerilus* species evokes memories of my earlier revision on *Olivierus* from Xinjiang, where a well-illustrated foreign species, *O. tarabaevi* Fet et al., 2021, characterized through an integrative approach, had to be synonymized with a Chinese species described in 2010, *O. longichelus* (Sun & Zhu, 2010), which had been originally described based on merely three juvenile specimens (therefore, the key diagnostic proposed by those authors, ChL/W, was virtually invalid). The same senior author further described two additional conspecific species (*O. bolensis* Sun, Zhu & Lourenço, 2010 and *O. karshius* Sun & Sun, 2011) relying on the erroneous data of that former species, without furnishing any photographic documentation. In the face of poorly described historical species, subsequent taxonomists are compelled to first undertake revisions and/or redescrptions to validate or abrogate these species before progressing with the proposal of new taxa in case raising synonyms, thereby imposing more burdens to their successors. This is particularly laborious, time-consuming, and even financially demanding in certain cases. Moreover, together with practical constraints, such as the availability of materials, this preparatory work often eventually delays more urgent studies. The issue is further compounded in the case of Chinese scorpions by the significant loss of type materials (Tang, 2025: 3), which was again corroborated by my friend who paid a recent visit to the specimen chamber of MHBUS in late January 2025 without discovering any types, but only a meager assortment of random specimens, most without detailed collection information. While some may deem it feasible to relegate these species to *nomina dubia* or *nomina nuda*, uncertainty persists as to the re-emergence of those specimens that remain as a Sword of Damocles, thereby invalidating any subjective junior synonyms. Public museum collections will prove meaningless if they fail to ensure the safe, strict, and long-term preservation of type materials, which is one of the primary reasons I have refrained from designating my holotypes to any museum until

Continuous	Pearson R^2							
	C-L_L	C-L_R	C-W_L	C-W_R	L_L-R	W_L-R	L-W_L	L-W_R
Real data	0.9399	0.9457	0.771	0.7801	0.9946	0.8682	0.8522	0.8202
MCS-data A	0.006716	0.00006104	0.0001828	0.004804	0.0008794	0.03692	0.0003706	0.01884
MCS-data B	0.9606	0.926	0.9846	0.9818	0.97	0.993	0.9704	0.9649
MCS-data C	0.02525	0.01494	0.007304	0.008734	0.007425	0.0005059	0.0007686	0.042
MCS-data D	0.00003353	0.00001553	0.00006204	0.000003397	0.00001588	0.00005881	0.00007528	0.00001302
Binary	Spearman R^2							
	DSC_L vs. DSC_R				PTC_L vs. PTC_R			
Real data	0.1073				0.1056			
MCS-data A	0.01675				0.0005569			
MCS-data B	as above				as above			
MCS-data C	0.006703				0.02145			
MCS-data D	0.0001254				0.000004353			

Table 6. Comparison of correlations between continuous variables for real (reddened) and synthetic data (from Monte Carlo simulations). C-L_L, CaL vs. ChL_L; C-L_R, CaL vs. ChL_R; C-W_L, CaL vs. ChW_L; C-W_R, CaL vs. ChW_R; L_L-R, ChL_L vs. ChL_R; W_L-R, ChW_L vs. ChW_R; L-W_L, ChL_L vs. ChW_L; L-W_R, ChL_R vs. ChW_R.

I have concluded my work in this field. To mitigate this, I unwaveringly proffered numerous visual references for the specimens I examined, which were either included within my publications, or made available in supplementary files. Readers are also welcome to request additional photographs.

Recently, Huber et al. (2024) advocated employing open nomenclature for newly discovered species with dubious identities (alternatively, Tarkhnishvili (2024) suggested the re-adoption of subspecies concept, which is subject to less stringent criteria). They emphasized issues arising when species are described from a single specimen, sex, or locality, as well as from poorly preserved specimens or ambiguous locality data. This is particularly problematic in genera where species exhibit equivocal morphological boundaries, closely paralleling the issues criticized earlier regarding insufficiently characterized species. In all candor, I have also described three new species based on single-female specimens (*Qianxie solegladi* Tang, 2022; *Scorpiops tongtongi* Tang, 2022; *Scorpiops kovariki* Tang et al., 2024). Following the publication of the first species, informal criticisms emerged from Chinese non-scorpionologists regarding its basis on a single female. However, I shall maintain that all decisions were grounded in judicious assessments. The first species, an epigeal member of a family (Pseudochactidae) with only six previously described species scattered across Asia—four of which are obligatory troglobites—exhibited phylogenetically significant morphological distinctions. Moreover, the other two known epigeal species are also geographically disjunct from this new species. A similar taxonomic history surrounds the unique coelacanth, *Latimeria chalumnae* J. L. B. Smith, 1939, also described from a single specimen. Both *Q. solegladi* and *L. chalumnae* are important discoveries representing ancient lineages, and both are markedly distinct from their nearest related taxa (Loria et al., 2022; Xuan et al., 2025). The second case involved the proposal of a new *Scorpiops* species, *S. tongtongi*, following a preliminary review of its congeners, leveraging two years of personal epistemological foundation concerning their morphological variation limit. As argued at the

beginning of this study, a review of closely related congeners is requisite prior to describing any putative new species, particularly when the researcher embodies a neophyte. This approach provides a holistic context for the researcher before delving into specific aspects. In the most recent instance (Tang et al., 2024b), although an integrative approach was employed, the final decision was based on morphological grounds, with the new species being readily distinguishable from all its congeners (see also the supplementary file of that study). Notably, the first species was also represented by an adult male specimen (though merely depicted in dorsal and ventral habitus), which was unfortunately lost (and over the following years there has been no successful collection of any new adult males). For the second species, I promptly supplemented the male description in the next year, accompanied by a further review of its associated congeners. As Huber et al. (2024) noted, descriptions based on single specimens are not inherently unacceptable but carry a heightened risk of misidentifying false new species. In practice, taxonomists must demonstrate a thorough understanding of their target taxa through comprehensive analyses and critical arguments. Supplementary descriptions should be provided as soon as possible. Unfortunately, many poorly described species were left unvisited following their initial description, especially with the Chinese scorpion taxa.

The present situation of Chinese *Chaerilus* species is far from satisfactory. Taxonomic work on this genus would have been significantly more straightforward had no new species been described from China. Considering the difficulty in obtaining topotypes and the mysterious loss of type material, I am most likely not going to undertake a deeper revision for these taxa. In light of the current observations, it may be more reliable to focus on chela morphology (e. g., geometry and carinae), PTC (though of limited utility), and DSC during interspecific comparison within this genus. Additional sources of differential characters (e. g., CPM) should be investigated with scrutiny when relying on external morphology to discriminate species. Distinctions may potentially lie in other

segments of the pedipalp, but whenever a diagnostic feature is proposed, it should be founded upon rigorous analyses based on a relatively large sample size with unambiguous definitions. Authors should, at a minimum, provide the key diagnostic data of all specimens they claim to have examined, especially with their new species. Given the fragmentary nature of taxonomic endeavors at the global scale, scholars are obliged to explicitly articulate their theoretical premises and acknowledge potential errors underlying their analyses, enabling effective evaluation by another party.

As a final note, I find it particularly perplexing that none of the previous Chinese authors had identified the deficiencies within the existing morphological characterization of this genus, instead adhering to conventional but deficient procedures uncritically (methodological stagnation). These definitional ambiguities and practical obstacles should have been immediately apparent to anyone possessing the specimens for examination. Even if some of these problems remain currently unresolved, they ought to be explicitly acknowledged by any professional researchers in their studies. While I consider all nine previous Chinese species as valid, this conclusion is based primarily on supposed differences from the original descriptions, which often lack objective supporting evidence, rendering it preliminary at best. In particular, *C. tessellatus* most likely represents a *nomen dubium*, while four other species, namely *C. mainlingensis*, *C. pseudoconchiformis*, *C. tryznai*, and *C. wrzecionkoi* warrant revised characterizations. Given my extensive firsthand experience with domestic scorpological literature and the multiple deficiencies I have already identified (some of which remain unpublished due to the sample size required for reliably reassessing their taxonomic decisions; e. g., species delimitations based on a handful of non-diagnostic characters, color descriptions from long-preserved specimens, failure to compare their “new” species with another almost identical congener they described from the very same locality, alongside other typical errors already criticized in the current study), I find it regrettably essential to critically assess the claims put forth by those authors. This presupposition, somewhat reminiscent of a genetic fallacy, may in hindsight prove unduly prejudiced, but it remains a necessary stance given the ubiquitous absence of adequate substantiations in those works. Another notable instance in the genus *Chaerilus* exemplified by these Chinese authors was their use of a clearly immature specimen (15.8 mm; Lourenço et al., 2010: 81) for the description of *C. thai* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2010. It is excusable when the presentation of species morphology is constrained by the then available (or even conceivable) equipment; however, these authors never provided subsequent redescriptions or supplementary works with detailed photographs to clarify their original characterizations. Instead, they irresponsibly left their species inadequately described for nearly two decades whilst describing other new species, forcing others to rectify their numerous oversights. It is also natural to occasionally commit mistakes; however, these authors rarely acknowledged or corrected them. Instead, they often conveniently recycled their earlier works as if they are flawless, perpetuating the originally

avoidable errors. Furthermore, when inconsistencies arose, the authors seldom, if ever, clarified their underlying causes. What is more troubling, as revealed in the current study, is the sporadic provision of important data limited to their MS dissertations. Many naïve amateur Chinese scorpion and arachnid enthusiasts often idolize their revered gurus, valuing them for the sheer number of papers and/or new species they have published. Works done by the previous Chinese scorpologists hardly adopted a holistic perspective that incorporates references from species distributed beyond China. This limited scope likely contributed to the superficiality in their taxonomic decisions. It is important to note that species are not confined by national boundaries, and valuable insights can often be drawn from foreign taxa. Specialists should consider broadening their focus and strategically exploring other fields.

The situation took an even more absurd turn when a newly emerging Chinese scorpologist recently argued that it was inappropriate for the journal *Euscorpius* to have not sought reviews from Chinese scholars regarding a scorpion I described, *Q. solegladi*, as his argument is but a subjective aversion rooted in unfounded rationales towards the name. This contention was conveyed to a Chinese amateur infamous for denigrating my work whilst engaging in kleptoparasitic exploitation of my contributions, who then disseminated their ludicrous conversation among other Chinese scorpion hobbyists, only to further stigmatize me during a recent cyberbullying event collectively instigated by several Chinese scholars belonging to external cliques—none of whom even studies scorpions (e. g., Yejie Lin from Chinese Academy of Sciences, and Michael Lee from University of California, Riverside; see the ResearchGate figure gallery and supplementary file “Factanonverba” of Tang (2022)). Ironically, this very scorpologist committed a notorious blunder characteristic of Chinese scorpology by comparing his new species with an immature specimen (corrected upon my review). The baseless critiques from those Chinese scholars against me, coupled with their incompetence, together constitute a paradoxical farce. What they have always been attempting to do is nothing short of coercing me to embrace their nonsensical “convention” (cognitive inertia)—unfortunately for them, I was never born a traditionalist. Rebellion has cursed me with ordeals, but conformism would have condemned me to affliction. My contempt for early Chinese scorpologists has only deepened, reinforced by their numerous irresponsible deeds beyond their flawed and self-contradictory taxonomic decisions. These actions include plagiarism in MS dissertations (or self-plagiarism in published papers), inaccurate retrospective estimation of coordinates, concealment of more precise type localities, and failure to properly maintain type specimens. While I am likely to collaborate with them in resolving long-standing taxonomic issues surrounding Chinese scorpions in another universe, such a harmonious utopia is but a fantasy, given the entrenched infantile psychology prevalent among many contemporary Chinese scholars and amateurs who censured me without proposing any professional or effective argument,

instead constantly via mere whimsical sophistries (enraptured in particular by the red herring fallacy) and inferior cyber violence. Such a preposterous mindset ultimately contributed to the various antagonistic incidents, even though I had never personally been in any active conflicts with them. This concatenation underscores the persistent and regrettable shortcomings in contemporary Chinese scorpiology—a state of affairs that prompted me to continue pursuing research independently as an amateur researcher and ultimately gave rise to my aggressive tone in the current paper.

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References

- BASTAWADE, D. B. 1985. Scorpions (Arachnida). *Records of the Zoological Survey of India*, 82(1–4): 259–262.
- BASTAWADE, D. B. 2006. Arachnida: Scorpionida, Uropygi, Schizomida and Oncopodid Opiliones (Chelicerata). *Zoological Survey of India. Fauna of Arunachal Pradesh, State Fauna Series*, 13: 449–465.
- BENTON, T. G. 1991. The life history of *Euscorpium flavicaudis* (Scorpiones, Chactidae). *The Journal of Arachnology*, 19: 105–110.
- BURBRINK, F. T., E. A. MYERS & R. A. PYRON. 2024. Understanding species limits through the formation of phylogeographic lineages. *Ecology and Evolution*, 14: 1–18.
- BURRIEL-CARRANZA, B., M. ESTARELLAS, G. RIAÑO, A. TALAVERA, H. TEJERO-CICUÉNDEZ, J. ELS & S. CARRANZA. 2023. Species boundaries to the limit: integrating species delimitation methods is critical to avoid taxonomic inflation in the case of the Hajar banded ground gecko (*Trachydactylus hajarensis*). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 186(4): 107834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2023.107834>
- CAIN, S., E. GEFEN & L. PRENDINI. 2021. Systematic revision of the sand scorpions, genus *Buthacus* Birula, 1908 (Buthidae C.L. Koch, 1837) of the Levant, with redescription of *Buthacus arenicola* (Simon, 1885) from Algeria and Tunisia. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History*, 450: 1–134.
- COYNE, J. A. & H. A. ORR. 2004. *Speciation*. Sunderland, Massachusetts: Sinauer Associates, 545 pp.
- DI, Z.-Y. 2009. [Faunistic Study of Scorpion Taxonomy from the Three Provinces of Tibet, Yunnan, and Hainan in China (Chelicerata: Arachnida)]. M.S. thesis, 211 pp. Hebei University. Hebei Province, China. [unpublished, in Chinese].
- DI, Z.-Y., Y.-L. WU, Z.-J. CAO, L.-Q. FAN & W.-X. LI. 2009. The genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae) in China, with a description of the female *C. tricostatus* Pocock, 1899. *Arthropoda Selecta*, 18: 131–138.
- DI, Z.-Y., X.-B. XU, Z.-J. CAO, Y.-L. WU & W.-X. LI. 2013. Notes on the scorpions (Arachnida, Scorpiones) from Xizang with the redescription of *Scorpiops jendeki* Kovařík, 2000 (Scorpiones, Euscorpiidae) from Yunnan (China). *ZooKeys*, 301: 51–99.
- DI, Z.-Y., Z.-Z. YANG, S.-J. YIN, Z.-J. CAO & W.-X. LI. 2014. History of study, updated checklist, distribution and key of scorpions (Arachnida: Scorpiones) from China. *Zoological Research*, 35(1): 3–19.
- DI, Z.-Y., Z.-Z. YANG, Z.-J. CAO, Y.-L. WU & W.-X. LI. 2015. [The scorpion fauna of China (Chelicerata: Arachnida)]. *Acta Arachnologica Sinica*, 24: 109–115. [in Chinese].
- DI, Z.-Y. & M.-S. ZHU. 2009. A new species of *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae) from China. *Acta Arachnologica*, 58: 97–102.
- DU, S.-Y., Q. XUAN, R. J. HOWARD, Y.-H. WANG, M. S. ENGEL & C.-Y. CAI. 2024. A genome-scale phylogeny of scorpions: model comparison and modeling among-site compositional heterogeneity. *Palaeoentomology*, 007(6): 792–801.
- DUPRÉ, G. 2016. Dictionary of scientific scorpion names. *Arachnides*, 78: 1–68.
- FET, V. 2000. Family Chaerilidae Pocock, 1893. Pp. 323–328 in Fet, V., W. D. Sissom, G. Lowe & M. E. Braunwalder (eds.). *Catalog of the Scorpions of the World (1758–1998)*. New York: The New York Entomological Society, 689 pp.
- FOERSTER, S. I. A. 2025. Body size prediction in scorpions: a phylogenetic comparative examination of linear measurements of individual body parts. *PeerJ*, 13(12): 1–24.
- FORDE, A., A. JACOBSEN, M. M. DUGON & K. HEALY. 2022. Scorpion species with smaller body sizes and narrower chelae have the highest venom potency. *Toxins*, 14(3): 219.

- FOX, G. A., A. M. COOPER & W. K. HAYES. 2015. The dilemma of choosing a reference character for measuring sexual size dimorphism, sexual body component dimorphism, and character scaling: cryptic dimorphism and allometry in the scorpion *Hadrurus arizonensis*. *PLoS ONE*, 10(3): e0120392. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0120392>
- HENDERSON, J. R. 1913. Zoological Results of the Arbor Expedition 1911-1912. Arachnida, I. C. Scorpiones. *Records of the Indian Museum*, 8: 128–133.
- HJELLE, J. T. 1990. Anatomy and morphology. Pp. 5–30 in: Polis, G. A. (ed.). *The Biology of Scorpions*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- HUBER, B. A., H. SZYMAŃSKI & A. BENNETT-WEST. 2024. Progress or burden? Formal description of every apparently new species available in collections is neither necessary nor useful. *ZooKeys*, 1214: 77–90.
- JOSHI, M., M. ESPELAND, P. HUEMER, J. DEWAARD & M. MUTANEN. 2024. Species delimitation under allopatry: genomic insights within and across continents in Lepidoptera. *Insect Systematics and Diversity*, 8(5): 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isd/ixae027>
- KARBSTEIN, K., L. KÖSTERS, L. HODAČ, M. HOFMANN, E. HÖRANDL, S. TOMASELLO, N. D. WAGNER, B. C. EMERSON, D. C. ALBACH, S. SCHEU, S. BRADLER, J. DE VRIES, I. IRISARRI, H. LI, P. SOLTIS, P. MÄDER & J. WÄLDCHEN. 2024. Species delimitation 4.0: integrative taxonomy meets artificial intelligence. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 39(8): 771–784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.11.002>
- KLOOCK, C. T. 2009. Reducing scorpion fluorescence via prolonged exposure to ultraviolet light. *Journal of Arachnology*, 37: 368–370.
- KOCH, C. L. 1845. Die Arachniden. Nürnberg: C. H. Zech'sche Buchhandlung, 11, 174 pp.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 1998. *Štíři* [Scorpiones]. Jihlava (Czech Republic): Madagaskar Publishing House, 176 pp. [in Czech].
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2000. Revision of family Chaerilidae (Scorpiones), with descriptions of three new species. *Serket*, 7: 38–77.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2001. Catalog of the Scorpions of the World (1758-1998) by V. Fet, W. D. Sissom, G. Lowe, and M. Braunwalder (New York Entomological Society, 2000: pp. 690). Discussion and supplement for 1999 and part of 2000. *Serket*, 7(3): 78–93.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2005. *Chaerilus pictus* (Pocock, 1890). *Akva tera forum*, 2005: 1.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2012. Five new species of *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 from China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Euscorpius*, 149: 1–14.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2018. Notes on the genera *Buthacus*, *Compsobuthus*, and *Lanzatus* with several synonymies and corrections of published characters (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpius*, 269: 1–12.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. 2019. *Chaerilus alberti* sp. n. from Malaysia (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Euscorpius*, 274: 1–9.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. & G. LOWE. 2012. Review of the genus *Neobuthus* Hirst, 1911 with description of a new species from Ethiopia (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpius*, 138: 1–25.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. & G. LOWE. 2022. Scorpions of the Horn of Africa (Arachnida, Scorpiones). Part XXVIII. Scorpions of Djibouti. *Euscorpius*, 357: 1–31.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, D. HOFEREK, M. FORMAN & J. KRÁL. 2015. Two new *Chaerilus* from Vietnam (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae), with observations on growth and maturation of *Chaerilus granulatus* sp. n. and *C. hofereki* Kovarik et al., 2014. *Euscorpius*, 213: 1–21.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, K. B. RANAWANA, D. HOFEREK, V. A. S. JAYARATHNE, J. PLÍŠKOVÁ & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2016a. Scorpions of Sri Lanka (Arachnida, Scorpiones: Buthidae, Chaerilidae, Scorpionidae) with description of four new species of the genera *Charmus* Karsch, 1879 and *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972, stat. n. *Euscorpius*, 220: 1–133.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, M. STOCKMANN & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2020. Two new *Chaerilus* from Thailand and Laos (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Euscorpius*, 324: 1–20.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2016b. Scorpions of the Horn of Africa (Arachnida: Scorpiones). Part IX. *Lanzatus*, *Orthochirus*, and *Somalicharmus* (Buthidae), with Description of *Lanzatus somalilandus* sp. n. and *Orthochirus afar* sp. n. *Euscorpius*, 232: 1–38.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2018. Three new *Chaerilus* from Malaysia (Tioman Island) and Thailand (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae), with a review of *C. cimrmani*, *C. sejnai* and *C. tichyi*. *Euscorpius*, 268: 1–27.

- KOVAŘÍK, F., V. FET, B. GANTENBEIN, M. R. GRAHAM, E. A. YAĞMUR, F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ, N. M. POVERENNYI & N. E. NOVRUZOV. 2022a. A revision of the genus *Mesobuthus* Vachon, 1950, with a description of 14 new species (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpium*, 348: 1–189.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ & P. JUST. 2022b. The genus *Barbaracurus* in Saudi Arabia (Scorpiones: Buthidae), with description of a new species. *Euscorpium*, 365: 1–27.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, M. STOCKMANN & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2020. Two new *Chaerilus* from Thailand and Laos (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Euscorpium*, 324: 1–20.
- KOVAŘÍK, F. & A. A. OJANGUREN-AFFILASTRO. 2013. *Illustrated catalog of scorpions. Part II. Bothriuridae; Chaerilidae; Buthidae I. Genera Compsobuthus, Hottentotta, Isometrus, Lychas, and Sassanidotus*. Prague: Clairon Production, 400 pp.
- KRAEPELIN, K. 1894. Revision der Scorpione. II. Scorpionidae und Bothriuridae. *Beiheft zum Jahrbuch der Hamburgischen Wissenschaftlichen Anstalten*, 11: 1–248.
- KRAEPELIN, K. 1899. Scorpiones und Pedipalpi. In Dahl, F. (ed.). *Das Tierreich. Herausgegeben von der Deutschen Zoologischen Gesellschaft*. Berlin: R. Friedlander und Sohn Verlag, 8 (Arachnoidea): 1–265.
- KRAEPELIN, K. 1913. Neue Beiträge zur Systematik der Gliederspinnen. III. A. Bemerkungen zur Skorpionenfauna Indiens. B. Die Skorpione, Pedipalpen und Solifugen Deutsch-Ost-Afrikas. *Mitteilungen aus dem Naturhistorischen Museum (2. Beiheft zum Jahrbuch der Hamburgischen Wissenschaftlichen Anstalten, 1912)*, 30: 123–196.
- LÊ, S., J. JOSSE & F. HUSSON. 2008. FactoMineR: an R package for multivariate analysis. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25(1): 1–18.
- LIU, Y.-Q., S.-R. LI, Y.-T. LI, X.-R. WANG, H.-Z. ZHANG, W.-J. WU, Z.-J. CAO, K. HUANG & Y.-L. WU. 2024. Differential fluorescence features and recovery speeds of different scorpion exoskeleton parts during the molting process. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 316, 124309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2024.124309>
- LÓPEZ-CABRERA, D., G. RAMOS-ORTIZA, E. GONZÁLEZ-SANTILLÁN & R. ESPINOSA-LUNA. 2020. Characterization of the fluorescence intensity and color tonality in the exoskeleton of scorpions. *Journal of Photochemistry & Photobiology, B: Biology*, 209, 111945: 1–9.
- LORIA, S. F., V. L. EHRENTAL, A. D. NGUYEN & L. PRENDINI. 2022. Climate relicts: Asian scorpion family Pseudochactidae survived Miocene aridification in caves of the Annamite Mountains. *Insect Systematics and Diversity*, 6(6): 1–21.
- LORIA, S. F. & L. PRENDINI. 2014. Homology of the lateral eyes of Scorpiones: a six-ocellus model. *PLoSOne*, 9: e112913.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. 2012. Fluorescence in scorpions under UV light; can chaerilids be a possible exception? *Comptes Rendus Biologies*, 335: 731–734.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. 2018. The evolution and distribution of noxious species of scorpions (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 24(1): 1–12.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. 2019. The genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae) in Vietnam with the description of a new species. *Arachnology*, 17(7): 45–53.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. 2020. The coevolution between telson morphology and venom glands in scorpions (Arachnida). *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 26: 1–8.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. 2023. The remarkable micro-scorpion genus *Microbuthus* Kraepelin, 1898 in North Africa; description of a new species with comments on its biogeography and ecology (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Serket*, 20(1): 1–10.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. & B. DUHEM. 2010. The genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae) in the Himalayas and description of a new species. *Zookeys*, 37: 13–25.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. & A. ROSSI. 2019. The cave population of *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 from Palawan, Philippines, and description of a new species (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Comptes Rendus Biologies*, 342: 45–53.
- LOURENÇO, W. R., D. SUN & M.-S. ZHU. 2010. A new species of *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae) from Thailand. *The Raffles Bulletin of Zoology*, 58(1): 79–85.
- LOURENÇO, W. R., T.-H. TRAN & D.-S. PHAM. 2020. The genus *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877, in Vietnam with the description of a new species found in a volcanic cave (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae). *Bulletin de la Société entomologique de France*, 125(1): 19–28.
- LOURENÇO, W. R. & E. YTHIER. 2021. A particular new species of *Orthochirus* Karsch, 1891 from Somalia (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Serket*, 17(4): 335–349.

- LOURENÇO, W. R. & E. YTHIER. 2024. A new cave species of *Chaerilus* Simon, 1877 from Myanmar (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Revista Ibérica de Aracnología*, 44: 51–56.
- LOWE, G. 2010. New picobuthoid scorpions (Scorpiones: Buthidae) from Oman. *Euscorpius*, 93: 1–53.
- LOWE, G. 2024. Star-studded stingers: fluorescent sensilla on the scorpion aculeus (Arachnida, Scorpiones). *Euscorpius*, 402: 1–39.
- LOWE, G. & V. FET. 2024. A survey of proximal sensilla associated with denticle subrows on scorpion pedipalp fingers (Arachnida: Scorpiones), with observations on scorpion fluorescence. *Euscorpius*, 382: 1–107.
- LOWE, G. & F. KOVAŘÍK. 2019. Review of *Grosphus* Simon, 1880, with description of *Teruelius* gen. n., a new buthid genus from Madagascar (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpius*, 281: 1–128.
- LOWE, G. & F. KOVAŘÍK. 2022. Reanalysis of *Teruelius* and *Grosphus* (Scorpiones: Buthidae) with descriptions of two new species. *Euscorpius*, 356: 1–105.
- LOWE, G., F. KOVAŘÍK, M. STOCKMANN, MARK & F. STAHLAVSKY. 2019. *Trypanothacus* gen. n., a new genus of burrowing scorpion from the Arabian Peninsula (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpius*, 2019: 1–30.
- MASON, N. A., N. K. FLETCHER, B. A. GILL, W. C. FUNK & K. R. ZAMUDIO. 2020. Coalescent-based species delimitation is sensitive to geographic sampling and isolation by distance. *Systematics and Biodiversity*, 0(0): 1–12.
- MNHN-RS-RS8623. *Chaerilus tessellatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005. Paratype female. *Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France* (accessed 5. XI. 2024). <https://science.mnhn.fr/institution/mnhn/collection/rs/item/rs8623?listIndex=10&listCount=22>
- MONJARAZ-RUEDAS, R., R. W. MENDEZ & M. HEDIN. 2023. Species delimitation, biogeography, and natural history of dwarf funnel web spiders (Mygalomorphae, Hexurellidae, *Hexurella*) from the United States / Mexico borderlands. *ZooKeys*, 1167: 109–157.
- NAVIDPOUR, S. & G. LOWE. 2009. Revised diagnosis and redescription of *Apistobuthus susanae* (Scorpiones, Buthidae). *The Journal of Arachnology*, 37: 45–59.
- PÉREZ, S. M. 1974. Un inventario preliminar de los escorpiones de la región Paleártica y claves para la identificación de los géneros de la región Paleártica Occidental. *Madrid: Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Facultad de Ciencias, Departamento de Zoología, Cátedra de Artrópodos*, 7: 1–45.
- POCOCK, R. I. 1890. Description of a new genus and species of scorpion belonging to the group Jurini. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, 6 (5): 250–252.
- POCOCK, R. I. 1894a. Scorpions from the Malay Archipelago. Pp. 84–100 in M. Weber (ed.). *Zoologische Ergebnisse einer Reise in Niederlandisch Ost-Indien*, 3: 84–99. Leiden: Verlag von E. J. Brill.
- POCOCK, R. I. 1894b. A small contribution to our knowledge of the scorpions of India. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, 6(13): 72–84.
- POCOCK, R. I. 1899. Descriptions of six new species of scorpions from India. *Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society*, 12: 262–268.
- POCOCK, R. I. 1900. *Arachnida. The Fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Published under the authority of the Secretary of State for India in Council. London: W. T. Blandford, xii, 279 pp.
- PRENDINI, L., V. L. EHRENTAL & S. F. LORIA. 2021. Systematics of the relictual Asian scorpion family Pseudochactidae Gromov, 1998, with a review of cavernicolous, troglobitic, and troglomorphic scorpions. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History*, 453: 1–149.
- QI, J.-X., M.-S. ZHU & W. R. LOURENÇO. 2005. Eight new species of the genera *Scorpiops* Peters, *Euscorpiops* Vachon, and *Chaerilus* Simon (Scorpiones: Euscorpiidae, Chaerilidae) from Tibet and Yunnan, China. *Euscorpius*, 32: 1–40.
- QUEIROZ de, K.. 2007. Species concepts and species delimitation. *Systematic Biology*, 56(6): 879–886.
- RANASINGHE, U. G. S. L., J. THORMANN, S. P. BENJAMIN, A. BEZDEK, J. EBERLE & D. AHRENS. 2023. Contrasting results of multiple species delimitation approaches cause uncertainty in synecological studies: A case study on Sri Lankan chafers. *Insect Conservation and Diversity*, 16(6): 870–885. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12684>
- SANCHEZ-PIÑERO, F., F. URBANO-TENORIO & L. PUERTA-RODRÍGUEZ. 2024. Foraging strategies, prey selection and size- and microhabitat-related diet variation in *Buthus*.
- SANTIAGO-BLAY, J. A., V. FET, M. E. SOLEGLAD & S. R. ANDERSON. 2004. A new genus and subfamily of scorpions from Lower Cretaceous Burmese amber (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Revista Ibérica de Aracnología*, 9: 3–14.

- SHARMA, P. P., C. M. BAKER, J. G. COSGROVE, J. E. JOHNSON, J. T. OBERSKI, R. J. RAVEN, M. S. HARVEY, S. L. BOYER & G. GIRIBET. 2018. A revised dated phylogeny of scorpions: phylogenomic support for ancient divergence of the temperate Gondwanan family Bothriuridae. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 122: 37–45.
- SHARMA, P. P., R. FERNÁNDEZ, L. A. ESPOSITO, E. GONZÁLEZ-SANTILLÁN & L. MONOD. 2015. Phylogenomic resolution of scorpions reveals multilevel discordance with morphological phylogenetic signal. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B, Biological Sciences*, 282: 20142953.
- SIMON, E. 1877. Études arachnologiques. 6e Memoire. X. Arachnides nouveaux ou peu connus. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France, Séries 1-6*, 7: 225–242.
- SISSOM, W. D., G. A. POLIS & D. D. WATT. 1990. Field and laboratory methods. Pp. 215–221 in: Polis, G. A. (ed.). *The Biology of Scorpions*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & V. FET. 2003a. The scorpion sternum: structure and phylogeny (Scorpiones: Orthosterni). *Euscorpium*, 5: 1–34.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & V. FET. 2003b. High-level systematics and phylogeny of the extant scorpions (Scorpiones: Orthosterni). *Euscorpium*, 11: 1–175.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & W. D. SISSOM, 2001. Phylogeny of the family Euscorpiidae Laurie, 1896: a major revision. Pp. 25–111 in Fet, V. & P.A. Selden (eds.). *Scorpions 2001. In memoriam Gary A. Polis*. Burnham Beeches, Bucks: British Arachnological Society.
- SOUSA, P., M. A. ARNEDO & D. HARRIS, DAVID. 2017. Updated catalogue and taxonomic notes on the Old-World scorpion genus *Buthus* Leach, 1815 (Scorpiones, Buthidae). *ZooKeys*, 686: 15–84.
- STAHNKE, H. L. 1970. Scorpion nomenclature and mensuration. *Entomological News*, 81(12): 297–316.
- SUN, D. 2010. [Taxonomy and Status of Resources of the Scorpiones from China (Chelicerata: Arachnida)]. M.S. thesis, 274 pp. Hebei University. Hebei Province, China. [unpublished, in Chinese].
- SUN, D. & Z.-N. SUN. 2011. Notes on the genus *Mesobuthus* (Scorpiones: Buthidae) in China, with description of a new species. *The Journal of Arachnology*, 39: 59–75.
- TAKASHIMA, H. 1945. [Scorpions of Eastern Asia]. *Acta Arachnologica*, 9(3-4): 68–106. [in Japanese].
- TANG, V. 2022a. A standardized list of scorpion names in Chinese, with an etymological approach. *Euscorpium*, 350: 1–91. Supplementary file (updated checklist) available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369762475_A_standardized_list_of_scorpion_names_in_Chinese_with_an_etymological_approach
- TANG, V. 2022b. Scorpions of China: an updated catalogue with comments on some taxonomic issues (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Euscorpium*, 355: 1–18.
- TANG, V. 2022c. A new species of *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from Yunnan Province, China, with a preliminary review of its congeners in Yunnan (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae). *Euscorpium*, 360: 1–45.
- TANG, V. 2023. Description of the adult male *Scorpiops tongtongi* Tang, 2022, with further comments on the genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 in China (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae). *Euscorpium*, 377: 1–52.
- TANG, V. 2024a. Scorpion external morphology glossary. *Zenodo*. 32 pp. <https://zenodo.org/records/13310174>
- TANG, V. 2024b. Confirmation of basitarsal compound slit sensilla (BCSS) in scorpion genera *Chaerilus* and *Scorpiops* (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Zenodo*. 29 pp. <https://zenodo.org/records/13310127>
- TANG, V. 2025. A review of scorpiofauna of China: nomenclatural notes and updated faunistic catalog (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Euscorpium*, 404: 1–24.
- TANG, V., Q.-Q. JIA & L. LIU. 2023. A new monotypic genus and species from China, *Langxie feti* gen. et sp. n. (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpium*, 370: 1–101.
- TANG, V. & Z.-B. LIU. 2024. Albinism in *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879) (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpium*, 396: 1–33.
- TANG, V., Z.-B. LIU, M. R. GRAHAM, V. FET, F. KOVAŘÍK & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2024a. Revision of the genus *Olivierus* in Xinjiang, China, with comments on *Mesobuthus thersites* (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpium*, 383: 1–58.
- TANG, V., K.-C. OUYANG, Z.-B. LIU & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2024b. Three new species of genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from Tibet, China (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae), with implications for the diagnostic values of qualitative characters. *Euscorpium*, 394: 1–40.
- TARKHNISHVILI, D. 2024. Molecular markers and taxonomic explosion in herpetology: more or less robust taxonomy? True and false advantages of DNA markers. *International Journal of Zoology and Animal Biology*, 7(2): 1–14.

- ERUEL, R. & A. K. TIETZ. 2008. The true identity of *Rhopalurus pinto* Mello-Leitão, 1932, with notes on the status and distribution of *Rhopalurus crassicauda* Caporiacco, 1947 (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpius*, 70: 1–14.
- TIKADER, B. K. & D. B. BASTAWADE. 1983. Scorpions (Scorpionida: Arachnida). In *The Fauna of India*, Vol. 3. (Edited by the Director). Calcutta: Zoological Survey of India, 671 pp.
- WU, W., W.-L. NG, J.-X. YANG, W.-M. LI & X.-J. GE. 2018. High cryptic species diversity is revealed by genome-wide polymorphisms in a wild relative of banana, *Musa itinerans*, and implications for its conservation in subtropical China. *BMC Plant Biology*, 18: 194.
- VENCES, M., A. MIRALLES & C. DUFRESNES. 2024. Next-generation species delimitation and taxonomy: implications for biogeography. *Journal of Biogeography*, 00: 1–14.
- WIKIPEDIA. Tibet Autonomous Region - Administrative divisions of Tibet Autonomous Region. (accessed 14. XI. 2024). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tibet_Autonomous_Region
- XUAN, Q., C.-Y. CAI & D.-Y. HUANG. 2022. Immature chaerilid scorpions from mid-Cretaceous amber of northern Myanmar (Arachnida: Scorpiones: Chaeriloidea). *Cretaceous Research*, 144(1): 64–101.
- XUAN, Q., L. PRENDINI, M. S. ENGEL, C.-Y. CAI & D.-Y. HUANG. 2025. Extinct scorpion family Chaerilobuthidae from Mid-Cretaceous Burmese amber reinterpreted as subfamily of extant family Pseudochactidae (Chelicerata: Scorpiones). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 203: 1–60.
- YANG, X.-F. 2008. [*Scorpion Fauna and Taxonomy in China (Chelicerata: Arachnida)*]. M.S. thesis, 108 pp. Hebei University. Hebei Province, China. [unpublished, in Chinese].
- YIN, S.-J., Y.-N. QIU, Z.-H. PAN, S.-B. L. & Z.-Y. DI. 2015. *Chaerilus pseudoconchiformis* sp. n. and an updated key of the chaerilid scorpions from China (Scorpiones, Chaerilidae). *ZooKeys*, 495: 41–51.
- ZHU, M.-S., G.-X. HAN & W. R. LOURENÇO. 2008. The chaerilid scorpions of China (Scorpiones: Chaerilidae). *Zootaxa* 1943: 37–52.
- ZHU, M.-S., QI J.-X. & SONG D.-X. 2004. [A Checklist of Scorpions from China (Arachnida: Scorpiones)]. *Acta Arachnologica Sinica*, 13(2): 111–118. [in Chinese]